

**Analysis of capital structure and its effects on profitability:
Evidence from financial service companies in the UK**

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ABSTRACT

London, the capital of the United Kingdom (UK) is one of the leading financial hubs in the world and it is also known as the financial capital of Europe. In the UK, the major contributors to the UK's economy are the financial service companies (FSCs). However, FSCs in the UK have been critically affected by 2008-2009 global financial crisis. Besides, financial service companies faced a tough competition from FinTech industry sector. In this regard, profitability is regarded as one of the most important measurements of the success of FSCs in the UK. To cope with these challenges, acquiring more funds and deciding whether to rely on debt funds or equity funds has become a major issue. This study aims to study the capital structure and its effect on the profitability of the FSCs in the UK.

To build the foundation, this study builds the conceptual framework based on empirical studies from different industries and countries. The conceptual framework has helped this study to draw three different objectives, which are factors that influence the capital structure decision, relation between capital structure and profitability of the firm and the effect of capital structure on profitability of FSCs in the UK.

This study focuses on the financial service companies listed on the London Stock Exchange (LSE) from the period of 1998 to 2018. Data is collected from secondary sources such as annual reports of the sixty financial service Companies. The number of observations in this study is 1260. In this study, Pearson correlation and regression analysis have been deployed that makes this study a quantitative research with positivist philosophy and deductive approach.

The results of this study show that external factors such as inflation and interest rate have an impact on capital structure and profitability. Inflation has a positive impact on short-term debt and interest rate has a positive impact on long-term debt, total debt and debt to equity ratio. In addition, short-term debt is influenced by total assets and liquidity. On the other hand, long-term debt is influenced by total assets, firm age, earning per share, and effective tax rate.

In regard to the profitability, capital structure shows an impact on firm's profitability. Short-term debt and long-term debt have a negative effect on ROA and ROIC. In case of external factors, financial crisis has a negative effect on ROA and ROIC whereas inflation shows a positive effect. Besides, assets growth and earnings per share both show positive effect on ROA and ROIC. Furthermore, ROE and ROCE both negatively affect short-term debts and is positively affected by debt to equity ratio. Similar to RAO and ROIC, inflation has a positive effect and financial crisis shows a negative effect. Both assets growth and earnings per share show positive influence.

This study extends the previous study of Abor (2005) by supporting that debt has a negative impact on profitability. Further, it also widens the study of Nasimi (2016) by including more variables in the study. In addition, this study supports the findings of Abeywardhana (2016) where the results show that the smaller firms are less dependent on debt funds and the larger firms maintain higher debt level in the capital structure. This study provides a new argument to the study of Gill *et al.* (2011) where debts have a negative effect on the profitability of firms rather than the positive relation. In addition, this study challenges the study of Vuong *et al.* (2017) by showing that financial crisis has a negative impact on firms' profitability in the UK's market. On the other hand, this study contradicts with the findings of Bui (2017) by showing negative effect of debt on firms' profitability.

The present study recommends financial service companies in the UK to follow the trend of interest rate and inflation rate in order to reduce agency cost and maximise tax shield. In addition, this study recommends the financial service companies to increase debt borrowings and balance the equity financing. This research also provides guidance for future research to explore this study in qualitative method with primary data. In addition, it recommends exploration of more areas and extension of time period.

CONTENTS

	Page
CHAPTER ONE: Introduction -----	1-13
1.1 Introduction to the Study	1
1.2 Research Background	2
1.3 Research Rationale	5
1.4 Research Problems	8
1.5 Aim, Questions and Objectives of Research	9
1.6 Significance of the Research	10
1.7 Scope of the Study	10
1.8 Structure of the Research	11
1.9 Summary	13
CHAPTER TWO: Literature Review -----	14-39
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 Theoretical Reviews	15
2.2.1 Capital Structure Theories	15
2.2.2 Profitability Analysis	22
2.3 Review of Previous Studies	25
2.3.1 Capital Structure Affecting Profitability	25
2.3.2 Factors affecting Profitability	30
2.4 Summary of Empirical Literature	33
2.5 Summary	39
CHAPTER THREE: Research Frameworks -----	40-59
3.1 Introduction	40
3.2 Theoretical Frameworks	40
3.3 Conceptual Framework	51
3.4 Research Hypotheses	53
3.5 Operationalisation of the Independent Variables and Dependent Variables	55
3.6 Summary	59
CHAPTER FOUR: Research Methodology -----	60-79
4.1 Introduction	60
4.2 Research Paradigm	60
4.2.1 Ontology	61
4.2.2 Epistemology	62
4.3 Methodology	63
4.3.1 Research Philosophies	63
4.3.2 Other Research Philosophies	65
4.3.3 Research Approaches	66
4.3.4 Types of the Research	67
4.3.5 Research Design	68
4.4 Research Methods	70
4.4.1 Target Population	70
4.4.2 Sampling	71
4.4.3 Data Collection	72
4.4.4 Statistical Instrument	73
4.4 Summary	78

CHAPTER FIVE: Presentation of Data and Critical Discussion of the Results ---	80-172
5.1 Introduction	80
5.2 Descriptive Analysis of Variable	80
5.3 Correlation	86
5.4 Hypotheses Testing with Regression Analysis	89
5.5 Summary of Descriptive Findings	165
5.6 Summary of Correlation and Regression Analyses	166
5.7 Summary	167
CHAPTER SIX: Discussions -----	173-186
6.1 Introduction	173
6.2 Macro environments with control variables and capital structure	173
6.2.1 Macro environments	173
6.2.2 Control variables	176
6.2.3 Macro environment, capital structure with control variables and profitability	179
6.3 Summary	185
CHAPTER SEVEN: Conclusion and Recommendations -----	187-197
7.1 Introduction	187
7.2 Overview of the Study	187
7.3 Contribution of the Research	189
7.3.1 Theoretical and empirical Contributions	189
7.3.2 Contributions for Financial Service Companies	191
7.4 Recommendations	193
7.5 Limitations of the Study	195
7.6 Future Research	196
BIBLIOGRAPHY -----	198-233
APPENDICES -----	234-235

LIST OF TABLES

	Page
Table 1.1 Research Aim, Question and Objectives	9
Table 2.1 Capital Structure Affecting Profitability	33
Table 2.2 Factors affecting Profitability	36
Table 3.1 Operationalisation Table	55
Table 5.1 Descriptive Analysis of Variables	81
Table 5.2 Pearson Correlation Matrix	86
Table 5.3.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt	90
Table 5.3.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt	91
Table 5.3.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt	91
Table 5.3.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms of ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt	93
Table 5.3.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms of ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt	94
Table 5.3.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms of ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt	94
Table 5.4.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt	96
Table 5.4.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt	96
Table 5.4.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt	97
Table 5.4.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt	99

Table 5.4.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt	99
Table 5.4.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt	100
Table 5.5.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt	101
Table 5.5.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt	102
Table 5.5.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt	103
Table 5.5.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt	104
Table 5.5.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt	105
Table 5.5.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt	106
Table 5.6.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity	107
Table 5.6.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity	108
Table 5.6.3 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity	108
Table 5.6.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity	110

Table 5.6.5 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity	111
Table 5.6.6 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity	111
Table 5.7.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of STD	113
Table 5.7.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of STD	114
Table 5.7.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of STD	116
Table 5.7.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of INF and profitability in terms of ROIC with control variables such as TA and LR on capital structure in terms of STD	117
Table 5.7.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of INF and profitability in terms of ROIC with control variables such as TA and LR on capital structure in terms of STD	117
Table 5.7.6 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of INF and profitability in terms of ROIC with control variables such as TA and LR on capital structure in terms of STD	118
Table 5.8.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD	119
Table 5.8.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD	120
Table 5.8.3 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD	121
Table 5.8.4 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD	123

Table 5.8.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD	123
Table 5.8.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD	124
Table 5.9.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of TD ..	126
Table 5.9.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of TD	126
Table 5.9.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of TD ..	127
Table 5.9.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET on capital structure in terms of TD	129
Table 5.9.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET on capital structure in terms of TD	130
Table 5.9.6 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR, and ET on capital structure in terms of TD	130
Table 5.10.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of DE ..	132
Table 5.10.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of DE ..	133
Table 5.10.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of DE ..	134
Table 5.10.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as AG, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of DE	136

Table 5.10.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as AG, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of DE	136
Table 5.10.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as AG, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of DE	137
Table 5.11.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROA	138
Table 5.11.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROA	139
Table 5.11.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROA	139
Table 5.11.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROA	140
Table 5.11.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROA	141
Table 5.11.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROA	141
Table 5.12.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE	142
Table 5.12.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE	143
Table 5.12.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE	143
Table 5.12.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE	144
Table 5.12.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE	145
Table 5.12.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE	145
Table 5.13.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROIC	146
Table 5.13.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROIC	147

Table 5.13.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROIC	147
Table 5.13.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROIC	148
Table 5.13.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROIC	149
Table 5.13.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROIC	149
Table 5.14.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE	150
Table 5.14.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE	151
Table 5.14.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE	151
Table 5.14.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE	152
Table 5.14.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE	153
Table 5.14.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE	153
Table 5.15.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROA	155
Table 5.15.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROA	155
Table 5.15.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROA	156
Table 5.16.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROE	157
Table 5.16.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROE	158

Table 5.16.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROE	158
Table 5.17.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROIC	159
Table 5.17.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROIC	160
Table 5.17.3 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROIC	161
Table 5.18.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of LTDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET on profitability in terms of ROCE	162
Table 5.18.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of LTDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET on profitability in terms of ROCE	163
Table 5.18.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of LTDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET on profitability in terms of ROCE	163
Table 5.19 Descriptive Statistics	165
Table 5.20 Summary of hypotheses results model 1	168
Table 5.21 Summary of hypotheses results model 2	169
Table 5.22 Summary of hypotheses results model 3	170
Table 5.23 Summary of hypotheses results model 4	170

LIST OF FIGURES

	Page
Figure 1.1: Largest Global Net Exporters of Financial Services, 2017	6
Figure 1.2: Chained Volume Measure (CVM) Index of Financial Industries, UK	7
Figure 2.1: Net Income Approach	16
Figure 2.2: Net Operating Income Approach	18
Figure 2.3: Traditional Approach	20
Figure 3.1: Determinants of Capital Structure and their impact on firm performance	41
Figure 3.2: Change in Capital Structure impacts firm performance	42
Figure 3.3: Impact of Capital Structure on Performance	43
Figure 3.4: Capital Structure and its impact on Profitability	44
Figure 3.5: Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance	45
Figure: 3.6: Impact of Firm Leverage to Performance	46
Figure 3.7: Effects of Capital Structure on Profitability	47
Figure 3.8: Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance	48
Figure 3.9: Impact of Capital Structure and Firm Performance	49
Figure 3.10: Impact of Capital Structure and Firm Performance	50
Figure 3.11: Conceptual Framework	52
Figure 6.1 Average values of macro environment, capital structure and profitability	186

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the Study

In any business, profitability of a firm is considered as a basic requirement for a long-term survival and success. It affects growth, employee, innovation, technological change and its stakeholder (Yazdanfar, 2013). Any business that is not profitable cannot sustain in the long run. On the other hand, a profitable company has the ability to rewards its owners with a large return on their investment. Hence, profitability is the most significant measurement of success (Johanns and Hofstrand, 2009).

In this globalisation era, opportunities for investment have also increased, prompting the firms to increase their investment in both domestic and international markets (Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey, 2018; Nasimi, 2016). This leads to a rise in competition in the markets. In this demanding environment, the companies require sufficient funds for sustainability. Sources of the fund are obtained from various channels and these channels can be categorised into two major proportions, which are debt and equity (Nasimi, 2016). FSCs need to decide the best suitable source of funds that has the capability to generate more returns. Thus, a correct decision-making is critical as any error in the decisions could affect the firm's growth rate and its profitability as a whole (Abor, 2005 and Shahar *et al.*, 2015)

The combination of both debt and equity funds is known as capital structure (Brigham and Daves, 2004). Decision in terms of capital structure made by a finance manager is called as capital structure decision. Since capital is the cornerstone of any business entity, the relationship between capital structure and profitability of the firm cannot be excluded from the financial decision making in an organisation as interest paid on debt is a tax-deductible payment. As a result, mixture of debt capital with equity capital in capital structure of a firm improves its profitability (Akkucuk, 2015). Therefore, the relationship between capital structure and profitability of the firm is essential because it affects the profitability of the firm if effective decision on capital structure is maintained.

This chapter exhibits research background where discussion about the theory of capital structure and its effects on the performance of firm has been briefly discussed. Subsequently, a brief discussion regarding the financial service industry in the United Kingdom is covered. Various research problems are also discussed in this chapter in relation to empirical studies. Based on the industry and research problem, a research question, aim and objectives of the research are also covered in this chapter. In addition, expected outcome and contribution of this study is presented, including the scope of the research and the structure of the research.

1.2 Research Background

Capital structure is a mixture of both debt capital and equity capital (Nasimi, 2016). These sources involve use of short term debt, long term debt, preferred stock and common stock or equity financing (Mutairi, 2011; Javed *et al.*, 2014; Shahar *et al.*, 2015; Singh and Pandey, 2017). When a firm raises its capital, it is critical for the firm to make precise decision on capital structure as correct decision-making on capital structure can maximise the firm's value and incorrect decision could affect the profitability of the firm (Shahar *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, many business owners or managers aim to balance this financing mix and try to keep close to their target capital structure ratio (Myers and Majluf, 1984; Myers, 1984). However, firms do not use identical capital structure and it varies from one firm to another in terms of their financial decisions (Javed *et al.*, 2014) because it is a complex task for managers to take decision on capital structure. Nevertheless, when the risk of shareholder and the cost of debt is minimised, it can raise the growth of the firm and maximise the shareholders' wealth. In order to escalate the growth of the firm, finding the optimal capital structure is important for every firm so that the combination of debt and equity fund can maximise the wealth of shareholders or minimise the weighted average cost of capital. The evidence of capital structure that affects firm value and performance can be traced from the theory of Modigliani and Miller (1958). According to Modigliani and Miller's (1958) approach, the different combination of debt and equity (capital structure) does not affect the value of a firm (hence, performances) and the position of optimal capital structure does not exist.

Despite the theory of Modigliani and Miller's (1958) revelation of the value of firm not affected by capital structure or capital structure's irrelevance to firm value, the pioneering work in terms of theory of capital structure can be traced to Modigliani and Miller's (1958). Before this work, there was no generally approved theory of capital structure (Luigi and Sorin, 2009). However, this theory was proposed under perfect capital market conditions in which taxes, transaction costs and information asymmetry are avoided and the value of any firm is independent of its financing decisions (Modigliani and Miller 1958). Although, Modigliani and Miller's proof is not based on practical world, their assumption has become an important theory in the study of capital structure (Sheikh and Wang, 2010). The following assumptions (Shahar *et al.*, 2015) presented by them are discussed below. However, these assumptions are unsuitable in real world and for that matter, their theory has been criticised for being purely theoretical (Danso and Adomako, 2014).

- i. There are no transaction and bankruptcy costs in capital markets.
- ii. There are no different risk classes for firms.
- iii. There are no corporate taxes.
- iv. Cash flows are perpetuities.
- v. There are no information asymmetries for insiders and outsiders.
- vi. There are no moral hazards on manager's part and they work for shareholder's wealth maximisation.
- vii. Firms issue solely two varieties of claims: equity with risk and debt without risk.

Modigliani and Miller (1963) and Miller (1977) approach this issue more precisely, where MM theory includes corporate taxes into their theorem and brings out a corrected approach of their theory in their article. This approach is similar to net income approach, which is popularly known as theory of relevance (Ganesamoorthy, 2016). Since Miller and Modigliani (1963) incorporates corporate taxes into their new theory, capital structure shows an effect on the cost of capital and the value of firm. This is because interest payments on debt are deductible from firms' profit in the purpose of corporate taxation (Devereux *et al.*, 2006; Mooij, 2011). For instance, when the firms mix debt with equity in their capital structure, the overall cost of capital decreases because the cost of debt is cheaper than cost of equity, prompting the market value of firm to grow (Ganesamoorthy, 2016). In addition, when two levered and unlevered firms are compared and have equal earnings, the levered firm produces more earnings to their equity shareholders than the unlevered firm and thus, existence of

optimum capital structure can be seen from this. However, many studies criticise MM theory in terms of markets being imperfect. The theory assumes that there is no transaction cost but in reality the transaction costs exist in securities transactions. Such criticisms have led to develop capital structure theories in different angles. According to Danso and Adomako (2014), MM's (1963) have inspired other theories by suggesting more reliable assumptions in imperfect market conditions. There are three major theories of capital structure that emerge from MM's irrelevance theory, which are trade-off theory, pecking order theory and market timing theory (Luigi and Sorin, 2009). Amongst these theories, the most influential theories inspired by MM's irrelevance theory are trade-off model and pecking order model (Danso and Adomako, 2014).

The Trade-Off theory is the oldest theory which is connected to the theory of Miller and Modigliani on capital structure that emphasises on optimal capital structure. According to Kraus and Litzebnerger (1973) firms achieve optimal capital structures by trading off the cost against the benefits of the use of debt and equity upon consideration of market imperfections such as taxes, bankruptcy costs and agency costs. In other words, firm can achieve an optimal capital structure by adjusting debt and equity level, which means to balance tax shield and financial distress cost. Myers (1977) suggests that use of debt up to a certain level can balance the cost of financial distress and interest tax shield. According to Fama and French (2002) the optimal capital structure can be identified through the benefits of debt tax deductibility of interest and cost of bankruptcy and agency cost. However, this theory fails to consider the impact of information asymmetry on value of the firm. This criticism has led to development of pecking order theory that considers the conflicts between the insiders and the outsiders due to the different information at their hands (Mostafa and Boregowda, 2014; Abeywardhana, 2017).

Pecking order theory has been proposed by Myers and Majluf (1984) and Myers (1984). However, this theory does not consider optimal capital structure, which means there is no target capital structure (Luigi and Sorin, 2009; Mostafa and Boregowda, 2014). Besides information asymmetry between insiders and the outsiders, Myers and Majluf (1984) assume perfect market, similar to Modigliani and Miller's (1958) study. According to this theory, firms rely on internal sources with lowest information asymmetry costs, then debt and ultimately equity with highest information asymmetry costs. In addition, this theory claims that firms with more profitability issue less debt. However, results of many studies reveal that

pecking order does not explain capital structure entirely (Ganesamoorthy, 2016). Even though there are some supportive evidences, some studies fail to find supportive evidences to this theory (Boudry *et al.*, 2010).

Baker and Wurgler in their study (2002) provide a new approach of capital structure, called as “Market Timing Theory”. This theory explains the timing attempts of security issues. This theory claims that capital structure decision is dependent on the cost of relative securities. In another words, the decision to issue either debt or equity is based on the cost of this respective security, which means this security must be lower than each other. Furthermore, this theory suggests that issue of equity is preferred when the stocks are valued in the market over and above their book value. For instance, when the market value of equity is high, its cost of capital is low and it gives an advantage for the firm to minimise the cost by issuing equity. On the other hand, when the market value of equity is low, debt funds are more preferable to meet the financial requirements.

Having reviewed several theories of capital structure, it has been found that financial decision of the firms is to find optimal capital structure that brings the highest profits for the firms. However, these decisions are influenced by different factors. These factors can be both internal and external factors. Thus, the effect of capital structure on the profitability of the firms has been proposed in this study by taking the evidence from the Financial Service Companies (FSCs) in the UK.

1.3 Research Rationale

London is one of the financial centres in the world and the financial capital of Europe. Financial service companies are significant contributors to the economy of the UK. According to Rhodes (2018), in 2017, the financial service sector contributed £190 Billion to the country’s economy, which is 6.5 percent of total economic output. This sector is the largest in London, where 50 percent of the sector’s output was generated. Furthermore, this industry provides 1.1 million financial services jobs in the UK, which is 3.2 percent of all jobs in the UK. In addition, the trade surplus of this industry is larger than other exporting industries in the UK. In 2016, exports of UK financial services was worth £61 billion and imports was worth £11 billion, meaning that there was a surplus in financial services trade of £50 billion, out of which 44 percent of financial services exports went to the EU and 39

percent of financial services imports came from the European Union (EU) (Rhodes, 2018). This proves that the UK is the leading exporters of financial services in the world, followed by the USA, Switzerland and Luxembourg in 2017 (UNCTAB, 2018; TheCityUk, 2018) (see figure 1.1). This industry also contributes significantly to the UK's tax. In 2016/17 financial year, this sector contributed £27.3 billion in tax in the UK (Rhodes, 2018) and in 2017/18 financial year, it contributed £29 billion in tax in the UK (Browning, 2019). Therefore, if the companies in financial service sector in the UK encounter unavoidable difficulties and face profitability issues, the probability of its effect on the country's economy is extremely high.

Figure 1.1: Largest Global Net Exporters of Financial Services, 2017.

Source: UNCTAB, (2018). Data Centre. [Online]. Available at: <http://unctadstat.unctad.org/wds/ReportFolders/reportFolders.aspx> [Accessed 17 Jul. 2020].

During 2007 to 2009, global financial crisis has had a tremendous effect on the financial service sector in the UK. Figure 1.2 shows that this industry has been struggling to recover from the financial crisis. Evidently, Chained Volume Measure (CVM) of Financial Industries in the UK shows a plunge during the global financial crisis (Thomas, 2016). On top of this crisis, FSCs in the UK faced a strong competition from FinTech industry sector. During 2017, forty percent revenue of FSCs in the UK dropped with the effect of FinTech firms. Nevertheless, forty seven percent of the UK FSCs have a plan to invest in FinTech acquisition in the next coming three to five years (PWC, 2017; Johansson, 2017). Thus, while coping from catastrophic crisis and fierce competition, financing the business and acquiring funds come to combat the threads have become a major issue for the financial service

companies (FSCs) in the UK. The question is whether the companies should rely only on debt funds or on equity funds or even the combination of both. Balancing the funding structure has always been a tough task for many managers in the firms and this structure keeps the managers baffled. Therefore, structuring the capital has become a major issue for the financial service companies in the UK because the probability of bankruptcy increases with the increase in debt level. Therefore, it inflames a fear that company might not be able to generate sufficient profits to pay back its interest and the loans (Abor, 2005). Since the UK is the highest exporter of financial service in the world (see figure 1.1), the profitability of FSCs of the UK has an important role in the growth of the economy of the UK. Figure 1.2 shows that 2008/09 financial crisis has major impact on the profitability of FSCs in the UK. Therefore, examining the performance of FSCs has become an important issue for the benefit of FSCs and the economy of the UK. Thus, question regarding the impact of capital structure on the profitability of FSCs has also emerged.

Figure 1.2: Chained Volume Measure (CVM) Index of Financial Industries, UK.

Source: Thomas M. (2016), Office of National Statistics (2016).

Where:

SIC = UK Standard Industrial Classification 2007 (UK SIC (2007)).

SIC 64 = Financial services activities, except insurance and pension funding.

SIC 65 = Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social.

SIC 66 = Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance services.

1.4 Research Problems

Considering the need to examine the impact of capital structure on FSCs, the research investigates empirical evidence. However, the research fails to detect empirical evidence on the impact of capital structure on the performance of FSCs in the UK. Nonetheless, the research has been productive in revealing that several related investigations regarding the impact of capital structure on firm's performance have been reviewed previously by several scholars. Some studies are published recently by Nasimi (2016); Abeywardhana (2016); Bui (2017) and Vuong *et al.* (2017). However, all related empirical evidences have failed to produce specific answer to the problems of the FSCs. This is because all the empirical evidences are based on different industries such as small and medium enterprises manufacturing sector, FTSE-100 Index of London Stock Exchange (LSE), large companies listed in LSE and British Gas and Oil companies. This research also reveals that previous studies provide different reports depending on the industry sector.

In addition, the researcher has expanded the empirical evidence outside the British market and detected numerous studies related to the impact of capital structure on profitability. Some of the studies are Ganiyu (2015) that explores the Nigerian market, Abor (2005) that is based on the study of Ghana, Javed *et al.* (2014) that focuses their study in Pakistan, Nenu *et al.* (2018) that investigates the Romanian market, Basit and Irwan (2017) that investigates the Malaysian industrial sector, Dawar (2014) that involves review of Indian market, Ebaid (2009) that provides evidence from Egypt, Ebrati *et al.* (2013) that focuses their study in Iranian market, Evgney (2015) that explores the Russian market, Gill *et al.* (2011) that produces evidence from the United States of America, Saputra *et al.* (2015) that discusses the Indonesian financial industry, Vieira (2017) that provides the evidence in the Portuguese's perspective and Yazdanfar and Ohman (2014) whose research is based on Swedish market. Having reviewed the empirical evidence from the international markets, the researcher conceptualises that capital structure of the companies from developing economy and the companies from the developed economies contradict with theory of capital structure.

Evidently, the companies from developing nations maintain lower debt level than the companies from the developed nations. However, few studies based on developed nations detect that certain companies of the developed nations maintain low level of debts in their capital structure. This contradictory finding has led the researcher to raise the issue into three main questions (see table 1).

1.5 Aim, Questions and Objectives of Research

After finding contradictory evidences and the problems of the FSCs in the UK, this research aims to explore the impact of capital structure on the profitability in new area, which is the FSCs in the UK. This study focusses on three main objectives, which helps this study to achieve the set goals (see table 1).

Table 1.1: Research Aim, Question and Objectives.

Aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives
To determine the effects of capital structure on profitability and how these impact a firms' performance.	1. What are the main determinants of capital structure?	1. To identify the determinants of capital structure.
	2. Is there a significant relationship between capital structure and firm performance?	2. To analyse the relationship between capital structure and firm performance.
	3. Does capital structure affect the profitability of FSCs in UK?	3. To determine the impact of capital structure on FSCs' profit in the UK.

1.6 Significance of the Research

In this study, the researcher intends to investigate the impact of the capital structure on profitability of the firms. In addition, this study exhibits how well the companies are managing its financial resources in order to get satisfactory returns and the effectiveness of the companies' management from a stockholders' point of view. This research aims to contribute conceptual and practical understanding to FSCs' management, investors, researchers and other concerned Government departments through its research findings.

The present study will help the FSCs in the UK to understand the management of debts and equity funds to improve the profitability of the companies. In addition, it will be helpful for the financial service companies outside the UK and the financial service companies that are listed in the Stock Exchange of London but are not included in this study. In regard to investment, this study will be of assistance to the investors and to those who are intending to invest in the FSCs as they can refer to this study in order to judge the performance of the companies. This study can also become an important starting point for future research in the study of capital structure and the profitability of a firm. This study will also be beneficial for future research in related fields by means of exploring more or even in different area of studies covering different industries and variables, time periods, different models for evaluation and covering different locations. In addition, this study has the ability to provide an evidence for both public and private financial institutions, as such institutions can use this study to understand companies' debts, equity funds and profitability of financial firms. For instance, public corporations and banks can also use the findings of this study.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The focus of this study is on the effects of capital structure on profitability. The main concerns are studying the effects of independent variables which are short-term debt (STD), long-term debt (LTD, total debt (TD) and debt to equity (D/E) and internal factors such as assets size, assets growth, firm age, earning per share, liquidity, interest coverage and effective tax rate and external factors such as financial crisis, gross domestic product (GDP), inflation and bank interest rate on dependent variable which is profitability measured as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), return on invested capital (ROIC) and return on capital employed (ROCE). The target population of this study is the FSCs of the UK

which are listed on the Stock Exchange of London. At present, the Stock of Exchange of London, there are five hundred and forty-nine (549) financial service companies (FSCs) listed in LSE in total. Out of five hundred and forty-nine companies, sixty (60) companies have been chosen to participate in this study. To address the research questions and to achieve the stated aim and objectives of the research, this study uses Pearson correlation and linear regression analysis.

1.8 Structure of the Research

This study is structured into seven chapters. A brief description of each chapter of this study is presented here.

Chapter one contains general introduction to the present study. It describes the background of the research by revisiting capital structure theories which have been developed by different researchers. The situations of financial service companies in the UK are also covered briefly and problem statement is also discussed based on the previous empirical studies. Based on the research problem, framing of research questions and also development of the research aim and objectives are presented in this chapter. In addition, significance and scope of the study and research structure are also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter two contains the review of theoretical literature that is related to capital structure and profitability ratios. In this chapter, literature review is divided into two, which are theoretical review and empirical review. In theoretical review, the theories of capital structure and profitability ratios have been explored. Under empirical review, the study of different researchers on capital structure and its impact on profitability of the firms have been explored. In addition, previous studies on the determinants of profitability have also been reviewed in this chapter.

Chapter three of this study contains the review of theoretical framework where possible concepts or models have been covered. Having reviewed the related concepts, the research framework has been developed to investigate the impact of capital structure on the profitability of financial service companies in the UK. Research hypotheses have been constructed based on the theoretical framework.

Chapter four discusses philosophical arguments that underpin the selection of research method. This study follows the positivist philosophy as this research involves financial ratios which remain structured. In addition, deductive approach is employed in this study as this study develops the research idea and analyses the data to confirm the results. Since this research uses the secondary data from the annual reports of financial service companies (FSCs) in the UK, quantitative research is applied in this study. As this study involves examining the cause and effect of internal and external factors on capital structure and profitability of FSCs, explanatory research is employed for this study. In addition, this chapter discusses about the data collection for this study. The data is gathered from the 60 FSCs listed in London Stock Exchange (LSE) from 1998 to 2018. Therefore, 1,260 data have been used in this study. Furthermore, the details about the research instruments are explained in this chapter. To investigate the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, Pearson correlation is employed. On the other hand, to analyse the cause and effect of independent variables on dependent variables, regression analysis is applied in this study.

Chapter five contains discussion based on the results of the analyses. In this study, analyses are conducted in four models. Thus, all these four models are intensively discussed in this chapter. The analyses are conducted in three major statistics, namely descriptive statistics, correlation and regression. Besides, the summary of the analyses is also shown in this chapter where the findings of this study are shown.

Chapter six provides detailed discussion regarding the results of the analysis. This chapter put up critical discussion by comparing the results with different theories or literature. To be more specific, this chapter discusses the impact of all the independent variables on dependent variables.

Chapter seven includes conclusion and recommendation of the study. This chapter provides factual and conceptual conclusion, followed by research contributions. It also provides a recommendation based on the findings. In addition, this chapter discusses the limitation of this study and closes the chapter with suggestions for future research.

1.9 Summary

This chapter provides an introduction and a broad context of the study. A brief discussion about capital structure theories are discussed in this chapter which is followed by the review of the financial service companies in the market. Besides, this chapter explores previous studies to find a research gap. Having reviewed the situation of the financial service companies in the UK and research gap, the research questions are developed in this chapter. In relation to the research questions, the aims and objectives of this study are also developed. Furthermore, this chapter discusses significance, scope and structure of the research.

CHAPTER TWO

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Literature review is the use of ideas in the literature to explain the particular approach, methodology and to demonstrate that the research contributes something new (Hart, 1998). Further, it explains that effective literature review is a firm foundation for advancing knowledge (Webster and Watson, 2002). Literature review leads to development of theory and selection of new areas where further research is needed. Therefore, the process of literature review should explain how the research builds on another research work (Shaw, 1995). Hence, the related theoretical and empirical literature is discussed in this chapter to understand and build strong foundation for this research.

This chapter is divided into two sections. The first section explores the literature based on the theories of capital structure and profitability analysis. The main theories of capital structure reviewed in this chapter are net income approach, modigliani and miller Approach, net operating income approach, traditional approach, trade-off theory, agency cost theory, signalling theory, pecking order theory and market timing theory. In addition, the main investigated profitability ratios are gross profit margin, operating profit margin, net profit margin, return on assets, return on equity, return on invested capital and return on capital employed. The second section covers the empirical literature review. This section is also divided into two parts. In the first part, related literature on capital structure affecting profitability is investigated from different industries, region and time. Similarly, the second section examines the related literature on factors affecting profitability from different industries, region and time.

2.2 Theoretical Reviews

2.2.1 Capital Structure Theories

The main decisions of financial managers of the business firm are investing decision, financing decision and dividend decision. As per the process of financial management, upon finalising the investing decision, the next step for the firm is to arrange the required capital. While arranging the capital, business firm mainly acquires the external capital from the two sources, which are from debt funds and equity funds. Thus, the composition of equity, debt and retained earnings is known as capital structure. Therefore, Ehrhardt and Brigham (2011) define capital structure as the mixture of firm's debt and equity. In another words, Nasimi (2016) defines it as the combination of debt and equity capital that a firm uses to fund their assets. Since maximising the profit is the sole objective of any business, many intellectual persons have come up with many theories on capital structure. These theories are discussed below.

a) *Net Income (NI) Approach (1952)*: This approach is introduced by David Durand in 1952 (Singh and Pandey, 2017). Durand (1952) first time stated that the capital structure influences value of the firm and the cost of capital. As far as this approach is concerned, as the overall or weighted average cost of capital decreases, the debt increases. Therefore, this indicates that increase in debt, increases the value of the firm and increases the value of the equity shares of the company. As per this theory, cost of equity and cost of debt are constant and as more debt is used, the overall cost of the capital starts declining. This is shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Net Income Approach

Source: Singh and Pandey (2017).

Where,

Ke: Cost of Equity

Kd: Cost of Debt

Ko: Cost of Capital or Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)

The assumptions of net income approach are based on the following:

- i) Corporate taxes are avoided.
- ii) The cost of equity is higher than the cost of debt.
- iii) The debt capitalisation rate and the equity capitalisation rate remain constant.
- iv) The proportion of the debt does not affect the risk perception of the investors.
- v) Dividend payout ratio is 100 percent.

According to this approach, the firm tries to optimise the capital structure by borrowing more and more debts as it is less costly than equity in the capital structure. For instance, when a firm increases the financial leverage, they increase the cheaper source of funds which is debt. This reduces the overall cost of capital, which consequently increases the value of the firm and the value of the equity share of the firm. Hence, the optimum capital structure exists when the firm employs 100 percent debt or maximum debt in the capital structure. In another words, it is optimum when the cost of capital is minimum. According to this approach, the

cost of capital is minimum when there is 100 percent level of debt in capital structure. Therefore, the capital structure is optimised at the 100 percent debt level.

b) *Modigliani and Miller (MM) Approach (1958)*: The modern theory of capital structure has its roots in an article, “The Cost of Capital, Corporate Finance and Theory of Investment”, a celebrated paper of Modigliani and Miller published in *American Economic Review*, June 1958 (Harris and Raviv, 1991; Pandey, 2005). Before this, there was no generally accepted theory of capital structure (Luigi and Sorin, 2009). This theory was introduced under perfect capital market conditions where there was no tax, no transaction costs and no information asymmetry (Modigliani and Miller, 1958). Thus, the firm value is irrelevant to capital structure or financing decision (Shahar *et al.*, 2015). In addition, this theory claims that firm’s value is self-determining and the value of the firm remains same even if the firm is levered or not. This indicates that there is no optimal capital structure that maximises the value of the firms. Therefore, Sheikh and Wang (2010) states that Modigliani and Miller’s proof is based only on assumptions which do not hold in real world. Since these assumptions do not hold in practical world, this irrelevance theory has been criticised for being purely theoretical (Danso and Adomako, 2014).

Since the publication of Modigliani and Miller's article in 1958, the issue on optimal capital structure has witnessed an interest within academic circles. The irrelevance of MM’s capital structure is because of the market’s imperfection. One of the most important imperfections is due to the existence of taxes. When taxes are applicable to corporate income, debt financing is advantageous due to the interest tax shield. Therefore, Modigliani and Miller (1963) in their work “Corporate Income Taxes and the Cost of Capital: A Correction” have corrected the irrelevance theory and brought out the tax advantages of debt financing. In this new study, they consider the value of the firm as a function of leverage and the tax rate. While dividends and retained earnings are not deductible for tax purposes but interest on debt is a tax deductible expense. As a result, the tax deductibility of corporate interest payments favours the use of debt. Therefore, the study concludes that due to tax shield on debt finance, the value of the levered firm is higher than the unlevered firms.

Later, Miller (1977) tries to improve their earlier work of 1963 and considers the effect of personal taxes. According to this study, personal taxes are classified into two categories; tax on income from holdings shares and tax on income from debt securities. With this study,

Miller identifies certain special cases where return from leverage is zero. This study gives the result of MM's original work in 1958. However, this study finds that there is an optimal capital structure at the macro level but not at the micro level.

c) *Net Operating Income (NOI) Approach (1959)*: This approach is also introduced by David Durand in 1959 (Ganesamoorthy, 2016). This theory is opposite to Net Income Approach. According to this approach, financial leverage does not affect the weighted average cost of capital and market value of the firm. Thus, the capital structure decision is irrelevant like MM's first theory. This approach notes that the value of firm is based on the earning and business risk. In another words, financial risk which comes from financial leverage does not influence the value of the firm. For instance, even if the firm utilises more and more debt in capital structure, the overall cost of capital does not change despite cheaper debt funds as compared to equity funds. This is due to the fact that the equity shareholders increase their expectations on return of their investment with every debt the firm increases. Consequently, higher expectations of shareholders multiply the business risk and the benefit of cheaper debt is offset by higher expected rate of return on equity. Therefore overall cost of capital remains constant. This is shown in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Net Operating Income Approach

Source: Singh and Pandey (2017).

Where,

Ke: Cost of Equity

Kd: Cost of Debt

Ko: Cost of Capital or Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)

Thus, Net Operating Income Approach is based on the following assumptions:

- i) There are no corporate taxes.
- ii) Cost of debt remains constant.
- iii) Overall cost of capital remains constant.
- iv) Value of the firm depends on expected net operating income and overall capitalization rate or the opportunity cost of capital.
- v) Net operating income of the firm is not affected by the degree of financial leverage.
- vi) The operating risk or business risk does not change with the change in debt equity mix.
- vii) WACC does not change with the change in financial leverage.

d) *Traditional Approach (1963)*: This approach is introduced by Ezra Soloman in 1963 (Pandey, 2005). This approach rejects both the relevance approach of Net Income Approach and the irrelevance approach of Net Operating Income Approach. This approach claims that when the level of financial leverage increases, weighted average cost of capital decreases to a certain level and starts increasing once the mixture of debt and equity level reaches the minimum. Thus, a firm attains an optimum capital structure when the cost of capital is minimum and the value of the firm is maximum. This is shown in figure 2.3. In addition, findings of Staking and Babbel (1995) support this approach as this study finds that the market value of equity grows up to certain level and then declines as the leverage increase.

Figure 2.3: Traditional Approach.

Source: Singh and Pandey (2017).

Where,

K_e : Cost of Equity

K_d : Cost of Debt

K_o : Cost of Capital or Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)

e) *Trade-off Theory (1973)*: Trade-Off theory is one of the well known capital structure theories (Singh and Pandey, 2017). This theory originates from the study of Kraus and Litzenberger (1973). The Trade-Off theory is the oldest theory and is connected to the theory of Miller and Modigliani on capital structure that emphasizes on optimal capital structure (Shahar *et al.*, 2015). This theory claims that optimal level of leverage is achieved by balancing the benefits from interest payments and costs of issuing debt (Jahanzeb *et al.*, 2014). According to Sheikh and Wang (2010), this theory chooses a capital structure that maximises the value of a firm by minimising the costs of market imperfections. Therefore, this theory is called tax-based and bankruptcy costs theory (Shahar *et al.*, 2015). In addition, this theory believes that each source of money has its own cost and return and this can affect firm's earning capacity and insolvency risks (Awan and Amin, 2014). Hence, firm with tax advantage will issue more debt to finance its operation to balance the cost of financial distress and benefit from tax shield (Shahar *et al.*, 2015).

f) *Agency Cost Theory (1976)*: Jensen and Meckling (1976) introduce the concept of agency costs. Agency costs arise due to conflicts between shareholders and debt-holders and between shareholders and managers. However, no company can satisfy expectations of all the stakeholders at a time because the expectations of different stakeholders are very high. Thus, interest of shareholders, debt-holders and managers are always in a conflict in a company. According to this theory, total agency cost first decreases to certain level but after the external equity capital increases into a certain level in capital structure, it increases. The total agency cost becomes minimal at certain level of external equity capital. Thus, this theory claims the concept of optimal capital structure (Baral, 2004).

g) *Signalling Theory (1977)*: The signalling theory emerges from information asymmetries between firm management and shareholders. For instance, when the firms are undervalued, the managers prefer debt funds rather than equity funds. On the other hand, if the firm is overvalued, the managers choose equity funds first instead of debt funds. Due to this reason, the signalling theory was first introduced by Ross (1977) who suggests that the value of firms will rise with leverage, since increasing leverage increases the market's perception of value. Asquith and Mullins (1983), Masulis and Korwar (1986), and Mikkelson and Partch (1986) also empirically observe that announcements of new equity issues lead to the sharp declines in stock prices. Due to this reason, equity issues are comparatively rarer among large companies. In addition, debt also plays an important role in allowing investors to generate useful information to monitor the management (Harris and Raviv, 1990).

h) *Pecking Order Theory (1984)*: Myers and Majluf (1984) made this theory popular in 1984 which was originally developed by Donaldson in 1961. This theory is one step ahead of signalling theory which suggests that the information costs are significant enough to justify managers to issue security with the least information costs (Barclay and Smith, 1999). Myers and Majluf (1984) demonstrate that issue of new shares are perceived negatively by the investors. This is because managers tend to issue shares when the values of shares are overpriced. In another words, this theory suggested to avoid the effect of information cost on new share, the firms are more likely to choose debt fund rather than equity funds. In addition, Martin *et al.*, (1988) confirm this theory by claiming that the management prefers internal financing to debt financing and finally external equity financing. Therefore, this theory suits large and highly profitable firms which has enough internal funds. Thus, this theory states

that highly profitable firms prefer internal funds and when external funds are required, the firm will borrow, rather than issuing equity.

i) *Market Timing Theory (2002)*: Market Timing theory is quite new and therefore, small numbers of studies have been conducted to test its validity (Danso and Adomako, 2014). This theory is pioneered by Baker and Wurgler (2002). According to this theory, firms have a timing to issue new equity shares. For instance, firm will issue new stock when the price is perceived to be overvalued (high price) and repurchase their shares when the price is undervalued (low price) (Luigi and Sorin, 2009; Mostafa and Boregowda, 2014; Baker and Wurgler 2002). As a result, fluctuations in stock prices affect the firm's decision on capital structures as Welch (2004) finds that the stock return is also an important determinant of capital structure. However, in the long run, market timing does not have a significant effect on the firms' capital structure (Hovakimian, 2006). In addition, Alti (2006) confirms the same that the impact of market timing entirely fades within two years.

2.2.2 Profitability Analysis

Iyer (1995) defines profit as a surplus of return over expenses and profitability is the ability of given investment to earn a return from its use (Nimalathan, 2009). In other words, it is the power of firm to earn profits (Tulsian, 2014). There are two types of ratios in profitability analysis. The first ratio is sales related ratio such as Gross Profit Margin (GPM), Operating Profit Margin (OPM) and Net profit Margin (NPM). The second ratios include Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). All these ratios demonstrate overall effectiveness of the firm's operation (Van Horne and Wachowicz, 2009) and measure the firm's ability to generate profits (Nishanthini and Nimalathan, 2013).

a) *Profitability in Relation to sales:*

- i) **Gross Profit Margin:** This ratio indicates the profit of a firm in relation with sales after deducting the cost of goods sold (Van Horne and Wachowicz, 2009). This ratio shows the efficiency of the firm's operation and it shows the product's price. According to this ratio, business management is considered good when the ratio is high.

- ii) **Operating Profit Margin:** This ratio is used to determine operational efficiency of the management. This ratio establishes relationship between operating profit and net sales (Tulsian, 2014). According to this ratio, when the ratio is high, it is better for operational efficiency of business. This indicates that a business is able to increase its sales and able to cut down its operating expenses.
- iii) **Net Profit Margin:** It is a measurement of the firm's profitability of sales after taking account of all the expenses and income taxes (Van Horne and Wachowicz, 2009). According to this ratio, if the ratio shows below the industry average, it indicates that the firm's sales are low and the cost is too high or it could be both (Brigham and Gapenski, 1997).

b) *Profitability in Relation to Investment:*

- i) **Return on Assets (ROA):** Schall and Haley (1991) state that ROA is a rate of return earned by the firm for its investors and lenders. This ratio shows how the profit from each unit of assets is generated. Thus, this ratio exhibits how efficiently and effectively the firm is being run (Petersen and Schoeman, 2008). In addition, ROA describes the ability of the firm to earn a satisfactory return from all the assets the company have invested in business (Pinches, 1990). According to this ratio, the return under the industry average indicates the company's inability to earn its return and high interest costs from the use of debt. In short, it is a ratio of net income to total assets (Brigham and Ehrhardt, 2002). However, Chandra (2008) argues that it is an odd measure because the numerator measures the return to shareholders which includes equity and preference shareholder. On the other hand, the denominator presents the contribution of all investors, which includes both the Shareholders as well as the lenders.
- ii) **Return on Equity (ROE):** Chandra (2008) defines this ratio as the measurement of the profitability of equity funds invested in the firm. Further, Chandra (2008) affirms that this ratio is a significant measurement of the performance because it measures shareholder's wealth and maximising them is the main financial goal of the firm. In another words, this ratio signifies the earning power on shareholders from their investment in the business (Van Horne and Wachowicz, 2009). According to this

ratio, high return above the industry average implies that company has a strong investment opportunities and effective management of expenses. However, Brigham and Ehrhardt, (2002) argue that this ratio fails to consider financial risk in investment while shareholders consider about both the returns and the risks. Further, it does not explain whether the firm is efficiently investing the shareholder's money. In addition, Van Horne and Wachowicz (2009) state that if a firm maintains a debt level higher than the industry standard, a high ROE might indicate a high financial risk in the business to invest.

- iii) Return on Invested Capital (ROIC): According to Damodaran (2007) it is a measurement to measure the return earned on capital invested in an investment. It is mainly used to assess a firm's efficiency in allocating capital to make profitable investments. It provides a clearer picture of how well a company uses the funds to generate returns (Nasimi, 2016). Furthermore, Borneman (2017) states that shareholders use this measurement as the best tools to understand how effectively corporate leaders utilise shareholders' capital and managing investments to generate an adequate return. When this measurement is more than the cost of capital, it indicates that management deployed the resources efficiently. Therefore, it is a tool that measure of a company's capital efficiency (Mauboussin and Callahan, 2014).

- iv) Return on Capital Employed (ROCE): Sing and Yadav (2013) state that it is a measuring tool that measures the efficiency and profitability of capital investments undertaken by the companies. The ratio of this tool indicates whether the company is earning sufficient revenues and profits in order to make the best use of its capital assets. It includes both equity funds and debt funds (Scarlet, 2006). Having reviewed both the theories, ROCE can be understood as a measurement that is important for the companies and it calculates the return before the interest and tax with total capital employed, whereas ROIC is calculated as the return after interest and tax with capital invested in the business and it is important for shareholders.

2.3 Review of Previous Studies

2.3.1 Capital Structure Affecting Profitability:

Abor (2005) investigates the relationship between capital structure and profitability for the period of 1998 to 2002, which are listed companies on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE). By using regression analysis, this study analyses the data and finds a significant and positive relation between short-term debt ratio (STDR), total debt ratio (TDR) and ROE. Therefore, this study suggests that increase of short term debt will lead to an increase in the profitability of the firm because this study claims that short term debt is less expensive due to low interest rate. Further, this study affirms that increase in total debts led to increase in profitability. This indicates that higher the debt, higher is the profitability. In contrast, Fama and French (1998) contradict the findings of Abor (2005) that debt negatively affects the profitability, indicating that debt does not provide tax benefits and decrease the profitability of the firm. However, the positive relation between TDR and profitability is consistent with the findings of Roden and Lewellen (1995) and Champion (1999) whose study suggests that debt financing improves the profitability of a firm. In addition, the results show a negative relationship between the long-term debt ratio (LTDR) and ROE. However, increase in long term debts is associated with decrease in the profitability because this study finds long term debt to be more expensive than the short term debts. This finding is supported by Mesquita and Lara (2003) who found a negative effect of debt on profitability. All in all, this study has shown that most of the Ghanaian profitable companies are more dependent on debt as their main financing option. Out of this debt financing, Ghanaian companies use more short-term debt which is 85 percent of the total debts.

Ebaid (2009) investigates the impact of capital structure choice on the performance of the publicly traded firms in Egyptian Stock Exchange as one of emerging or transition economies. The data has been taken from the period of 1997-2005. In this study, multiple regression analysis has been used to estimate the relationship between the leverage level and firm's performance. The dependent variables are return on equity (ROE) return on assets (ROA) and gross profit margin (GPM). The results reveal that short-term debt and total debt have a negative effect on ROA. This finding is consistent with the studies of Chiang *et al.* (2002) and Zeitun and Tian (2007) which portray negative effect in the area of property and construction sector in Hong Kong and Jordanian Firms. On the other hand, short-term debt,

long-term debt and total debt show insignificant effect on ROE. Baum et al. (2007) which confirm insignificant effect in American Industrial Companies support this finding. This is the first study that examines the relationship between leverage level and firm performance in Egypt.

In the study by Nimalathasan and Brabete (2010), an attempt has been made to analyse the capital structure and its impact on profit earning capacity of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka for the period of 2003 to 2007, which is for five years. This study finds that debt to equity ratio (D/E) ratio has a positive and strong relationship with profitability ratios like gross profit ratio (GPR), operating profit ratio (OPR) and net profit ratio (NPR). Similarly, Debt to assets (D/A) exhibits positive and strong relation to OPR, NPR and ROCE. In addition, capital gearing (CG) ratio shows positive correlation with GPR and NPR. Again, this finding shows the similar outcome with Roden and Lewellen (1995) and Champion (1999) and supported to Taub (1975) findings who found significant and positive effect of debt on profitability. However, D/E has no relationship with return on capital employed (ROCE) and return on investment (ROI). Baum et al. (2007) who conclude that capital structure has no relation with profitability of firm support this finding.

Gill *et al.* (2011) attempts to extend Abor's (2005) findings by examining the effect of capital structure on profitability of the American service and manufacturing firms. In this study, 272 American firms have been selected as a sample. These companies are listed on New York Stock Exchange for a period of three years from 2005 to 2007. The correlations and regression analyses have been used to measure the effect of capital structure on profitability (measured by return on equity). The finding of this study shows a positive relationship of short-term debt ratio, total debt ratio with profitability in the service industry. This result is similar to the study of Abor (2005). In regard to manufacturing industry, the result shows a positive relationship between of short-term debt ratio, long-term debt ratio and total debt ratio with profitability. However, this finding does not show similarity to Abor's study because there is a change in long-term debt ratio. Nevertheless, this finding gives a new picture on the capital structure and profitability study.

The empirical findings of the study conducted by Olokoyo (2013) based on 2003 to 2007 accounting and marketing data for 101 quoted firms in Nigeria add to the understanding of the pecking order and static trade-off theories of capital structure. The study employs panel

data analysis by using fixed effect estimation, random effect estimation and a pooled regression model. For the analysis, usual identification tests and Hausman's Chi square statistics have been conducted to test the appropriateness of fixed effects model estimator instead of the random effects model, which has been conducted for each model. The findings reveal that a firm's leverage has significant and negative impact on the firm's accounting performance which is ROA. This is consistent with Majumdar and Chhibber (1999) whose study finds significant and negative effect of debt on profitability. On the other hand, leverage exhibits positive and highly significant relationship with the market performance which is Tobin's Q. Similar to Abor (2005), this study finds that Nigerian firms are either heavily financed by equity capital or a mix of equity capital and short term financing.

In the study of Javed *et al.* (2014), an attempt has been made to analyse the impact of capital structure on firm performance of 63 companies listed on Karachi Stock Exchange. Data has been taken for the period of 5 years, from 2007 to 2011. This study uses fixed effects regression model to find the relationship between capital expenditure and firm performance. The finding reveals that capital structure shows positive impact on firm performance in terms of return on assets (ROA). This study supported the previous studies of Berger and Patti (2006); Margaritis and Psillaki (2007); Jang *et al.* (2008); Morogie and Erah (2010) and Park and Jang (2013) whose findings find positive effect of debt on profitability of firm. When return on equity (ROE) is used as dependent variable, there is a mixed relationship where debt over assets ratio (DTA) exhibits positive impact but equity over assets ratio (EQA) and long term debts over assets ratio (LDA) show a negative impact over ROE. When return on sales (ROS) is used as dependent variable, DTA and EQA exhibits negative relationship ROS but LDA is revealed to have a positive impact over ROS. This mixed effect of debts on profitability is previously found in the study of Li *et al.* (2008), which is later supported by Tsangao *et al.* (2009). For instance, Arbabiyan and Safari (2009) empirically proves that short-term debts and total debts have positive effect on profitability whereas long-term debts have negative effect in 100 Iranian firms. The evidence of mixed effect of debt on profitability is claimed by Cheng *et al.* (2010) after researching 650 Chinese companies, where 53.97 to 70.48 percent of debt ratio in capital structure represents a positive effect. On the other hand, if the debt ratio is above 70.48 percent, then the effect of debt on profitability is negative. Nevertheless, this study also proves that capital structure has an impact over firm performance.

Based on the agency theory, Dawar (2014) empirically investigates the impact of capital structure choice on firm performance in India listed in Bombay stock exchange for the period of 2003 to 2012 as one of the emerging economies. This study uses short term debt ratio (STD) and long term debt ratio (LTD) as its independent variables while return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) as its profitability variables. In addition, factors like size, age, tangibility, growth, liquidity and advertising have been used as controlling factors. To find the relationship between leverage and firm performance, fixed effect panel regression model has been used to analyse ten years of data on the sample units. The findings of this study suggest that leverage has a negative influence on financial performance of Indian firms. This result defends the study of Goddard *et al.* (2005) whose study find negative effect in manufacturing and service sector in Belgium, France, Italy and the UK. Later, Nunes *et al.* (2009) also support the findings by witnessing negative effect in Portuguese service sector.

Hasan *et al.* (2014) examines the influence of capital structure on the performance of Bangladeshi firms for the period of 2007 to 2012. In this study, 36 Bangladeshi firms listed in Dhaka Stock Exchange have been chosen as a sample. There are four performance measures in this study, namely; earnings per share (EPS), return on equity (ROE), return of asset (ROA) and Tobin's Q as dependent variables. In addition, there are three capital structure ratios, which are short-term debt, long-term debt and total debt ratios as independent variables. Using pooling panel data regression method, the study finds that short-term debt has a significant and positive relationship with EPS while long term debt has a significant and negative relationship. This mixed effect has justified the study of Arbabiyan and Safari (2009) which find similar results. Further, the debt ratios are shown to have a significant and negative relationship with ROA. Although, this finding contradicts with many studies which show positive effect of debt on profitability such as Berger and Patti (2006); Margaritis and Psillaki (2007); Jang *et al.* (2008); Morogie and Erah (2010) and Park and Jang (2013), this result is consistent with the findings of Majumdar and Chhibber (1999); Chiang *et al.* (2002) and Zeitun and Tian (2007) who witnessed negative effect of debts on profitability. On the other hand, debt ratios have no significant relation with ROE and Tobin's Q. Thus, this result validates the claims of Baum *et al.* (2007) where no relation between capital structure and profitability has been witnessed.

In the study of impact of capital structure on firm performance, Abeywardhana (2016) examines the performance of manufacturing sector SMEs in UK for the period of 1998 to 2008. To examine the impact, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis have been employed. The outcome of this study reveals a significant and negative relationship between leverage and firm performance (ROA, ROCE). Despite the contradiction with the study of Gill *et al.* (2011), whose studies show positive impact of debt on profitability, this study is consistent with the results of Omondi and Muturi (2013) which reveal negative effect of debts on financial performance of Kenyan firm. Later, this result is supported by Umer (2014) who finds similar result in Ethiopia. In addition, the results show that liquidity has a negative relationship with firm performance whereas size has a positive relationship with firm performance. Therefore, this study concludes that firms which perform well are less dependent on debt capital. Instead, SMEs in the UK finance their operations from retained earnings because this study claims that SMEs have less access to external finance and face difficulties in borrowing funds.

The study of the relationship between capital structure and profitability is important because of the firm's dependence on its profitability, which is determined by the length of the survivability of the firm. A study by Nasimi (2016) explores the effects of capital structure on firm profitability by studying three firms from FTSE-100 index of the London Stock Exchange for the period of 2005 to 2014. By using regression analysis, this study finds that the results show a positive and significant impact of interest coverage on return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and return on invested capital (ROIC). Further, the results reveal that debt to equity has a positive and significant impact on ROE but shows a negative and significant impact on ROA and ROIC. This mixed effect of debt on profitability is consistent with the argument of Arbabiyani and Safari (2009) and Hasan *et al.* (2014), the studies that reveal positive effect of short-term debts and negative effect of long-term debts on profitability.

In another study of impact of capital structure on firm performance, Basit and Irwan (2017) researches by using convenience sampling technique on 50 industrial product companies listed in Bursa Malaysia main exchange market based on the report from 2011 to 2015 report. This study uses debt to equity ratio, total debt ratio and total equity ratio as independent variables. To measure the performance, return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and earnings per share (EPS) have been used as dependent variable. The analysis of the data with

the use of descriptive statistics and multiple regressions reveals that industrial product company are dependent on equity finance in their capital structure. Thus, the regression result reveals that debt to equity has a negative impact on ROA, ROE and EPS. This result is supported by previous studies of Foo *et al.* (2015) whose study is inspired by pecking order theory and finds negative effect of capital structure on firm performances. In contrast, total debt ratio shows positive impact on ROE and EPS and it supports the claim of Abor (2005) where total debt increases the profitability of the firm. Besides, both the total debt ratio and total equity ratio show insignificant impact on ROA while only total equity ratio exhibits insignificant impact on ROE and EPS. This is related with the finding of Baum *et al.* (2007) which reveal insignificant effect of capital structure on firm performance.

The impact of debt ratios on the firm performance have been conducted by Bui (2017). This study has been conducted on 18 British Gas and Oil companies from the period of 2009 to 2014. The two dependent variables used in this research are ROA (return on assets) and ROE (return on equity) while the three independent variables were STD (short term debt), LTD (long term debt) and TD (total debt). In addition, this study uses growth (growth of assets) as a control variable. With the help of the regression analysis, the finding of this study reveals a negative impact of LTD and TD on ROA and ROE. This result supports the finding of Arbabiyan and Safari (2009) and Hasan *et al.* (2014), studies that show significant and negative effect of LTD on profitability. In contrast, STD has no significant effect on ROA and ROE, which is consistent with the finding of Ebaid (2009) who finds insignificant effect of STD on profitability. According to the results, the firms having high level of long term debt and total debt are likely to show poorer performance of return on assets and return on equity.

2.3.2 *Factors affecting Profitability:*

Bhutta and Hasan (2013) examine the impact of firm specific and macroeconomic factors on profitability of food sector listed on Karachi stock exchange, Pakistan for the period of 2002 to 2006. The main firm specific factors of this study are debt to equity, tangibility, growth and size while the macroeconomic factor is food inflation. By employing multivariate regression analysis, this study finds that size has a negative relation with profitability of the firm (net income ratio) (Goddard *et al.*, 2005). However, this result contradicts with the findings of Smirlock (1985) and Akhavein *et al.* (1997) where size has positive effect on

profitability. Hence, this empirical result produces the evidence that profitability of food sector is determined by firm-specific factors and not by macroeconomic variables.

Sivathaasan *et al.* (2013) in their study investigates the factor determining the profitability of selected manufacturing companies listed on Colombo stock exchange, Sri Lanka over a period of five years from 2008 to 2012. The main factors determining the firms' profitability are capital structure, working capital, firm size, non-debt tax shield and growth rate. To measure the impact, this study employs multiple regression analysis. The results reveal that capital structure (Javed *et al.*, 2014) and non-debt tax shield (Shah and Khan, 2007) have statistically significant impact on profitability (ROA and ROE).

Yazdanfar (2013) investigates the variables affecting firm profitability of 12,530 Swedish non-financial micro firms operating in four industry sectors (healthcare, transport, manufacturing of metallic products and retail trade) for the period of 2006 to 2007. By applying regression analysis, this study finds that firm size (Goddard *et al.*, 2005), lagged profitability (Bothwell *et al.*, 1984; Fenny and Rogers, 1999), growth (Samiloglu and Demirgunes, 2008; Asimakopoulos *et al.*, 2009) and productivity (Stierwald, 2010) positively influence the micro firms' profitability (ROA). On the other hand, firm age (Akben-Selcuk, 2016) and industry affiliation negatively influences the profitability of micro firms. In the case of Swedish non-financial micro firms, the most significant determinant of profitability is productivity. Unlike other studies, this study suggests that firm performance is mainly determined by internal factors rather than external factors, which is consistent with the study of Bhutta and Hasan (2013).

Phan (2013) investigates factors affecting the profitability of 40 listed companies in the Consumer Products sector in the Stock Exchange of Thailand from 2008 to 2012. By employing multiple linear regression analysis, the influence of liquidity using quick ratio (QR), cash conversion cycle (CCC), inventory conversion period (ICP), receivable conversion period (RCP) and payable deferral period (PDP), capital structure using debt to equity ratio (DTER), sales growth (SG) and tax rate (TR) on profitability in terms of return on equity (ROE) have been measured. Accordingly, the results of this study show that only QR (Sur *et al.*, 2001) and DTER (Shah and Khan, 2007) have significant and negative impact on ROE while SG has a positive and significant impact on ROE (Giannett and Ongena, 2007).

The study of factors determining the profitability of companies has caught attention over time from different fields or area. Pratheepan (2014) analyses 55 Sri Lankan listed manufacturing companies over the period of 2003 to 2012. This study uses regression analysis to measure the influence of size, leverage, liquidity and tangibility on return on assets (ROA). According to the findings, size is found have significant and positive relationship with ROA (Asimakopoulos *et al.*, 2009). However, tangibility is shown to be statistically significant but negatively related to ROA (Nunes *et al.*, 2009).

Al-Jafari and Samman (2015) investigate the determinants of profitability of 17 industrial companies listed on Muscat securities market in Oman for the period of 2006 to 2013. This study considers profit margin (PM) and return on assets (ROA) as the variable of firm's profitability while firm average tax rate, size, growth, fixed assets, working capital and financial leverage as the determining factors of profitability. To measure these variables, ordinary least squares regression analysis has been employed. The results show that firm size (Pratheepan, 2014), growth (Yoo and Kim, 2015), fixed assets (Azadi, 2013) and working capital (Pouraghajan and Emamgholipourarchi, 2012) have a positive and significant relationship with firms' profitability. On the other hand, the average tax rate (Beigi *et al.*, 2013) and the financial leverage (Fama and French (1998) have a negative relationship with profitability.

Margaretha and Supartika (2016) examine the factors affecting profitability of 22 SMEs firm listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange for six years which is from 2007 to 2012. This study includes variables such as firm size, firm age, growth, lagged profitability, productivity, and industry affiliation as the determining factors of SMEs' profitability (ROA). To measure the impact of the variables, this study employs multiple regression analysis. Hence, the findings of this study show that firm size (Salman and Yazdanfar, 2012), growth (Jasra, 2011) and lagged profitability (Musah *et al.*, 2019) have negative and significant effect on ROA whereas productivity (Yazdanfar, 2013) and industry affiliation (Salman and Yazdanfar, 2012) have a significant and positive impact on ROA.

The study of Alarussi and Alhaderito (2018) examine the factors affecting profitability of 120 Malaysian companies listed on Bursa Malaysia from the period of 2012 to 2014. This research is based on five independent variables such as firm size (as measured by total sales), working capital, company efficiency (assets turnover ratio), liquidity (current ratio) and

leverage (debt equity ratio and leverage ratio). Besides, it has two dependent variables, which are return on equity (ROE), and earnings per share (EPS). To measure these variables, this study uses pooled ordinary least squares and Fixed-effects regression analysis. The regression results show that firm size (Malik, 2011), working capital (Malik, 2011) and company efficiency (Murtadlo *et al.*, 2014) have a positive influence on profitability. Besides, leverage has a negative impact on firms' profitability (Fama and French, 1998).

2.4 Summary of Empirical Literature

Table 2.1: Capital Structure Affecting Profitability

Author(s)	Title	Methodology (Model and Data)	Findings
Abor (2005)	The effect of capital structure on profitability: An empirical analysis of listed firms in Ghana.	Regression analysis on 22 listed firms on the Ghana Stock Exchange, Ghana from 1998 to 2002 (5 years).	The results revealed a significantly positive relation between short-term debt to total assets and ROE. On other hand, a negative relationship between long-term debt to total assets and ROE was found.
Ebaid (2009)	The impact of capital-structure choice on firm performance: empirical evidence from Egypt.	Multiple regression analysis on 64 non-financial listed companies on the Egyptian stock exchange from 1997 to 2005 (9 years).	Capital structure has a weak or no impact on firm's performance.
Nimalathasan and Brabete (2010)	Capital Structure and Its Impact on Profitability: A Study of Listed Manufacturing Companies in Sri Lanka.	Multiple regression analysis on 13 listed manufacturing companies on Colombo Stock Exchange, Sri Lanka from 2003 to 2007 (5 years).	Capital structure has a great impact on all profitability ratios except return on Capital employed and return on investment.
Gill <i>et al.</i> (2011)	The Effect of Capital Structure on Profitability: Evidence from the United States	Correlations and regression analyses on 272 American firms listed on New York Stock Exchange from 2005 to 2007 (3 years).	Showed a positive relationship between short-term debt and total debt to total assets and profitability in the service industry. In

			addition, showed a positive relationship between short-term debt, long-term debt and total debt to total assets and profitability in the manufacturing industry.
Olokoyo (2013)	Capital Structure and Corporate Performance of Nigerian Quoted Firms: A Panel Data Approach.	Regression analysis on 101 Nigerian firms listed in Nigerian stock exchange from 2003 to 2007 (5 years).	Firm's leverage has a significant negative impact on the firm's performance (ROA). All the leverage measures have been found to have a positive and highly significant relationship with the market performance (Tobin's Q).
Javed <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance: Evidence from Pakistani Firms	Regression analysis on 63 companies listed on Karachi stock exchange from 2007 to 2011 (5 years).	Capital structure shows positive impact ROA. DTA shows positive impact but EQA and LDA reveal negative impact on ROE. LDA reveal positive impact but DTA and EQA show a negative impact to ROS.
Dawar (2014)	Agency theory, capital structure and firm performance: some Indian evidence.	Regression analysis on 100 companies listed on S&P BSE index, India from 2003 to 2012 (10 years).	Leverage has a negative influence on financial performance of Indian firms.
Hasan <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Influence of Capital Structure on Firm Performance: Evidence from Bangladesh.	Regression analysis on 36 firms listed in Dhaka stock exchange, Bangladesh from 2007 to 2012 (6 years).	STD shows a significantly positive relation with EPS but LTD shows negative relation. Capital structure shows negative relation with ROA. However, no statistically significant relation exists between

			capital structure and ROE and Tobin's Q.
Abeywardhana (2016)	Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance: Evidence from Manufacturing Sector SMEs in UK.	Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis on 224,231 observations of SMEs manufacturing sector from 1998 to 2008 (11 years).	Leverage has a significant and negative relationship on firm performance (ROA, ROCE). Firms which perform well do not rely on debt capital and finance their operations from retained earnings. In addition, SMEs have less access to external finance and face difficulties in borrowing funds.
Nasimi (2016)	Effect of Capital Structure on Firm Profitability: An Empirical Evidence from London, UK.	Multiple regression analysis on 30 firms listed in FTSE-100 of London stock exchange from 2005 to 2014 (10 years).	Interest Coverage has positively significant impact on ROA, ROE and ROIC. Debt to Equity has positively significant impact on ROE but negatively significant impact on ROA and ROIC.
Basit and Irwan (2017)	The Impact of Capital Structure on Firms Performance: Evidence from Malaysian Industrial Sector - A Case Based Approach.	Multiple regression analysis on 50 Malaysian industrial product companies from 2011 to 2015 (5 years).	Industrial product companies are heavily relied on equity finance. D/E shows a negative impact on ROA and ROE. TD has insignificant impact on ROA but has a negative impact on ROE. TE has insignificant impact on ROA and ROE.
Vuong <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Impact of Capital Structure on Firm's Financial Performance: Evidence from United Kingdom.	Regression analysis on 739 very large and large UK companies listed in the London stock exchange from 2006 to 2015 (10 years).	The results indicated that LTD has a negative relationship with firms' financial performance. However, STD has insignificant with firms' financial

			performance. Besides, Firms' leverage has no relation with EPS. Size and growth factors is benefitted to firms' performance but financial crisis has no relation between the leverage and profitability of the firm.
Bui (2017)	The Impact of Financial Leverage on Firm Performance: A Case Study of Listed Oil and Gas Companies in England.	Regression analysis on 18 British Oil and Gas companies from 2009 to 2014 (6 years).	LTD and TD has a strongly negative impact on ROA and ROE. STD has insignificant affect on ROA and ROE. Besides, the firms having high level of LTD and LTD tend to show poorer performance of ROA and ROE.

Table 2.2: Factors affecting Profitability

Author(s)	Title	Methodology (Model and Data)	Findings
Bhutta and Hasan (2013)	Impact of Firm Specific Factors on Profitability of Firms in Food Sector.	Regression analysis on 12 Pakistani food firms listed in Karachi stock exchange from 2002 to 2006 (5 years).	Size shows a negative relation with profitability. Tangibility, growth of the firm and food inflation is found insignificantly positive relation with profitability. Debt to equity ratio shows insignificantly negative relation with profitability.
Sivathaasan <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Factors Determining Profitability: A Study of Selected Manufacturing Companies listed on	Multiple regression analysis on 11 manufacturing companies listed in Colombo stock	Capital structure and non-debt tax shield has a positively and statistically significant impact on

	Colombo Stock Exchange in Sri Lanka	exchange, Sri Lanka from 2008 to 2012 (5 years).	profitability.
Yazdanfar (2013)	Profitability Determinants among Micro Firms: Evidence from Swedish Data.	Regression analysis on 12,530 non-financial mic1w1w12sro firms from 2006 to 2007 (2 years).	Firm size, lagged profitability, growth, and productivity positively influence profitability. Firm age and industry affiliation negatively influence profitability. Productivity shows the most significant determinant of profitability.
Phan (2013)	Factors Affecting Profitability: Case of Consumer Products Companies of Thailand.	Multiple regression analysis on 40 consumer products companies listed in Stock exchange of Thailand from 2008 to 2012 (5 years).	Quick ratio and debt to equity ratio have a negative impact while sales growth has positive impact on return on equity.
Pratheepan (2014)	A Panel Data Analysis of Profitability Determinants: Empirical Results from Sri Lankan Manufacturing Companies.	Static panel models analysis on 55 manufacturing companies listed in Colombo stock exchange from 2003 to 2012 (10 years).	Size has statistically and positively significant relation with profitability. Tangibility shows statistically and negatively relation with profitability. Leverage and liquidity has insignificant impact on profitability.
Vatavu (2014)	The Determinants of Profitability in Companies Listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange.	Cross sectional regression analysis on 126 Romanian companies listed on the Bucharest stock exchange from 2003 to 2012 (10 years).	Profitable companies operate with limited borrowings. Tangibility, business risk and the level of taxation have a negative impact on ROA. Performance is affected by high levels of liquidity. Inflation rates and financial crisis have a strong and negative impact on corporate performance.

Al-Jafari and Samman (2015)	Determinants of Profitability: Evidence from Industrial Companies Listed on Muscat Securities Market.	Regression analysis on 17 industrial companies listed on Muscat securities market, Oman from 2006 to 2013 (8 years).	Firm size, growth, fixed assets and working capital have a positive and statistical significant relationship with profitability. On the other hand, average tax rate and the financial leverage variables show a negative relationship with profitability.
Margaretha and Supartika (2016)	Factors Affecting Profitability of Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Firm Listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange.	Multiple regression analysis on 22 Indonesian SMEs listed in PEFINDO 25 Index of Indonesia stock exchange from 2007 2012 (6 years).	Firm size, growth, lagged profitability have negatively and significantly effect on profitability. Productivity and industry affiliation have positively and significantly impact on profitability. Firm age does not significantly influence profitability.
Alarussi and Alhaderito (2018)	Factors affecting profitability in Malaysia.	Regression analysis on 120 companies listed on Bursa Malaysia from 2012 to 2014 (3 years).	Total sales, working capital, assets turnover ratio have a strong and positive relation with profitability. Debt equity ratio and leverage ratio have a negative relationship with profitability. Current ratio has no significant relationship with profitability.

2.5 Summary

As discussed previously, the main objective of this chapter is to provide appropriate approach to the topic by building strong foundation in the process of selection of appropriate theories and methods. In this chapter, four types of literature has been reviewed which is capital structure theoretical review, profitability theoretical review, empirical review of how capital structure impacts profitability and empirical review of profitability factors. Both the literature review of capital structure and profitability provide contextual background of the theories. On the other hand, empirical review produces detail information about the previous study such as area of the study, methods used in the study and sample of the research.

In this chapter, empirical review has been conducted covering different regions, which include both developed and developing nations. The empirical review reveals that majority of the previous studies show negative impact of capital structure on firms' profitability. In addition, the majority of the previous studies have been conducted using regression analysis and the period of study taken into consideration is found to be short. Thus, this chapter gives a clear picture about the theories to be built, methods to be followed and sample to be collected. The next chapter presents the concept and the theory of this study, which is based on literature and empirical review.

CHAPTER THREE

Research Frame works

3.1 Introduction

Theoretical and conceptual framework helps readers to firmly understand the concept of research. Therefore, Adom *et al.* (2018) stated that theoretical and conceptual frameworks are the guide of a research pathways and offer foundation for establishing its credibility. This chapter is divided into four parts which consists of theoretical framework, conceptual framework, research hypothesis and details of the variables. Firstly, the theoretical frameworks for this study are discussed briefly. Secondly, the conceptual framework is developed and shows the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. Thirdly, the hypotheses are developed which are proposed to be tested in this study. Lastly, the details of the variables are discussed.

3.2 Theoretical Frame works

Grant and Osanloo (2014) state that theoretical framework is a plan or guide for research. More clearly, Adom *et al.* (2018) explain that it is based on an existing theory, which is in related field and reflects the hypothesis of a study. Further, the study also states that it is a plan often adopted by the researcher to shape the research inquiry. It also serves as the foundation upon which a research is constructed. Sinclair (2007) states that the theoretical framework is similar to that of a map or travel plan. For instance, when someone is travelling to a particular location, the map guides the person's path. Likewise, the theoretical framework guides the researcher so that the researcher would be able to focus on the accepted theories to make a final contribution scholarly and academically. All the theoretical models used in this study are discussed as follows:

Figure 3.1: Determinants of Capital Structure and their impact on firm performance.

Note: GDP = Gross Domestic Product, ROE = Return on Equity.

Source: Ganiyu Y. O. (2015). Dynamic Analysis of the Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance. *PhD Thesis, Department of Accounting and Finance, Leicester Business School, De Montfort University.*

Ganiyu (2015) studies the impact of capital structure on firm performance in Nigeria. In this study, the author examines thirteen (13) different sectors of the Nigerian economy. All the companies selected in this study are listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). According to this study, the data have been collected largely from the annual reports of the sample companies and the fact books of the NSE. In this study, the author has taken into account firms specific factors such as firm size, assets tangibility, growth opportunities, firm risk, ownership structure, dividend and age. In addition, country specific determinants are also taken in this study as inflation, interest rates, GDP, financial development and institutional quality. To explore the capital structure, the variables are taken as total debt ratio, long-term debt ratio and short-term debt ratio. This study applies only one variable for firm performance, which is return on equity. Therefore, in order to estimate all the chosen variables, this study employs generalised method of moments (GMM) in the STATA 12 with XTABOND2 command developed by Rodman (2006). The study concludes that both firm specific variables (risk, age, size, tangibility, growth opportunities, dividend, ownership),

ROE and country variables (inflation, interest rates, GDP, institutional quality) jointly influence capital structure choice of firms in Nigeria. In addition, the capital structure choice of firms influences firm performances.

Figure 3.2: Change in Capital Structure impacts firm performance.

Note: ROA = Return on Assets.

Source: Hassan L., Samour S. and Holmstedt M. (2015). Capital Structure and Firm Performance: Did the Financial Crisis Matter? - A cross-industry study. *Master Thesis, Department of Business Studies, Uppsala University.*

Hassan *et al.* (2015) examine the impact of financial crisis on capital structure in different industries. In addition, the authors explore the industries' chosen capital structure's impact on firms' performance during the financial crisis. This study exclusively focuses on the US firms that are listed in NASDAQ, NYSE and NYSE MKT for eight years from 2003 to 2011 and the data is collected from these stock exchanges. The selected industries in this study are consumer goods, consumer services, healthcare, industrials and technology. The authors construct the study in two models; the first model studies the pre-financial crisis and the second model studies financial crisis period. The researcher utilises two panel data regression to analyse the data. The variables in this study are long-term debt ratio and short-term debt

ratio for capital structure and ROA for profitability. In addition, liquidity, tangibility, firm size and growth are control variables. The finding of this study shows that capital structure differs differently amongst the industries and financial crisis significantly affect consumer service and healthcare industry. Further, the authors find that the impact of capital structure on firms' performance is also industry-specific because only consumer service, healthcare and technology industry are statistically supported in this study.

Figure 3.3: Impact of Capital Structure on Performance

Note: ROA = Return on Asset, ROE = Return on Equity.

Source: Kanwal M., Shahzad S. J. H., Rehman M. U. and Zakaria M. (2017). Impact of Capital Structure on Performance of Non-Financial Listed Companies in Pakistan. *Pakistan Business Review*.

Kanwal *et al.* (2017) examine the relationship between capital structure and financial performance of non-financial firms. This study has been conducted on 213 non-financial companies of Pakistan that are listed in the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) for the period of 1999 to 2015. The data is collected from the balance sheet analysis, which is published by the state bank of Pakistan and from business recorder. This study uses two regression model which are fixed model and random model and compares between the models. Capital structure, which includes debt to equity ratio, short-term debt ratio and long-term debt ratio are independent variables. The dependent variables are ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q and price to earnings ratio. This study includes control variables such as size, sales growth, operating risk

and asset turnover. This study concludes that there is a significant negative impact of capital structure on firm performance.

Figure 3.4: Capital Structure and its impact on Profitability

Source: Nimalathan B. and Brabete V. (2010). Capital Structure and its impact on Profitability: As study of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. *The Young Economist Journal*.

Nimalathan and Brabete (2014) investigate the impact of capital structure on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka, which are listed in Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE). This study is conducted on thirty one manufacturing companies for five years which is from 2003 to 2007. The main source of data is the financial report of the selected companies, which are published by CSE. This study uses capital structure as independent variables and the variables are debt to equity ratio, debt to assets ratio, capital gearing ratio and interest coverage ratio. On the other hand, dependent variable is profitability, which includes gross profit ratio, net profit ratio, operating profit ratio and return on capital employed. In order to analyse these variables, the study uses correlation and multiple regression analysis. This study concludes that capital structure in terms of all the variables is positively associated with profitability.

Figure 3.5: Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance

Source: Javed T., Younas W. and Imran M. (2014). Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance: Evidence from Pakistani Firms. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Studies*, 3(5), 28-52.

Javed *et al.* (2014) analyse the impact of capital structure on firm performance in Pakistan. This study is conducted on sixty three non-financial companies of twenty five sectors which are listed in Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE). The main source of data for this research is balance sheet analyses, which are available in State Bank of Pakistan's website and uses the data from 2007 to 2011. The main independent variables of this study are debt to assets, long-term to assets and equity over assets as capital structure. Dependent variables are return on assets, return on equity and return on sales as firm performance. In addition, this study uses assets turnover, net assets, net sales, earnings per share, dividend per share, market price of share, capital expenditure over assets, percentage change in assets and percentage change in sales as control variables. Thus, in order to analyse all these variables, the authors employ regression model. The findings show that capital structure has a positive impact on return on assets. However, return on equity has a positive impact from debt over assets and has a negative impact from equity over assets and long-term debt over assets. In the case of return

on sales, long-term debts over assets show a positive impact but debt over assets and equity over assets show negative impact. Nevertheless, the findings conclude that capital structure impacts firm performance.

Figure: 3.6: Impact of Firm Leverage to Performance

Note: ROA = Return on Assets, ROE = Return on Equity, MTBV = Market to Book Value.

Source: Shahar W. S. S. Bt. and Shahar W. S. S. Bt. (2015). Impact of Firm Leverage to Performance: Evidence from Shariah and Non-Shariah Compliant Companies in Malaysia. *First International Conference on Economics and Banking*, 140-148.

Shahar and Shahar (2015) investigate the impact of firm leverage in the performance of seventy construction companies (Shariah compliant and Non-Shariah compliant) in Malaysia which are listed on Securities Commission Malaysia. This study fails to reveal data sources. The variables used in this study are short-term debt, long-term debt and total debt for capital structure which is also an independent variable. In case of performance, ROA, ROE and MTBV are used as dependent variables. In addition, size and growth are used as control variables. To analyse the chosen variables, the authors employ pooled ordinary least square of regression analysis in SPSS and generalised least square with random effect and fixed effects of STATA. In addition, this study also uses E-views to analyse the data set. The results indicate that total debt ratio exhibits no impact on Shariah compliant company's performance (ROA and ROE) but short-term debt and long-term debt have negative impact on Shariah compliant company's performance (MTBV). In case of Non-Shariah Compliance

Company, long-term debt shows negative impact on company's performance (ROE) but total debt shows positive impact. Besides, size also exhibits positive effect on Non-Shariah compliant company's performance (ROE).

Figure 3.7: Effects of Capital Structure on Profitability

Note: ROE = Return on Equity.

Source: Gill A., Biger N. and Mathur N. (2011). The Effects of Capital Structure on Profitability: Evidence from the United States. *International Journal of Management*, 28(4.1), 3-15.

Gill *et al.* (2011) further extends Abor's (2005) study by examining the effect of capital structure on profitability of the American service and manufacturing companies. This study explores two hundred and seventy two firms which are listed on New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) for three years (2005 to 2007). Data is collected from Mergent Online. The variables are short-term debt, long-term debt and total debt, which are clubbed under capital structure and size and sales growth, clubbed under control variables. On the other hand, return on equity represents as a profitability variable. To interpret the data in a meaningful way, the authors employ correlation and regression analyses. The results show positive relationship between short-term debt, total debt and profitability in the service industry. On the other hand, the results show positive relationship between short-term debt, long-term debt, total debt and profitability in the manufacturing industry.

Figure 3.8: Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance

Note: ROA = Return on Assets, ROCE = Return on Capital Employed.

Source: Schulz T. (2017). The Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance: an investigation of Dutch Unlisted SMEs. *9th IBA Bachelor Thesis Conference, The Netherlands*.

Schulz (2017) conducts a research on the impact of capital structure on firm performance in the Netherlands. This study focuses on total three thousand three hundred and sixty three (3,363) small and medium sized enterprises for over the period of 2008 to 2015. Data is collected from the database Reach, which is operated by Bureau van Dijk. The independent variables are short-term debt, long-term debt and total debt. The dependent variables are ROA and ROCE. In addition, control variables are size, liquidity and financial crisis. To analyse the data, the author employs correlation and regression analyses. The results show negative and significant relationship among all the variables of capital structure and ROA as a performance. In the case of ROCE, there are mixed results where long-term debt shows negative impact and short-term debt exhibits positive impact on profitability.

Figure 3.9: Impact of Capital Structure and Firm Performance

Note: ROA = Return on Assets, ROE = Return on Equity.

Source: Dawar V. (2014). Agency theory, capital structure and firm performance: some Indian evidence. *Managerial Finance*, 40(12), 1190-1206.

Dawar (2014) investigates the impact of capital structure choice on firm performance in India. This study explores seventy eight Indian companies, listed on the list of S&P BSE 100 Index in Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) for one decade which is from 2003 to 2012. The variables of this study are short-term debt and long-term debt, grouped under capital structure. Variables such as size, sales growth, age, tangibility, liquidity and advertising represent control variables. The dependent variables are ROA and ROE. To analyse these variables, the researcher collects the data from Prowess database of the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE). Further, panel data regression method is used to conduct the analysis. This study concludes that leverage has a negative impact on the firm performance in Indian companies.

Figure 3.10: Impact of Capital Structure and Firm Performance

Note: ROA = Return on Assets, ROE = Return on Equity, ROIC = Return on Invested capital.

Source: Nasimi, A. N. (2016). Effect of Capital Structure on Firm Profitability: An Empirical Evidence from London, UK. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: C Finance*, 16(4:1).

Nasimi (2016) explores the effect of capital structure on firm profitability in the UK. The author investigates thirty firms listed on FTSE-100 Index of the London Stock Exchange for one decade which is from 2005 to 2014. The independent variables are debt to equity and interest coverage, which are grouped as capital structure. The dependent variables are ROA, ROE and ROIC, which represent the performance of the firm. This study is unclear about the source of the data collection. To analyse the data, the author employs multiple regression analysis. This study reveals that interest coverage has a positive and significant impact on ROA, ROE and ROIC. In addition, debt to equity ratio has a positive and significant effect on ROE and has a negative and significant impact on ROA and ROIC.

3.3 Conceptual Framework

Similar to theoretical frameworks, conceptual framework is based on previous research and literature (Underhill, 1991). Jabareen (2009) redefines conceptual framework as a network of interlinked concepts that provide a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon or phenomena. In other words, it is linked with concepts, empirical research and theories (Peshkin, 1993). It presents a way of looking at a problem under study (Liehr and Smith, 1999) and explains of how the research problem is going to be explored (Adom *et al.*, 2018).

In statistical perspective, it explains the relationship between main concepts of study (Adom *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it is arranged in a logical structure to provide a clear picture of how ideas or theories relate to each another (Grant and Osanloo, 2014) so that it can show the series of action a researcher intends to carry out in the research work (Dixon *et al.*, 2001). Therefore, a conceptual framework makes the study easier for a researcher or reader to easily identify and define concepts and problems of study (Luse *et al.*, 2012). Hence, Miles and Huberman (1994) conclude that conceptual frameworks are constructed to show the main variables graphically or in a narrative form and presume the relationship of each variable between them.

Figure 3.11: Conceptual Framework

Source: Developed by the author.

There are four independent variables under the macro environment factors where financial crisis is adapted from the studies of Hassan *et al.* (2015) and Schulz (2017). Gross Domestic Product (GDP), inflation rate and interest rate are borrowed from the study of Ganiyu (2015).

There are seven other independent variables under control variables where the total asset is derived from the studies of Javed *et al.* (2014); Shahar and Shahar (2015); Schulz (2017) and Dawar (2014). Assets growth rate is adapted from the study of Javed *et al.* (2014). Age of the firm is based on the studies of Dawar (2014) and Ganiyu (2015). Earnings per share (EPS) is taken from the study of Javed *et al.* (2014) and Liquidity is derived from the studies of Dawar (2014); Schulz (2017) and Hassan *et al.* (2015). Interest coverage is based on the study of Nimalathasan and Brabete (2010) and Nasimi (2016). Effective tax rate is suggested by the author of this study based on the study of Nenu *et al.* (2018).

There are four variables under capital structure where short-term debt ratio is based on the studies of Dawar (2014); Schulz (2017); Gill *et al.* (2011); Shahar and Shahar (2015); Kanwal *et al.* (2017); Hassan *et al.* (2015) and Ganiyu (2015). The long-term debt ratio is derived from the studies of Ganiyu (2015); Hassan *et al.* (2015); Kanwal *et al.* (2017); Javed *et al.* (2014); Shahar and Shahar (2015); Gill *et al.* (2011); Schulz (2017) and Dawar (2014). Total debt ratio is procured from the studies of Shahar and Shahar (2015); Gill *et al.* (2011); Schulz (2017) and Ganiyu (2015). Debt to equity ratio is derived from the studies of Kanwal *et al.* (2017); Nimalathasan and Brabete (2010) and Nasimi (2016).

There are four dependent variables under profitability where return on asset is taken from the studies of and Nasimi (2016); Shahar and Shahar (2015); Schulz (2017); Dawar (2014); Hassan *et al.* (2015); Kanwal *et al.* (2017) and Javed *et al.* (2014). Return on equity is derived from the studies of Nasimi (2016); Dawar (2014); Gill *et al.* (2011); Shahar and Shahar (2015); Javed *et al.* (2014); Kanwal *et al.* (2017) and Ganiyu (2015). Return on invested capital is based on the study of Nasimi (2016) and Return on capital employed is derived from the studies of Nimalathasan and Brabete (2010) and Schulz (2017).

3.4 Research Hypotheses

Hypotheses are a tentative statement of something in which the validity is unknown (Black and Champion, 1976). In other words, it is a proposition which is stated in a testable form and then predicts a particular relationship between the variables (Bailey, 1978). In addition to Bailey's definition, Kerlinger (1986) defines hypotheses as a conjectural statement of the relationship between two or more variables. Chansomboon (2002) also states that a hypothesis is an unproven proposition or supposition that tentatively explains certain facts or

phenomena. By summarising the above mentioned definitions, Kumar (2011) defines hypotheses as an assumption, suspicion, assertion or an idea about a phenomenon, relationship or situation in which the reality or truth is not known.

Upon identification of proper variables, the relationships between independent variables and dependent variables have been elaborated so that relevant hypothesis could be developed and subsequently tested. In this research, sixteen hypotheses have been developed.

H1: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (STDR).

H2: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (LTDR).

H3: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (TDR).

H4: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (DER).

H5: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (STDR).

H6: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (LTDR).

H7: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (TDR).

H8: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (DER).

H9: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROA).

H10: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROE).

H11: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROIC).

H12: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROCE).

H13: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROA).

H14: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROE).

H15: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROI).

H16: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROCE).

3.5 Operationalisation of the Independent Variables and Dependent Variables

Table 3.1: Operationalisation Table

<u>Variables</u>	<u>Concept of Variables</u>	<u>Operational Components</u>	<u>Measurement Scale</u>
Size (Asset Size)	An asset is something that can potentially be changed into cash or one of the other asset categories (Westphal, 2002).	Natural logarithm of assets (Dawar, 2014; Schulz, 2017).	Ratio Scale
Growth (Asset Growth)	Asset growth rate is defined as year over year percentage change in total assets (Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2011).	$(\text{Total Assets}_{t-1} - \text{Total Assets}_{t-2}) / \text{Total Assets}_{t-2}$ (Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2011).	Ratio Scale

Age	Firm age is the number of years of incorporation of the company (Ilaboya and Ohiokha, 2016).	Firm age has been measured as the number of years since inception to the date of observation (Dawar, 2014).	Ratio Scale
Earnings Per Share (EPS)	Earnings per share is a profit per share. It shows the money earned by shareholders per each stock (Nagendra <i>et al.</i> , 2018).	Net profit after tax / No. of ordinary shares (Javed <i>et al.</i> , 2014).	Ratio Scale
Liquidity (Current Ratio)	Liquidity ratio indicates the firm's solvency to repay its short-term debt (Mclaney and Atrill, 2014), especially, current ratio measures the company's ability to pay short-term liabilities such as payable accounts and short-term loans (Durrah <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	Current Assets / Current Liabilities (Abeywardhana, 2017; Schulz, 2017).	Ratio Scale
Interest Coverage	Interest coverage ratio measures the ability of companies to make interest payments on its debt in a timely manner (Nasimi, 2016).	Earnings before interest and taxes / Interest charges (Nimalathan and Brabete, 2010).	Ratio Scale
Effective Tax Rate	The effective tax rate calculates the tax volume of companies (Dias and Reis, 2018).	Income tax expenses / Earning before taxes (Nenu <i>et al.</i> , 2018).	Ratio Scale
Financial Crisis	A financial crisis is the result of disorder in financial markets which is called "disruption"	Dummy variable for financial crisis, where 1 stands for the crisis period of 2001 and between 2007 and 2019, and 0	Ratio Scale

	(Mishkin, 1995; Antczak, 2000).	for the non-crisis period (Schulz, 2017).	
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	It measures the monetary value of final goods and services that is, those that are bought by the final user, produced in a country in a given period of time (Callen, 2008).	Annual average growth rate of the UK.	Ratio Scale
Inflation Rate (INF)	Haberler (1960) defined it as an expansion in the monetary circulation; more precisely, as an increase in the quantity of money times the velocity of circulation.	Annual average inflation rate of the UK.	Ratio Scale
Bank Interest Rate	Interest rate is the amount charged on borrowed money, expressed as a percentage of the principal, by a lender to a borrower for the use of money (Yakubu <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	Annual average interest rate of the Bank of England.	Ratio Scale
Short-Term Debt	Short-term debt is defined as the debt with maturity of one year or less (Dadush <i>et al.</i> , 2000).	Short-term debt / Total asset (Shahar and Shahar, 2015).	Ratio Scale
Long-Term Debt	Long-term debt is a source of funding with a maturity of over one year (Rixtel <i>et al.</i> , 2015).	Long-term debt / Total asset (Gill <i>et al.</i> , 2011).	Ratio Scale

Total Debt	It measures the percentage of total assets financed with debt (Henry <i>et al.</i> , 2011).	Total debt / Total asset (Shahar and Shahar, 2015).	Ratio Scale
Debt to Equity	It measures the proportion of debt and equity used to finance the assets (Kanwal <i>et al.</i> , 2017).	Total liabilities / Shareholder's equity (Kanwal <i>et al.</i> , 2017).	Ratio Scale
Return on Asset (ROA)	It measures the effectiveness of the company in generating profits by exploiting its assets (Heikal <i>et al.</i> , 2014).	Net Profit / Total Asset (Abeywardhana, 2016).	Ratio Scale
Return on Equity (ROE)	It measures company's efficiency to generate profits by using shareholder's funds (Ichsani and Suhardi, 2015).	Net Profit / Total Equity (Shahar and Shahar, 2015).	Ratio Scale
Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	It measures the company's efficiency at allocating the capital under its control to profitable investment (Nasimi, 2016).	(Net income – Dividends) / Total Capital (Nasimi, 2016).	Ratio Scale
Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	It measures the efficiency and profitability of capital investments undertaken by a company (Singh and Yadav, 2013).	Earnings before interest and tax (EBIT) / Capital employed (Abeywardhana, 2016). Capital employed is total assets minus current liabilities (Schulz, 2017).	Ratio Scale

3.6 Summary

The main objective of this chapter is to provide appropriate concept to the study. In this chapter, several previous studies on capital structure and profitability have been reviewed, followed by building of theoretical framework to offer strong foundation to the concept of this study. Having built theoretical framework, a conceptual framework has been built to display the ideas of this study. This new concept is borrowed from the theoretical framework. Besides, independent and dependent variables are adopted from the theoretical framework, which is followed by developing appropriate and unproven hypotheses.

CHAPTER FOUR

Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

Thomas (2004) speculates that a research design is a way of deciding what and how the strategy and methods of research is to be applied. In other words, it is the process of planning when, where and how the data would be collected and appropriate techniques to be used to analyse the data. An effective design of methodology is considered critical in research work because it can ensure that evidence collected is best fitted to test the theory (Rindfleish *et al.*, 2008). This chapter provides a detail explanation about the methodology of this study. There are three major parts in this chapter. The first part is research paradigm. The second part is methodology and the third part is the research method. The details are discussed below.

4.2 Research Paradigm

The term paradigm is derived from Greek word, meaning “pattern” (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017) and it has been broadly described by different academics. Kuhn (1962) defines research paradigm as a set of common beliefs and agreements which is shared by researchers regarding on how problems should be understood and addressed. In another word, it is a cluster of beliefs, which guide researchers to decide what should be studied and how results should be interpreted (Kuhn, 1970; Greener, 2008). Therefore, every researcher has a particular understanding about knowledge and truth (Chilisa and Kawulich, 2012) and such knowledge shapes researchers’ thoughts and views about themselves, other people and about the world (Schwandt, 2001). Kamal (2019) clearly explains the paradigm as the researchers’ belief and values about the world. This means the way researcher defines the world and the way researcher work within the world. In case of research, this means researchers’ thoughts and beliefs about the issues explored which guide researchers’ actions. Kivunja and Kuyini (2017) further clarify that paradigm directs the researchers’ investigation processes such as data collection and analysis procedure. Therefore, a research paradigm is a specific way of viewing the world and making sense of it (Mukherji and Albon, 2015). Thus, paradigm has important implications for every decision made in the research process (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

In addition, Guba (1990) categorises research paradigm into three main categories, which are ontological, epistemological and methodological assumptions. Further, Guba and Lincoln (1994) define research paradigm as a basic belief-system or world-view that guides the investigation. In addition to Guba (1990), Scotland (2012) adds methods as one of the components of research paradigm; namely, ontology, epistemology, methodology and methods. Each of these components is discussed below.

4.2.1 *Ontology:*

According to Saunders *et al.* (2009), ontology is concerned with nature of reality that is defined by Hudson and Ozanne (1988) indistinguishably. Similarly, Guba and Lincoln (1994) define it as the philosophy of reality and the nature and form of reality to constitute legitimate researchable questions. It is also called as the study of being (Crotty, 1998). Therefore, ontological assumptions are concerned with what constitutes reality. Thus, researchers need to take a position regarding the perceptions of how things really are and how things work (Scotland, 2012). In addition, Edirisingha (2012) explains that ontology is concerned with identifying the overall nature of existence of a particular phenomenon.

Thus, relating with the study, ontology of this study adopts objectivism view and avoids the subjectivism view. According to objectivism, reality exists independent of humans (Lakoff, 1987). In other words, it is an external to social actors (Saunders *et al.*, 2007). On the other hand, subjectivists state that knowledge does not exist independent of the learner because knowledge is constructed (Vrasidas, 2000). Saunder *et al.* (2007) clearly explains about subjectivism as the social phenomena that are created from perceptions and consequent actions of social actors. In addition, this is a continual process and through the process of social interaction, these social phenomena are in a constant state of revision. However, this study is completely focused on financial ratios and figures which remain structured even if the personnel of financial service companies is different over time. In addition, the data collection of this study is from secondary source, which is from annual report of the sample companies. Therefore, the ontology of this study adopts deductive research approach where it involves development of a theory that is subjected to a rigorous test.

4.2.2 Epistemology:

According to Burrell and Morgan (1979), epistemology is concerned with knowledge that constitutes acceptable, valid and legitimate knowledge and how one can communicate to others. Guba and Lincoln (1994) also define it as the philosophy of knowledge or how one comes to know and what counts as knowledge. Epistemology can also be defined as the relationship between the researcher and the reality or how the reality is captured or known (Carson *et al.*, 2001). Edirisingha (2012) claims that it is about how one go about uncovering the knowledge that is external to researcher and learn about reality. For instance, epistemology is concerned with questions such as how one knows what is true and how one distinguish true from false. Therefore, it is internal to the researcher and it shows how researcher sees the world around them. Thus, epistemology demonstrates validity and scope of knowledge.

According to Jackson (2012), there are seven sources of knowledge. These are intuition knowledge, authority knowledge, tenacity knowledge, rationalism knowledge, empiricism knowledge and science knowledge. When a person gains knowledge through intuition, it means the knowledge is based on human feelings such as intuition, faith, belief etc. Knowledge through authority represents knowledge gained from those viewed as authority figures such as experts, celebrities, leaders etc. Tenacity knowledge involves in obtaining knowledge through repeated ideas that are stubbornly clung to despite evidence to the contrary such as slogan, advertisement etc. When a person gains knowledge through rationalism, it involves logical reasoning. Empirical knowledge involves obtaining knowledge through objective observation and experiences. Gaining knowledge through science involves the combination of empiricism and rationalism. Scientific knowledge collects data and tests the hypotheses with data.

Thus, in relation to seven sources of knowledge, the source of this study is based on scientific knowledge. Since the scientific knowledge collects data and tests the hypotheses, this study collects data from the annual report of financial service companies in the UK and also reviews for the period of twenty one (21) years. In addition, sixteen hypotheses also set to test the main aim of this study, which is to examine the impact of capital structure and its determinants on profitability of financial service companies in the UK. Therefore, the epistemology of this study is based on scientific knowledge and the other sources of

knowledge are avoided. This means this research has adopted observable phenomenon based on financial data as knowledge. Since scientific knowledge is empiricism and rationalism, the philosophy of this study is associated with the philosophy of positivism (see 4.3.1 research philosophies) because positivism is empiricism, logicism, objectivism, and scientism (Sousa, 2010) where reality is stable regardless of the researcher's perspective or belief.

4.3 Methodology

Sarantakos (1998) describes it as the procedure that researchers use to investigate their beliefs and rationale behind the procedures. Crotty (1998) defines methodology as the strategy or plan of action, which lies behind the choice, and use of particular methods. Thus, methodology is concerned with why, what, from where, when and how data is collected and analysed (Scotland, 2012). In other words, it is a systematic way and process of solving the research. In short, Schwardt (2007) defines it as a theory of how a research should proceed. Thus, the selected approaches for this study has been discussed systematically in this chapter such as research philosophy, research approach and design and research methods. These approaches are further discussed below.

4.3.1 Research Philosophies: According to Blaxter *et al.* (2006), philosophy of research is a belief about how the data should be gathered, analysed and used. In western tradition of science, there are two main research philosophies. These two philosophies are positivism and interpretivism. Based on epistemology, this study involves data and numerical values which remain structured. Therefore, positivism is applied in this study and the reason for applying this approach is discussed below and compared with other philosophies.

a) *Positivism:* The term "Positivism" was first introduced by Saint Simon and later popularised by the French sociologist and philosopher, Auguste Comte (1798-1857) who is considered to be the father of the positivist movement in the first half of the 19th Century (Crotty, 1998; Tanzella-Nitti *et al.*, 2002). Commonly, positivism is referred to as empiricism, foundationalism, instrumentalism, logicism, modernism, objectivism and scientism (Sousa, 2010). Levin (1988) states that positivists believe that reality is stable and can be observed and described from an objective point of view. In other words, the positivist believes that the world is external (Carson *et al.*, 2001) and that there is a single objective to any research phenomenon or situation despite the fact that every researcher's perspective or

belief is not fixed (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). For instance, “*a tree in the forest is a tree, regardless of whether anyone is aware of its existence or not*” (Scotland, 2012). Thus, positivistic statements are descriptive and factual which are based on data and facts (House, 1991). Due to this reason, positivists attempt to identify causes, which influence outcomes (Creswell, 2009) because the main objective of positivist is prediction (Sousa, 2010). In addition, a study can be made on the previous observation and explanation about the realities and their inter-relationships (Gicheru, 2013). In a research work, positivist controls the situation and follows the structural approach in conducting research. Positivist executes this process by identifying a clear research topic, constructing appropriate hypotheses and by adopting a suitable research methodology (Churchill, 1996; Carson *et al.*, 2001). Besides, Carson *et al.* (2001) state that a positivist research seeks objectivity and use rational and logical approaches consistently in their research. Due to this reason, statistical and mathematical techniques are important to positivist research, which follow the structured research techniques to uncover single and objective reality (Carson *et al.*, 2001).

The data for this study is gathered from the secondary source, which is the annual report of financial service companies in the UK. This annual reports provide financial ratios of the firms that involve data sets and the numerical figures which remain structured. Previous study is used to build a conceptual framework and hypotheses are set in order to achieve the main objectives of this study. To translate the raw data into a meaningful one and to predict the impact of capital structure on profitability, this study adopts statistical instrument such as correlation and regression analysis. As discussed earlier, positivism believes in stable reality and facts. Regardless of researcher’s perspective or belief, the data of FSCs for this study presents facts, which remain unvarying for any researcher. Similarly, hypotheses set for this study are strictly dependent on controlled and structured assumptions. In addition, the results of this study are statistically proven which also remains unvarying and structured for any researcher. Therefore, positivism is found to be the most suitable philosophy for this study.

b) *Interpretivism*: Interpretivism is based on relativism (Scotland, 2012). Relativism is the view that reality is subjective and differs from person to person (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Scotland (2012) states that the realities are mediated by person’s senses and without consciousness, the world is meaningless. Crotty (1998) confirms that reality emerges when consciousness engages with objects, which are already filled with meaning. According to Grix (2004), interpretivism is based on real world phenomenon because world does not exist

independently of the knowledge of it. Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991) states that it focuses on reality as a human construct which can only be understood subjectively. Unlike positivist, interpretivist does not work with falsifiable statements or strict hypotheses (Ballsun-Staton, 2010). For instance, “*a tree is not a tree without someone calling it a tree. It is human beings who have constructed it as a tree, given it the name and attributed to it the associations we make with trees*” (Scotland, 2012). Therefore, interpretivism recognises that different people may construct meaning in different ways (Crotty, 1998). In addition, Cresswell (2009) interprets interpretivism as the understanding phenomenon from an individual’s perspective and with participation in both social and cultural life (Elster, 2007; Walsham, 1995).

4.3.2 Other Research Philosophies:

a) *Realism*: Critical realism is a meta-theory for social science. This research philosophy relies on the idea of independence of reality from the human mind. This philosophy is based on the assumption of a scientific approach to the development of knowledge. According to this philosophy, there are two groups of realism, which are direct and critical realism. The direct realism, which is also called as naive realism, can be described as “what you see is what you get” (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). In other words, direct realism sees the world through personal senses and there are no other interferences. On the other hand, critical realism argues that humans experience the personal sensations and images of the real world. According to critical realism, both the experiences can be illusive and usually do not show the real world (Novikov and Novikov, 2013). Direct realists perceive the world as unchanging and they concentrate only on one level. However, critical realists, accept the presence of multi-level phenomenon. Therefore, critical realism philosophy appreciates the influence and interrelationship between the individual, the group and the organization.

b) *Postmodernism*: This philosophy accepts basic ontological assumption of relativism and claims that there is no “objective” or final truth because all truth is socially constructed entity. According to this philosophy, all the knowledge of reality is dependent on human culture, personality and biology, which cannot be disconnected from what a specific group of people or culture calls knowledge. Postmodernists believe that there is no fixed, universal and eternal foundation to reality. Since, reality is influenced by culture and the culture changes over time and differs from community to community, the reality cannot be same for everyone. Therefore, knowledge is fundamentally fragmented and unstable (Intgrty, 2016).

c) *Pragmatism*: Pragmatism is formulated by early scholars like James (1907), Peirce (1931), Dewey (1931) and Mead (1938) as an alternative philosophy. According to this philosophy, there are many different ways of interpreting the world and undertaking research. This philosophy believes that there is no single point of view that can give full picture because there are multiple realities (Saunders *et al.*, 2012) and research question is the most important determinant of the research philosophy. Due to this reason, pragmatism suggests the combination of both positivism and interpretivism philosophy according to the nature of the research question. Thus, pragmatic paradigm implies the combination of methods, which is necessary to provide appropriate answer to research questions. For instance, this process can be a combination of data collection methods and data analysis procedures within the research process (Creswell, 2003).

4.3.3 *Research Approaches*:

a) *Deductive*: According to Saunders *et al.* (2009), it involves the development of a theory that is subjected to a rigorous test. Similarly, Greener (2008) describes that deductive approach starts with theoretical study, development of hypotheses from the related theory and proceeds to test the theory. In addition, deductive approach constitutes development of an assumption based on existing theories and forms a research plan to test the assumption (Wilson, 2010; Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). According to Holloway (1997), this approach starts with the development of idea or theoretical framework, which is followed by usage of data to verify or disprove the idea. In addition, this approach is incorporated in the development of hypotheses, selection of variables and the measurement of the results. This research process dominates management studies (Johnson, 2015) and in social sciences in general (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Thus, the value of this approach is able to make use of previous researchers' work (Ali and Birley, 1999).

This study develops theoretical framework by depending on previous studies. Theoretical framework helps to develop independent and dependent variables for this study. Thus, based on theoretical framework and research variables, the conceptual framework is developed which prompts the development of research hypotheses. With the help of the FSCs' financial data, the theory of the impact of capital structure on profitability is verified whether to accept or reject the theory. Since deductive approach verifies or disproves the idea built for the

study, deductive approach is more appropriate for this research because it starts with theory expressed in the form of hypotheses, which are then tested (Bryman, 1988).

b) *Inductive*: Inductive approach starts with specific observations before it develops the theory (Zalaghi and Khazaei, 2016). In other words, it starts with the observations and theories are proposed towards the end of the research process as a result of observations (Goddard and Melville, 2004). Zalaghi and Khazaei (2016) clearly explain that once the number of observations is selected correctly, conclusions are drawn from the observations to similar phenomenon. However, these conclusions need to be tested which might be verified or rejected. Until the conclusions are verified, any observation that is derived based on inductive approach can be theoretically falsifiable. Due to this reason, a researcher must honestly, with no prejudgments and biases and with an impartial mind, register what they observe. Then these observations form a basis on which theories and laws are constructed and become scientific knowledge. Since no theory is applied at the beginning of the research, the researcher has a complete privilege in terms of determining the research work. In particular, there is no assumption at the early stages of research and the researcher is not sure about the kind and the nature of findings.

4.3.4 *Types of the Research:*

Methodology of a research is often classified as qualitative, quantitative and mixed method in academic research (Harwell, 2011). Therefore, identification of an ideal type of research is crucial in research because information derived from each type of research is different. The types of research employed for this study is discussed below.

a) *Qualitative Research*: Denzin and Lincoln (2000) claim that qualitative research involves an interpretive and naturalistic approach. This indicates that researchers who adopt qualitative research can study things in their natural settings to interpret what they observe. For instance, this is suitable to understand how people make sense of their world and the experiences they have in the world or the meaning people have constructed (Merriam, 2009). Similarly, qualitative research is concerned with developing explanations of social phenomena. This means, it aims to help to understand the social issues of the world (Hancock *et al.*, 2007).

b) *Quantitative Research*: As this research uses raw data to measure the hypotheses, quantitative research approach is employed. For instance, the financial reports data of FSCs in the UK has been used as to analyse the impact of capital structure on profitability. Thus, quantitative research approach is suitable for this study. Kothari (2004) defines quantitative research as a research that measures quantity or amount. This study is supported by Zikmund *et al.* (2009) who define quantitative business research as a study that addresses objectives through empirical assessments that involves numerical measurement to analysis the phenomenon. In relation to the definition, quantitative researchers start with a considerable amount of activity mainly development of the theories and data collection procedures before the measuring of concepts. Later, the numeric values are used in statistical computations and hypothesis testing (Zikmund *et al.*, 2009). As this study adopts positivism and deductive approach, this study falls under quantitative research. This concept is validated by Berg (2001) who identifies quantitative research as a positivistic approach and quantitative research is frequently described as deductive in nature (Harwell, 2011).

4.3.5 *Research Design*:

Research design can be defined as a sketched out plan for a research study, which guides a researcher with a framework to gather data (Leedy, 1997). It can be explained as a plan that leads to a selection of appropriate subjects, research area and procedures to collect data in order to answer the research questions in an effective manner (Macmillan and Schumacher, 2001). Further, Durrheim (2004) states that it is a strategic framework leading to action that bridges between the research questions and the implementation of the research strategy. The research design for this study is discussed below.

a) *Exploratory Research*: Exploratory research is also termed as a formulative research studies (Kothari, 2004). The main purpose this type studies is to formulate a problem for more precise investigation (Ackoff, 1962; Singh, 2014). In other words, the primary goal of this research is to gain better understanding of an issue or situation. It is appropriate to provide ground work for rigorous studies at a later date (Davis 2000; Zikmund, 2003; Cooper and Schindler, 2006). This research is useful in the situations where limited information is available and the researcher wishes to have the flexibility to future explore areas of research (Polonsky and Waller, 2005; Cooper and Schindler, 2006).

b) *Descriptive Research*: Descriptive research is a type of research, which is involved in describing the characteristics of a particular individual or of a group (Kothari, 2004). The main goal of this research is to describe a phenomenon and its characteristics (Nassaji, 2015). Therefore, observation and survey tools are often used to gather data (Gall, *et al.*, 2007). For instance, specific predictions with narration of facts and characteristics about individual, group or situation are the processes involved in descriptive research studies. In addition, Ethridge (2004) describes this type of research as a study that determines, describe or identify “*what is*”, while analytical research attempts to establish “*why it is that way*” or “*how it came to be*”. Thus, descriptive research is aimed at revealing information or details on current issues or problems through a process of data collection that enables the researcher to explain the situation more precisely (Fox and Bayat, 2007).

c) *Explanatory Research*: Explanatory studies go beyond description and aims to explain the reasons for the phenomenon while the descriptive study only observes the situation. In explanatory study, researcher use theories or hypotheses to represent the forces that cause a certain phenomenon to occur (Akhtar, 2016). The present research design is guided by the study’s aim to investigate the impact of firms’ capital structure on its profitability in FSCs in the UK. As this involves conducting a study where variable x causes variable y, where variable x are a variables of capital structure and variable y are a variables of profitability, explanatory research is found to be suitable for this study. Explanatory research is appropriate when the objective of a research to identify the causes of the phenomenon (Elahi and Dehdashti, 2011). Given the objective of the study, explanatory research is suitable for the present study as it is aimed at examining linkage between variables by observing existing phenomena through available data to identify causal relationships (Ross, 2005).

Since this study aims to investigate the effect of capital structure of FSCs on its profitability, an explanatory research is adopted in this study. This approach is ideal for this research as explanatory research identifies the cause and effect relationships between variables (Zikmund, 2000).

d) *Experimental Research*: This research design is used to test relationship under controlled situation (Akhtar, 2016). In other words, an experiment research is an observation under controlled conditions. For instance, it is a design in which some of the variables under study are manipulated or under controlled condition. Controlling of conditions means that the

situation or condition is not allowed to change while the experimentation is going on. In this type of study, various types of evidence have to be controlled so that hypotheses can be tested. Therefore, the primary goal of an experimental design is to study a connection between the independent and dependent variables. A secondary goal is to extract the maximum amount of information with the minimum expenditure of resources.

4.4 Research Methods

A research method is a specific technique and procedure involved in the collection and analysis of data (Crotty, 1998). Research methods include various procedures, schemes and algorithms (Rajasekar *et al.*, 2013). Bodla and Turan (n.d.) clearly explains research method as a technique that is used to conduct a research. It includes all the methods applied by a researcher so that available data can be used to provide a solution for a given problem. In this study, target population, sampling method, data collection method and method of data measurement are used as methods. These methods are discussed below.

4.4.1 Target Population:

Population in a research is the observation or measurement of an entire set under study (Keller and Warrack, 2000). In other words, population is a set of all possible measurements pertaining to a group of people or objects that is of interest (Kvanli *et al.*, 2000). Thus, target population is a group or an individual on whom research is conducted (Kitchenham and Pfleeger, 2002).

In this study, target population of the research is the FSCs in the UK, listed on London Stock Exchange (LSE) for twenty one years or more. The period for this study is for twenty one years which is from 1998 to 2017. Twenty one years is taken as a study period as lengthy time period of the study produce better results (Nasimi, 2016). There are three major financial crisis which occurred during this period, namely, Asia Crisis from 1997 to 1998, Dotcom Bubble from 1999 to 2000 and Global Financial Crisis from 2007 to 2008 (Anderson, 2013). Therefore, any FSCs that are listed in LSE for at least twenty-one years or more has a potential to provide sufficient information or data on the strategies adopted by FSCs to face these catastrophic events. These events are crucial in studying the operation of FSCs capital structure during this period to sustain their business. Considering all these reasons, the target

population for this study is the FSCs that have been listed in LSE at least for twenty-one years.

4.4.2 *Sampling:*

A sample is a finite part of a statistical population on which a study is conducted to gain information about the whole population (Webster, 1985). In other words, it is a process of extracting a sample from a population, which is defined as a group of relatively smaller number of population selected from a larger population for investigation purpose (Alvi, 2016). To derive information from larger population, the sampling follows certain procedures, which are sampling frame, sampling methods and sample size. These processes are discussed below.

a) *Sampling Frame:* Sampling frame is a list that contains all the list of items from which the sample is to be drawn. All such sampling units is called sampling frame (Kothari, 2004). The LSE website is the sampling frame in this study. The list of FSCs has been gathered from the industry sector link in the website of LSE. In this link, LSE records all the companies that are listed in LSE. Therefore, this study uses LSE and UK government website to gather the sample of FSCs in the UK. The data listed on LSE is according to 30th September 2018 and the data has been accessed between 4th October 2018 to 31st January 2019.

b) *Sampling Method:* In sampling method, there are mainly two techniques in choosing the sample size, which are probability and non-probability sampling techniques. Probability sampling is a technique used in random selection of sample whereas non-probability sampling is a sample, which is applied on the basis of subjective judgment of the investigator (Alvi, 2016). Since this research is a quantitative research, the sampling method for this study is a probability sampling method. However, there are five hundred and forty-nine (549) FSCs listed in LSE in total. Out of five hundred and forty-nine companies, sixty (60) companies meet the requirement of this research as these companies are listed from or before 1998 as this study are conducted from 1998 to 2018. Thus, the financial data of sixty FSCs, which are listed on LSE for at least twenty one years or more, is selected in this study. Other companies have been omitted because data is not available to the researcher. Thus, fully eligible FSCs are selected in this probability sampling.

c) *Sample Size*: Sample size is a subset of data selected from the population (Sincich, 1996). In other words, it is a part of research population from which information can be gathered (Weiss, 1999). Since this research shortlists sixty FSCs out of five hundred and forty-nine FSCs, the data have been accessed from these sixty FSCs only. The data gathered is for the period of twenty one years that stretch across sixty companies. Upon calculation of data of sixty FSCs for twenty-one years, the sample data comes to one thousand two hundred and sixty. The equation is given below.

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \text{ company for 21 years (1 x 21)} &= 21 \text{ data per company.} \\ 60 \text{ companies for 21 years (60 x 21)} &= 1,260 \text{ data in total.} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, there is one thousand two hundred and sixty sample data used in this study.

4.4.3 *Data Collection*:

Data is acquired from primary and secondary sources. Primary data is the first-hand information obtained by a researcher whereas secondary data is the information collected from the already existing sources.

In this research, the data has been collected from the secondary source which is from the annual financial report of FSCs in the UK. These financial reports are gathered from the LSE and Govt.UK. From these two organisations' website the annual reports of FSCs is gathered. Secondary sources produce varied source of information such as books and periodicals, Government publications of economic indicators, census data, statistical abstracts, data base, the media and annual reports of companies (Sekaran, 2003). Since data has been gathered and recorded previously for some other purposes, it becomes a historical and assembled data, which is why access to respondents are not required for secondary data (Zikmund, 2000).

After the annual reports of FSCs is collected, Microsoft excel is used to calculate the raw data. Then, the calculated data for each company is coded in SPSS according to the independent and dependent variables.

4.4.4 *Statistical Instrument:*

Research tools are important part of any research as it is through the instrument that meaning can be given to the data gathered in a research. Drawing the most appropriate conclusion from the study is possible by proper arrangement of the raw data (Marak and Chaipoopirutana, 2014). Thus, the statistical model used in this study, including descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and regression analysis. The SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Science) is used to analyse the data after the data collection stage is finished.

a) *Descriptive Statistics:* According to Sincich (1996), the branch of statistics is devoted to organization, summarization and description of data. Descriptive statistics involves arranging, summarizing and presenting a set of data in such a way that the meaningful essentials of the data can be extracted and interpreted easily (Keller and Warrack, 2000). Descriptive statistics is used to describe a large set of data (Kvanli *et al.*, 2000) to understand and summarize the data (Adams *et al.*, 2007). In brief, descriptive statistics consists of methods for organizing and summarizing information (Weiss, 1999).

b) *Correlation Analysis:* Zikmund (2003) states that the Pearson correlation method is considered as the proper technique to describe the relationship of variable and enable researcher to investigate the relationship between variables. The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to +1, the values that close to -1 or +1 mean a strong linear relationship while the closer the correlation is to zero mean the weaker the relationship between variables. The value of correlation coefficient is +1 mean a sample correlation coefficient of +1 corresponds to a perfect positive linear relationship between x and y while the value of correlation coefficient is -1 mean a sample correlation coefficient of -1 corresponds to a perfect negative linear relationship between x and y. A positive coefficient means the values of variable x and y move in the same direction while a negative coefficient means the values of variable x and y move in the opposite direction.

c) *Regression Analysis:* This analysis provides an understanding about the value of the dependent variable changes when independent variable is varied (Nasimi, 2016). Therefore, Regression analysis is used on Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Regression analysis is used in the analysis because it investigates the relationship between variables (Sykes, 1992) and it can predict the variables, especially, the change of value in independent

variables that changes dependent variables (Zhang, 2009). Since this study is an explanatory research, to study the impact of capital structure on firms' profitability, this analysis meets the criteria of this research.

Since, the objective of this research is to test the impact of capital structure and its determinants towards profitability of FSCs in the UK, the ordinary least-square (OLS) method is used in this study as this technique is the most used regression estimation technique. In this study, the researcher uses four regression models. Therefore, the regression model of each model is given below.

The equation of model one is written as:

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \beta_8X_8 + \dots + \beta_nX_n + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Capital Structure (STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1FC_1 + \beta_2GDP_2 + \beta_3INF_3 + \beta_4IR_4 + \beta_5ROA_5 + \beta_6ROE_6 + \beta_7ROIC_7 + \beta_8ROCE_8 + \epsilon$$

Where:

\hat{Y} = Capital Structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER.

β_0 = Estimated intercept of the y axis.

β_1 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of FC.

X_1 = Macro environment in terms of FC.

β_2 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of GDP.

X_2 = Macro environment in terms of GDP.

β_3 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of INF.

X_3 = Macro environment in terms of INF.

β_4 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of IR.

X_4 = Macro environment in terms of IR.

β_5 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROA.

X_5 = Profitability in terms of ROA.

β_6 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROE.

X_6 = Profitability in terms of ROE.

β_7 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROIC.

X_7 = Profitability in terms of ROIC.

B_8 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROCE.

X_8 = Profitability in terms of ROCE.

ϵ = Error available.

The equation of model two is written as:

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \beta_9 X_9 + \beta_{10} X_{10} + \beta_{11} X_{11} + \beta_{12} X_{12} + \beta_{13} X_{13} + \beta_{14} X_{14} + \beta_{15} X_{15} + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Capital Structure (STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FC_1 + \beta_2 GDP_2 + \beta_3 INF_3 + \beta_4 IR_4 + \beta_5 ROA_5 + \beta_6 ROE_6 + \beta_7 ROIC_7 + \beta_8 ROCE_8 + \beta_9 TA_9 + \beta_{10} AG_{10} + \beta_{11} FA_{11} + \beta_{12} EPS_{12} + \beta_{13} LR_{13} + \beta_{14} IC_{14} + \beta_{15} ET_{15} + \epsilon$$

Where:

\hat{Y} = Capital Structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER.

β_0 = Estimated intercept of the y axis.

β_1 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of FC.

X_1 = Macro environment in terms of FC.

β_2 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of GDP.

X_2 = Macro environment in terms of GDP.

β_3 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of INF.

X_3 = Macro environment in terms of INF.

β_4 = Regression coefficient associated with macro environment in terms of IR.

X_4 = Macro environment in terms of IR.

B_5 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROA.

X_5 = Profitability in terms of ROA.

B_6 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROE.

X_6 = profitability in terms of ROE.

B_7 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROIC.

X_7 = profitability in terms of ROIC.

B_8 = Regression coefficient associated with profitability in terms of ROCE.

X_8 = profitability in terms of ROCE.

B_9 = Regression coefficient associated with control variable in terms of TA.

X_9 = Control Variable in terms of TA.

B_{10} = Regression coefficient associated control variable in terms of AG.

X_{10} = Control Variable in terms of AG.

B_{11} = Regression coefficient associated control variable in terms of FA.

X_{11} = Control Variable in terms of FA.

B_{12} = Regression coefficient associated control variable in terms of EPS.

X_{12} = Control Variable in terms of EPS.

B_{13} = Regression coefficient associated control variable in terms of LR.

X_{13} = Control Variable in terms of LR.

B_{14} = Regression coefficient associated control variable in terms of IC.

X_{14} = Control Variable in terms of IC.

B_{15} = Regression coefficient associated with control variable in terms of ET.

X_{15} = Control variable in terms of ET.

e = Error available.

The equation of model three is written as:

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_n X_n + e$$

$$\text{Profitability (ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{STDR}_1 + \beta_2 \text{LTDR}_2 + \beta_3 \text{TDR}_3 + \beta_4 \text{DER}_4 + e$$

Where:

\hat{Y} = Profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE.

β_0 = Estimated intercept of the y axis.

β_1 = Regression coefficient associated with capital structure in terms of STDR.

X_1 = Capital structure in terms of STDR.

β_2 = Regression coefficient associated with capital structure in terms of LTDR.

X_2 = Capital structure in terms of LTDR.

β_3 = Regression coefficient associated with capital structure in terms of TDR.

X_3 = Capital structure in terms of TDR.

β_4 = Regression coefficient associated with capital structure in terms of DER.

X_4 = Capital structure in terms of DER.

e = Error available.

The equation of model four is written as:

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Profitability (ROA)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AG}_1 + \beta_2 \text{EPS}_2 + \beta_3 \text{FC}_3 + \beta_4 \text{INF}_4 + \beta_5 \text{STDR}_5 + \beta_6 \text{LTDR}_6 + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Profitability (ROE)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AG}_1 + \beta_2 \text{EPS}_2 + \beta_3 \text{FC}_3 + \beta_4 \text{INF}_4 + \beta_5 \text{STDR}_5 + \beta_6 \text{DER}_6 + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Profitability (ROIC)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AG}_1 + \beta_2 \text{EPS}_2 + \beta_3 \text{FC}_3 + \beta_4 \text{GDP}_4 + \beta_5 \text{INF}_5 + \beta_6 \text{STDR}_6 + \beta_7 \text{LTDR}_7 + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Profitability (ROCE)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AG}_1 + \beta_2 \text{EPS}_2 + \beta_3 \text{ET}_3 + \beta_4 \text{FC}_4 + \beta_5 \text{INF}_5 + \beta_6 \text{STDR}_6 + \beta_7 \text{TDR}_7 + \beta_8 \text{DER}_8 + \epsilon$$

Where:

\hat{Y} = Profitability in terms of return on ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE.

β_0 = Estimated intercept of the y axis.

β = Regression coefficient associated with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET; with macro environment in terms of FC, INF and GDP; with capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER.

X = control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET; with macro environment in terms of FC, INF and GDP; with capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER.

ϵ = Error available.

The researcher applies an ordinary least square linear regression model for this study in order to validate the dependent and independent variables. In this analysis, there are three main indicators, which indicate the significance of this study.

Firstly, to determine how well a regression model fits the data, the value of R and R² is estimated. The value of R represents the measurement of the quality of prediction of the dependent variables. It shows whether the relationship between dependent and independent variables are positively or negatively related. The R value is stronger when the value is closer to one in both positive and negative direction that is $R < 1$. Further, R² represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variables that explained by the independent variables.

Secondly, to predict the statistical significance of independent variables towards the dependent variables, F test is estimated. The significant level of F test is .05, which is significant when the estimated P value is less than .05, that is $P < .05$. If the probability value is less than or equal to .05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, showing the F-test is significant which means that the linear regression model is reliable. Thus, the results prove that there is a significant relationship with the dependent variables at least with one independent variable. On the other hand, if the probability value is more than .05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, showing the F-test is insignificant which means that the linear regression model is not reliable. Thus, the model cannot to be used to predict the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Thirdly, to predict statistical significance of each of the independent variables, a t test is estimated. The significant level of the t test is .05, meaning that the t test is significant when the estimated P value is less than .05 that is $P < .05$. Thus, the results prove that there is a significant relationship with one particular independent variable with the dependent variables. Furthermore, to indicate how much the dependent variable varies with particular independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant, unstandardised coefficients is estimated, which shows the positive or negative significance of a particular independent variable towards the dependent variables.

4.4 Summary

Research methodology is an important process in research because appropriate approach, methods and techniques helps research to be conducted in meaningful way. In order to achieve the research objectives, this study follows several research paradigms. This study adopts objectivism where knowledge is external to researcher and based on data and facts or not from the feelings. Besides, this study supports objectivism by approving positivism philosophy where the methodology of this study is controlled and structured. Thus, deductive approach is adopted to test the hypotheses in order to verify or disprove the theory.

Since this study follows positivism philosophy and deductive approach, quantitative research has been chosen to conduct data collection, which is from secondary data sources. Appropriate sample is chosen in this chapter to examine the FSCs. There are sixty sample companies and one thousand two hundred and sixty data collected for the analysis. To translate the data into meaningful information, correlation and regression analysis have been employed.

CHAPTER FIVE

Presentation of Data and Critical Discussion of the Results

5.1 Introduction

This is the empirical chapter of the research. It aims to examine the impact of micro and macro factors on the capital structure and firm performance. Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) has been used to analyse the data. The results of the data analysis consist of three main sections. These are descriptive analysis of the variables and hypotheses testing by using correlation analysis and regression analysis.

5.2 Descriptive Analysis of Variable

In this study, data has been obtained from secondary source of 60 financial service companies on the London Stock Exchange from 1998 to 2018. A total number of observations can be seen in the second column of Table 5.1, which is 1200. The minimum and maximum value of each variable is shown in the third and fourth columns. The fifth column shows the mean value of each variable, which, in other words is the average value of each variable. In the sixth column, the standard deviation of each variable that measures the level of dispersion of data from its mean can be seen. This denotes that larger the standard deviation, larger is the dispersion from its mean.

During the period, Table 5.1 below reveals the mean value of total assets which is 8.4 for the entire sample. The standard deviation showed 0.59, where the value of assets indicates that there is minimal variation during this period. This is clearly reflected in the minimum and maximum, which are 6.9 and 9.9 respectively. These figures indicate that the sample firms used in this study are comparably similar in size.

In relation to total asset, asset growth rate of financial service companies (FSCs) is revealed to be of an average of 8.21 percent growth during 1998 to 2018. As compared to total assets, assets growth rate is shown to be more deviated. A standard deviation for the period is 27.47 percent. The minimum assets growth rate is -72 percent and the maximum assets growth is showed as 308 percent. These figures indicate that assets growth rate of the sample

companies highly fluctuated during the period of 1998 to 2018. The fluctuations of asset value, determined by various reasons and financial crisis in 2001 and 2008-09 is one of the reasons that influenced the fluctuation of assets growth.

Table 5.1 Descriptive Analysis of Variables

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Total Assets (TA)	1260	6.882	9.898	8.41145	.589508
Assets Growth Rate (AG)	1260	-72.039	308.474	8.21032	27.469036
Firm Age (FA)	1260	2.100	161.700	53.26982	43.524125
Earnings Per Share (EPS)	1260	-426.600	873.020	41.72629	101.824593
Liquidity Ratio (LR)	1260	.013	514.887	6.65896	23.705095
Interest Coverage (IC)	1260	-10575.500	130291.778	266.88470	4183.734454
Effective Tax Rate (ET)	1260	-4.039	3.390	.03131	.216861
Financial Crisis (FC)	1260	.000	1.000	.19048	.392833
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	1260	-4.200	3.500	1.97143	1.625202
Inflation Rate (INF)	1260	.000	4.500	1.99048	1.038223
Bank Interest rate (IR)	1260	.250	6.250	2.67857	2.241137
Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	1260	.000	.632	.04097	.064484
Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	1260	.000	1.143	.08107	.119423
Total debt ratio (TDR)	1260	.000	1.236	.12232	.129086
Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	1260	.000	19.203	.36223	1.083836
Return on Asset (ROA)	1260	-1.317	.967	.05270	.201461
Return on Equity (ROE)	1260	-1.596	1.584	.06550	.241966
Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	1260	-1.366	.878	.03429	.206972
Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	1260	-1.338	1.029	.06981	.226514
Valid N (listwise)	1260				

During the period of 1998 to 2018, the average age of the sample firms is 53 years. The oldest firm that existed in the sample firms is 161 years and the newest firm is only 2 years. The variability of the age of the sample firms is 43.5 as shown in the standard deviation, which indicates high deviation. This is illustrative of the companies' existence that they greatly vary, throwing the light on the fact that some companies are relatively older, while some are rather newer in the financial service market. Despite the total assets of the sample,

firms are similar in size, which reveals that the sample of this study has been gathered from significantly dissimilar age.

In regard to the earning from the share, the average earning per share of the sample firms is 41.7 per share which confirms that shareholders earned 41.7 from the every share the investor held from the financial service companies during the period of 1998 to 2018. Furthermore, earning per share has shown the second highest deviation amongst the variable. The descriptive statistics show that the standard deviation for earning per share is 101.8. This is evident from the minimum and maximum figures of the sample data, which are -426.6 and 873 per share respectively. This indicates that, from the sample firms, shareholders earned as high as 873 per share. On the other hand, investors lost their earnings as low as -427 per share during the period 1998 to 2018.

As far as the ability of meeting the short-term obligations is concerned, the data sample reveals that the average liquidity ratio for the period of 1998 to 2018 is 6.7 percent. Standard deviation is recorded to be 23.7 percent for liquidity ration which signifies that there is variation in the sample data. The variability of data is shown in the minimum and the maximum of the sample data which are .01 and 514.9 percent respectively. Thus, the sample data of this study indicates that majority of the firms from the sample firms are meeting the short-term obligations.

In terms of companies' ability to meet its interest in a timely manner, the average interest coverage ratio is denoted to be 266.9 percent for the period of 1998 to 2018. This reveals that sample firms in this study have the ability to cover its interest on due date. However, this variable has revealed to be bearing the highest variability amongst the variables of this study. The standard deviation is showed as 4183.7 percent for two decades from 1998 to 2018 signifying that there are relatively high number of companies whose interest coverage ratio is negative. This is identified in the minimum value for interest coverage ratio of table 5.1 which is -10575.5 percent. Nevertheless, the maximum value is 130291.8 percent for the period of the study. This indicates that majority of the sample firms were meeting the interest payment on time.

The sample firms in this study exhibit that the companies significantly paid less tax during the period of 1998 to 2018. This has been reflected in the mean value of descriptive statistics which show the average effective tax rate at 0.031 percent. In addition, standard deviation is shown as 0.22 percent which signifies less deviation. It is to be noted that the minimum value of the effective tax rate is depicted as -4 percent which implies that there are companies who gain tax benefits from the sample firms. On the other hand, the maximum value for the effective tax rate is 3.4 percent which is justifiable that the 3.4 percent is the maximum tax that the sample firms paid during the period of 1998 to 2018.

Table 5.1 throws light on the financial crisis that it has 0 minimum values and 1 maximum value. This is the reason as to why financial crisis has been used as a dummy variable in this study, where 1 stands for the crisis period in 2001 and between 2007 and 2019, and 0 for the non-crisis period.

During the period of 1998 to 2018, the average gross domestic product growth rate of the United Kingdom has been shown as 1.97 percent which indicates that gross domestic product had been experiencing a sluggish growth. Furthermore, the minimum value is -4.2 percent, which shows that there was a negative growth rate during the crisis period. Despite the positive growth rate, during the non-crisis period, the maximum value has been recorded to be 3.5 percent for the data sample. Therefore, it can be said that the gross domestic product growth rate of the United Kingdom does not show rapid growth rate during the study period. In addition, gross domestic product shows constant growth rate during the period as the standard deviation has been calculated to be merely 1.6 percent for the two decades from 1998 to 2018.

The average inflation rate is 1.99 percent during the period of 1998 to 2018. In similar to gross domestic product, inflation rate also depicts sluggish growth and the less change of the average price level in the United Kingdom market. It is showed to be 0 percent in the minimum value and this can be narrated as a static change of price level in the market. However, the maximum value, which is 4.5 percent, portrays the market to have been experiencing rapid growth by showing moderate inflation rate. Unlike the gross domestic product, inflation rate also illustrates constant growth rate during the period of 1998 to 2018 by demonstrating the deviation at 1 percent in the standard deviation.

During the period of 1998 to 2018, the average interest rate of Bank of England is shown as 2.7 percent, which means on an average, the sample firms of this study had an opportunity to acquire loan from the banks in a low interest rate in the United Kingdom. Standard deviation appears to have less variation, which is only 2.2 percent. Therefore, it can be said that Bank of England has been maintaining steady and low interest rate in the market. The lowest interest rate can be identified as 0.25 percent and the highest is 6.25 percent, which is shown in the minimum and maximum of Table 5.1. From these figures it can be comprehended that the borrowings are reasonably less expensive in the United Kingdom.

In regard to the leverage during the period of 1998 to 2018, the average short-term debt is recorded to be 4.1 percent and the average long-term debt is shown as 8.1 percent. This suggests that on the average, the sample firms have been employing more long-term debt than short-term debt as a proportion of total assets. The standard deviation for short-term debt is 0.064 and for long-term debt is 0.12. This indicates that long-term debts have higher variability than short-term debts. This variability is reflected on the range of the data, which has been recorded between 0.00 and 0.63 for short-term debts and between 0.00 and 1.14 for long-term debts.

In similar to short and long term debts, the average total debt is .12232 for the whole sample firms during the period of 1998 to 2018. This reveals that on the average 12.2 percent of debt finance is utilised to fund the total assets by the sample firms. Standard deviation of total debts has shown to be .13, which is higher than both the short-term and long-term debts. This statistic suggests that total debts is highly variable than both the short-term and long-term debts. This variability is proven by the minimum and the maximum value of total debts in Table 5.1, which is recorded to be 0.00 and 1.24 respectively.

When proportion of debt and equity is taken into account, the average debt to equity ratio is shown as .36223 for the year 1998 to 2018. This indicates that on an average, the sample companies during the study period utilised more of equity funds than the debt funds which is recorded 36.2 percent of debt financing and 64 percent of equity funds. The standard deviation of 1.1 during the study period illustrates that there is higher variation than the total debts. Since the variability has wider range than the total debts, the results of descriptive statistics show the minimum of 0.00 and the maximum of 19.2. This is evident of the fact that some sample companies did not use any debts and some used only equity.

The performance variable, return on asset (ROA) that estimates the company's ability to generate profit by using its assets has shown that the average return on assets is 0.05270 for the period of 1998 to 2018. This portrays that the sample firms in this study have been generating profit by using its assets on the average of 5.27 percent, which is an average positive return for the financial service sector during the study period. The standard deviation of return on assets is 0.201461 for the sample data having 20.1 percent variability. The data range such as minimum and maximum value for the return on assets is -1.317 and .967 respectively which are -131.7 percent and 96.7 percent. This indicates that the negative return is higher than the positive return in spite of the average return is positive in the sample data.

The performance variable, return on equity (ROE), which estimates company's ability to generate profit by using shareholder's funds shows that the average return on equity is .06550 for the whole sample firms. This indicates that sample firms generated profit on the average of 6.55 percent from its shareholder's fund. Based on the data, return on equity is a positive return and showed higher return than the return on assets. Among the performance variable, return on equity shows the highest variability, which recorded the standard deviation of 24.2 percent. The data variation of return on equity has seen minimum of -159.6 percent and maximum of 158.4 percent.

The performance variables, return on invested capital (ROIC) and return on capital employed (ROCE), which estimated the efficiency of investment to generate the return produces the average value of 0.03429 and 0.06981 respectively. This indicates that return on capital employed is shown to be 6.98 percent return. On the other hand, return on invested capital is only 3.4 percent return. Both the variables reveal positive return. However, return on capital employed exhibits higher return than the return on invested capital. Both the variables display similar standard deviation that is 20.7 percent for return on invested capital and 22.65 percent for return on capital employed. However, return on capital employed demonstrates slightly higher in return. In addition, the minimum value is -136.6 percent for return on invested capital and -133.8 percent for return on capital employed. The maximum value is 87.8 percent for return on invested capital and 102.9 percent for return on capital employed.

5.3 Correlation

In this study, Pearson correlation is employed in order to analyse the relationship of the variables. In correlation analysis, significance (P-value) level is below 0.05 and anything above 0.05 is insignificant (see appendix). In other way, -1 and 1 denote the strength of correlation. Correlation closer to 1 represents positive and stronger correlation, whereas correlation closer to -1 indicates negative and stronger correlation. The correlation closer to zero (0) signifies weak correlation.

Table 5.2 Pearson Correlation Matrix

	TA	AGR	FA	EPS	LR	IC	ETR	FC	GDP	INF	IR	ST	LT	TD	DE	ROA	ROE	ROIC	ROCE
TA	1	.059*	.101**	.214**	-.012	-.063*	.052	-.037	-.026	.036	-.153**	-.102**	.255**	.184**	.120**	.100**	.137**	.107**	.170**
AGR		1	-.073**	.466**	-.010	.140**	.013	-.237**	.196**	-.019	.095**	-.019	-.021	-.028	.121**	.671**	.648**	.678**	.668**
FA			1	-.070*	-.031	.028	.051	-.020	-.047	.038	-.123**	-.040	.169**	.135**	.114**	-.010	-.007	-.028	-.001
EPS				1	.058*	.044	.018	-.230**	.140**	-.012	-.013	-.051	-.002	-.027	-.013	.545**	.555**	.543**	.574**
LR					1	.007	-.032	.003	-.035	.043	-.037	-.153**	-.039	-.112**	-.054	.020	.005	.020	.000
IC						1	-.003	-.017	.007	.004	.004	-.035	-.042	-.056*	-.018	.102**	.075**	.087**	.091**
ETR							1	-.054	.017	.042	.006	.006	.178**	.168**	.223**	.019	.059*	.021	.092**
FC								1	-.529**	.156**	.070*	.038	.041	.056*	-.001	-.269**	-.260**	-.266**	-.266**
GDP									1	-.365**	.506**	-.072*	-.010	-.045	.028	.160**	.160**	.173**	.159**
INF										1	-.344**	.088**	-.036	.010	-.032	.021	.012	.017	.017
IR											1	-.058*	.077**	.044	.082**	-.020	-.004	-.002	-.009
ST												1	-.113**	.394**	.055	-.058*	-.057*	-.068*	-.032
LT													1	.867**	.348**	-.058*	.038	-.078**	.129**
TD														1	.349**	-.082**	.008	-.105**	.104**
DE															1	-.033	.094**	.010	.171**
ROA																1	.958**	.988**	.871**
ROE																	1	.966**	.885**
ROIC																		1	.863**
ROCE																			1

*.Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5.2 displays the correlation of both the independent variables and dependent variables. The correlation is observed as significant when the value is lower than or equal to 0.05 and anything above 0.05 is insignificant. In addition, table 5.2 denotes that the correlation of one asterisk (*) is significant at the 0.05 level and the correlation of two asterisk (**) is significant at the 0.01 level. The correlation between macro environment and capital structure displays interesting results. Financial crisis exhibits a positive correlation with only total

debts of capital structure. On the other hand, gross domestic product shows a negative correlation with short-term debts of capital structure. Both these variables exhibit correlation at the significant level of 0.05 levels. Inflation is found to have stronger correlation than financial crisis and gross domestic product where it is positively correlated at the significant level of 0.01 with short-term debts of capital structure. Interest rate represents better correlation with capital structure. It is found to bear negative correlation with short-term debts, positive correlation with long-term debts and debt to equity ratio. However, it shows significance at 0.05, which is a weaker correlation as compared to both the long-term debts and debt to equity ratio where both the variables are correlated at the significance level of 0.01.

The correlation between macro environment and capital structure demonstrates surprising results. Financial crisis depicts a negative correlation with all the profitability variables such as return on assets, return on equity, return on invested capital and return on capital employed at the significant level of 0.01. In the opposite direction, gross domestic product is recorded to have a positive correlation with all the profitability variables at the significance level of 0.01. Furthermore, both the inflation and interest rate produce an insignificant correlation with firm's profitability.

In regard to the control variables, Table 5.2 gives significant outcome. Total assets shows correlation with all the variables of capital structure and all the variables are correlated at 0.01 significance level. However, it exhibits positive correlation with long-term debts, total debts and debt to equity ratio except for short-term debts because it is negatively correlated to total assets. In relation to the assets, assets growth rate has a positive correlation only with debt to equity ratio of capital structure, correlated at 0.01 significance level. Firm age is revealed to have a positive correlation with long-term debts, total debts and debt to equity ratio of capital structure. It shows its significance at 0.01 level. However, Firm age signifies that there is no significant correlation with short-term debts of capital structure. In terms of liquidity, it reveals a negative and strong correlation with short-term and total debts of the capital structure which is correlated at 0.01 significant level. In the opposite manner, liquidity exhibits no significant correlation with long-term debts and debt to equity ratio of the capital structure. Similar to liquidity, interest coverage also depicts a negative correlation with long-term debts of capital structure. Unlike liquidity, it exhibits a weaker correlation which is at 0.05 significance level. On the other hand, interest coverage exhibits no significant

correlation with short-term debts, total debts and debt to equity ratio. Effective tax rate produces a significant correlation as it has a positively strong correlation with the variables like long-term debts, total debts and debt to equity ratio. This means that it has a significant level at 0.01 for all the three variables. On contrary, the effective tax rate shows no significant correlation with short-term debts of the capital structure.

The control variables like total assets, assets growth rate, earning per share and interest coverage illustrates a positive correlation with profitability of the firm such as return on assets, return on equity, return on invested capital and return on capital employed. All these variables are correlated at the significant level of 0.01. However, effective tax rate shows unique correlation with firm's performance. It has a positive correlation with only return on equity and return on capital employed. The significant level also differed to 0.05 and 0.01 significant level respectively and it shows no significant correlation with return on assets and return on invested capital. Furthermore, firm age and liquidity indicate insignificant correlation with the profitability of the firms.

The correlation between capital structure and the firm profitability show significant results. According to the table 5.2, short-term debts exhibits a negative correlation with three profitability variables such as return on assets, return on equity and return on invested capital. The significant level of this variable is at 0.05 level. However, short-term debts shows an insignificant correlation with return on capital employed. In similar to short-term debts, long-term debts also reveals a negative correlation with return on assets and return on invested capital. However, the strength of the significant level is dissimilar. Return on assets exhibits weaker correlation than the return on invested capital which is at the 0.05 and 0.01 significant level respectively. Return on equity appears to be insignificant with long-term debts. It also demonstrates a positive correlation with return on capital employed at 0.01 significant level. In addition, total debts also shows a similar negative correlation with return on assets and return on invested capital and a positive with return on capital employed at a significance level of 0.01. It also manifests an insignificant correlation with return on equity. As opposed to other capital structure variables, debt to equity exhibits a positive correlation with return on equity and return on capital employed at the significant level of 0.01. Profitability variables such as return on assets and return on invested capital exhibit an insignificant correlation.

5.4 Hypotheses Testing with Regression Analysis

For estimation purposes, the significant level of t-statistics is shown in this part. If the significant value is less than the 0.05 significant levels, it indicates that the independent variable is statistically significant to the dependent variable. However, if it is more than the 0.05 significant level, the independent variable is statistically insignificant to the dependent variables. To measure the hypotheses, there are four model developed in this study. Model 1 uses capital structure as dependent variable and macro-economic factors and profitability variable as independent variables. Model 2 uses control variables, macro-economic factors and profitability variable as independent variables and capital structure as dependent variables. Model 3 employs capital structure as independent variables and profitability ratios as dependent variables. Model 4 employs profitability ratios as dependent variables and all the proxies such as control variables, macro-economic factors and capital structure as independent variables.

In regression analysis, there are three major analyses which include model summary, ANOVA and coefficients. In model summary, R and R square (R^2) values are provided. R value represents correlation of the model and it signified the degree of the correlation. R^2 indicates that how much the dependent variables can be explained by the independent variable which means how well the regression model fits the observed data. ANOVA table illustrates the prediction of regression model about the dependent variable and it is defined by P-value which is 0.05. Thus, the value below P-value indicates that the model is statistically significant. ANOVA also helps to determine whether to accept or reject the hypotheses of the study. In relation to ANOVA, coefficients show the significance of each variable instead as a model. It also shows the beta value of each independent variable which explains the degree of influences of each independent on each dependent variable.

Model 1: Factors affecting Capital Structure without Control Variables

In this analysis, all the variables from macro environment and profitability are used as independent variables and all the variables from capital structure are used as dependent variables. Variables in macro environment are financial crisis, gross domestic product, inflation and interest rate. Variables in profitability are return on assets, return on equity, return on invested capital and return on capital employed. Variables in capital structure are short-term debt (STD), long-term debt (LTD), total debts (TD) and debt to equity (DE).

Hypothesis 1

H1: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (STDR).

Table 5.3.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.135 ^a	.018	.012	.064099
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				
b. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio				

Table 5.3.1 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis shows that the R value is 0.135. This indicates that effect from macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation and interest and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt is weak. Weak result also indicates that there are only few independent variables that affect or influence the short-term debt. Further, the result of regression analysis showed that the R² value is 0.018. This indicates that both the independent variables from macro environment and profitability can determine the model only by 1.8 percent which means short-term debt of capital structure can be affected by macro environment and profitability by 1.8 percent.

Table 5.3.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.095	8	.012	2.896	.003 ^b
	Residual	5.140	1251	.004		
	Total	5.235	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

Table 5.3.2 that shows the result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA). According to the result, significance level of F-Statistics is 0.003, which is less than 0.05 ($0.003 < 0.05$), which means the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is significant, the significant value illustrates that at least one independent variable of the macro environment and profitability affects the short-term debt of capital structure. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of the macro environment and profitability on capital structure which is a short-term debt. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.3.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of short-term debt.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.032	.006		5.087	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	.001	.006	.005	.135	.893
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.001	.002	-.019	-.439	.660
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.005	.002	.075	2.418	.016
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	-.001	.001	-.018	-.476	.634
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.080	.060	.251	1.346	.179
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.017	.031	.063	.533	.594
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-.136	.064	-.435	-2.129	.033
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.021	.018	.072	1.168	.243
a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio (STDR)						

As shown in Table 5.3.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that inflation of macro environment, return on invested capital of profitability and short-term debt of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.016 and 0.033 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.016 < 0.05$ and $0.033 < 0.05$). This denotes that inflation has statistically positive and significant effect on short-term debts. On the other hand, return on invested capital has statistically negative and significant effect on short-term debts. Other variables like financial crisis, GDP and interest of macro environment show a significant at the level of 0.893, 0.66 and 0.634 respectively with short-term debts, which is more than 0.05 ($0.893, 0.66$ and $0.634 > 0.05$). Similarly, ROA, ROE and ROCE of profitability exhibit significance at the level of 0.179, 0.594 and 0.243 respectively with short-term debts, which is more than 0.05 ($0.179, 0.594$ and $0.243 > 0.05$). Thus, it can be concluded that financial crisis, GDP, interest, ROA, ROE and ROCE have an effect on short-term debts of capital structure. However, these variables are not statistically significant.

In Table 5.3.3, beta exhibits a positive effect, which is 0.001 for financial crisis. This illustrates that when there is financial crisis, the short-term debt of financial service companies also increases by 0.1 percent. However, in the case of GDP, beta value shows negative effect, which is -0.001. This indicates that when there is an increase in GDP, there is a decrease in short-term debts in financial service companies by -0.1 percent. Beta value of inflation shows positive effect, which is 0.005. This demonstrates that increase of inflation triggers the short-term debt level to increase by 0.5 percent. In similar to GDP, beta value of interest shows negative of -0.001 effects. This indicates that when there is an increase in bank interest, there is a decrease in short-term debts by -0.1 percent. In regards to profitability variables, ROA, ROE and ROCE exhibit positive effect on short-term debts in which the beta values are 0.080, 0.017 and 0.021 respectively. These figures represent that when there is an increase in ROA, ROE and ROCE, there is an increase in short-term debts of capital structure by 8, 1.7 and 2.1 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC shows negative effect, which is -0.136. This depicts that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in short-term debts by -13.6 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$STDR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF_1 + \beta_2 ROIC_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$STDR = 0.032 + 0.005 * INF - 0.136 * ROIC$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 1:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 1 have been excluded and only the significant variables have been used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are inflation from macro environment and return on invested capital from profitability.

Table 5.3.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms of ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.112 ^a	.013	.011	.064127
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Invested Capital, Inflation Rate				

Table 5.3.4 provides R and R² values. Regression analysis shows that R value is 0.112. This indicates that the affect from macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.013 which is 1.3 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.3.1), this new analysis shows weaker result where R value is 0.112 instead of 0.135 and R² is 0.013 instead of 0.018. The new R² indicates that the significant independent variables such as inflation from macro environment and ROIC from profitability can affect the dependent variables which is short-term debts of capital structure by 1.3 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.3.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms of ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.066	2	.033	8.027	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.169	1257	.004		
	Total	5.235	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Invested Capital, Inflation Rate						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) as shown in Table 5.3.5 shows that the significance level of F-Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), signifying that the regression model is statistically significant. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.3.2), this new model produces more precise result which is 0.000 instead of 0.003. It can be concluded that this new model is a better predictor and an acceptable model for hypothesis one. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, macro environment and profitability is statistically have a significant effect on capital structure.

Table 5.3.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of inflation and profitability in terms of ROIC on capital structure in terms of short-term debt.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.031	.004		7.823	.000
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.006	.002	.090	3.197	.001
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-.022	.009	-.069	-2.469	.014
a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio						

As shown in Table 5.3.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that inflation of macro environment, return on invested capital of profitability and short-term debt of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.001 and 0.014 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$ and $0.014 < 0.05$). It can be explained that the inflation has statistically positive and significant effect on the short-term debts. Return on invested capital has statistically negative and significant effect on the short-term debts. As compared to the previous analysis

(see table 5.3.3), this new analysis shows stronger significant value which are 0.001 instead of 0.016 and 0.014 instead of 0.033 for inflation and ROIC respectively. Since the results are closer to 0.000, this new model of analysis validates as a better predictor for the hypothesis one.

In Table 5.3.6, beta value of inflation shows positive effect, which is 0.006. This shows that increase of inflation triggers the short-term debt level to increase by 0.6 percent. ROIC exhibits negative effect, which is -0.022. This illustrates that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in short-term debts by -2.2 percent. In regard to inflation, it shows stronger positive effect on short-term debts which is 0.6 percent instead of 0.5 percent which is from previous analysis (see table 5.3.3). In addition, ROIC shows weaker negative effect on short-term debts, which is -2.2 percent instead of -13.6 percent which is from the prior analysis (see table 5.3.3). From the comparison of this new analysis with the previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the analysis presented a stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be expressed that the inflation of macro environment and ROIC of profitability affects the short-term debts of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$STDR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF_1 + \beta_2 ROIC_2 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$STDR = 0.031 + 0.006 * INF - 0.022 * ROIC$$

Hypothesis 2

H2: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (LTDR).

Table 5.4.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.514 ^a	.265	.260	.102739
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				
b. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio				

Table 5.4.1 provides R and R² values. As per the regression analysis, R value is 0.514. This indicates that effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation and interest and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.265. This portrays that both the independent variables from macro environment and profitability determine the model significantly because the long-term debt of capital structure is affected by macro environment and profitability by 26.5 percent.

Table 5.4.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.751	8	.594	56.262	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.205	1251	.011		
	Total	17.956	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) is presented in Table 5.4.2. The analysis shows that F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is highly significant, it illustrates that the independent variable of the macro environment and profitability has an effect on the long-term debt of capital structure. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of the macro environment and profitability on the long-term debts of capital structure. Therefore, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.4.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.045	.010		4.405	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	.008	.010	.025	.755	.450
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.002	.003	-.033	-.875	.382
	Inflation Rate (INF)	-.002	.003	-.014	-.519	.604
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.005	.002	.098	3.039	.002
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.148	.095	.250	1.549	.122
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.646	.050	1.309	12.816	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.155	.102	-2.002	-11.319	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.260	.028	.494	9.194	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.4.3, the result of the T-Statistics reveals that interest rate of macro environment, return on equity, return on invested capital, return on capital employed of profitability and long-term debt of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.002, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.002 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$ and $0.000 < 0.05$). From these figures it can be said that interest rate, ROE and ROCE has statistically and positively significant affect on the long-term debts. On the other hand, ROIC has statistical negative and significant effect on the long-term debts. Other variables like financial crisis, GDP and inflation of macro environment show a significant at the level of 0.450, 0.382 and 0.604 respectively with long-term debts, which is more than 0.05 (0.450,

0.382 and 0.604 > 0.05). Similarly, ROA of profitability shows a significant at the level of 0.122 with long-term debts, which is more than 0.05 (0.122 > 0.05). Thus, the researcher concludes that financial crisis, GDP, inflation and ROA has an effect on long-term debts of capital structure. However, these variables are not statistically significant.

In Table 5.4.3, beta produces a positive effect, which is 0.008 for financial crisis. This illustrates that when there is financial crisis, the long-term debt of financial service companies also increases by 0.8 percent. However, in the case of GDP and inflation, beta value shows negative effect, which is -0.002 for both. This indicates that when there is an increase in both the GDP and inflation there is a decrease in long-term debts in financial service companies by -0.2 percent. Beta value of interest shows positive of 0.005 effect. This indicates that when there is an increase in bank interest, there is an increase in the long-term debts by 0.5 percent. In regards to profitability variables, ROA, ROE and ROCE showed positive effect on long-term debts in which the beta value showed 0.148, 0.646 and 0.260 respectively. These represents that when there is an increase in ROA, ROE and ROCE there is an increase in long-term debts of capital structure by 14.8, 64.6 and 26 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC produces negative effect, which is -1.155. This demonstrates that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in long-term debts by -115.5 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$LTDR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROE_2 + \beta_3 ROIC_3 + \beta_4 ROCE_4 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$LTDR = 0.045 + 0.005*IR + 0.646*ROE - 1.155*ROIC + 0.260*ROCE$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 2:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 2 have been excluded and only the significant variables are used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are interest rate from macro environment and ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability.

Table 5.4.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.511 ^a	.261	.259	.102819
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity				

The result from the regression analysis as given in Table 5.4.4 shows that the R value is 0.511. This indicates that effect of macro environment in terms of interest and profitability in terms ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.261 which is 26.1 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.4.1), this new analysis produces weaker result where R value is 0.511 instead of 0.514 and R² is 0.261 instead of 0.265. However, both the value of R and R² show close results from the previous analysis. The new R² indicates that the interest from macro environment and ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability can affect the dependent variable which is a long-term debts of capital structure by 26.1 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.4.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.688	4	1.172	110.859	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.268	1255	.011		
	Total	17.956	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity						

The results from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) given in Table 5.4.5, shows that the significance level of F-Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), denoting that regression model is statistically significant. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.4.2), this new model produces the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis. However, this new analysis is taken as an acceptable model because the insignificant variables are excluded in this model. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, macro environment and profitability is statistically has a significant effect on capital structure.

Table 5.4.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of long-term debt.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.043	.005		9.116	.000
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.004	.001	.084	3.453	.001
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.649	.050	1.316	12.895	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.030	.054	-1.785	-18.968	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.267	.027	.506	9.699	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.4.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that interest of macro environment, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability and long-term debt of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.001, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.001, 0.000, 0.000 \text{ and } 0.000 < 0.05$). This explains that the interest, ROE and ROCE has statistically positive and significant effect on the long-term debts. ROIC has a statistically negative and significant effect on the long-term debts. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.4.3), this new analysis shows stronger significant value which are 0.001 instead of 0.002 for interest and same result for ROE, ROIC and ROCE which is 0.000 significant level. Since it produces results closer to 0.000 significant in interest, this new model of analysis validates as a better predictor for the hypothesis two.

In Table 5.4.6, beta value of interest, ROE and ROCE shows positive effect, which are 0.004, 0.649 and 0.267 respectively. This in turn indicates that increase of interest, ROE and ROCE triggers the long-term debt level to increase by 0.4, 64.9 and 26.7 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC shows negative effect, which is -1.030. This demonstrates that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in long-term debts by -103 percent. In regard to the interest, it shows positively weaker effect on long-term debts which is 0.4 percent instead of 0.5 percent which is from previous analysis (see table 5.4.3). In addition, ROIC shows negatively weaker effect on long-term debts which is -103 percent instead of -115.5 percent which is from the prior analysis (see table 5.4.3). On the contrary, ROE and ROCE exhibits positively stronger effect on long-term debts which is 64.9 percent instead of 64.6 percent and 26.7 percent instead of 26 percent which is from previous analysis (see table 5.4.3). After comparing this analysis and previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the analysis produces a stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be said that the interest of macro environment and ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability affect the long-term debts of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$LTDR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROE_2 + \beta_3 ROIC_3 + \beta_4 ROCE_4 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$LTDR = 0.043 + 0.004*IR + 0.649*ROE - 1.030*ROIC + 0.267*ROCE$$

Hypothesis 3

H3: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (TDR).

Table 5.5.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.506 ^a	.256	.251	.111732
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				
b. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio				

Table 5.5.1 provides R and R² values. As per the table, regression analysis shows that the R value is 0.506. This indicates that the effect from macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation and interest and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis presented the R² value, which is 0.256. This indicates that both the independent variables from macro environment and profitability determine the model significantly because the total debt of capital structure is affected by macro environment and the profitability by 25.6 percent according to this study.

Table 5.5.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.362	8	.670	53.686	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.617	1251	.012		
	Total	20.979	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The results from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is presented in Table 5.5.2. As per the table, the significance level of F-Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) which means the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is highly significant, it can be illustrated that the independent variable of the macro environment and profitability has an effect on the total debt of capital structure. It can be concluded from the results that there is statistically significant effect of the macro environment and profitability on the total debts of capital structure. Therefore, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.5.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.078	.011		7.001	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	.008	.011	.024	.713	.476
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.003	.003	-.042	-1.102	.271
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.003	.003	.024	.907	.365
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.005	.002	.085	2.607	.009
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.225	.104	.350	2.162	.031
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.662	.055	1.240	12.072	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.285	.111	-2.061	-11.583	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.281	.031	.492	9.119	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.5.3, the result of T-Statistics reveals that interest rate of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability and total debt of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.009, 0.031, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.002 < 0.05$, $0.031 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$ and $0.000 < 0.05$). The figures suggest that the interest rate, ROA, ROE and ROCE have a statistically positive significant effect on total debts. On the other hand, ROIC has a statistically negative and significant effect on total debts. Other variables like financial crisis, GDP and inflation of macro environment show significance at the level of 0.476, 0.271 and 0.365 respectively with total debts, which is more than 0.05 ($0.476, 0.271$ and $0.365 > 0.05$). Thus, the researcher concludes that financial crisis, GDP and inflation have an effect on total debts of capital structure even if these variables are not statistically significant.

In Table 5.5.3, beta produces a positive effect, which is 0.008 for financial crisis. This illustrates that when there is financial crisis, the total debt of financial service companies also increases by 0.8 percent. However, in the case of GDP, beta value shows negative effect, which is -0.003. This indicates that when there is an increase in GDP, there is a decrease in total debts in financial service companies by -0.3 percent. Beta value of inflation shows positive effect, which is 0.003. This indicates that when there is an increase in inflation, there

is an increase in total debts in financial service companies by 0.3 percent. Beta value of interest exhibits positive effect of 0.005. This indicates that when there is an increase in bank interest, there is an increase in the total debts by 0.5 percent. In regards to the profitability variables, ROA, ROE and ROCE shows positive effect on total debts in which the beta value showed 0.225, 0.662 and 0.281 respectively. These represent that when there is an increase in ROA, ROE and ROCE, there is an increase in total debts of capital structure by 22.5, 66.2 and 28.1 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC shows negative effect, which is -1.285. This depicts that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in total debts by -128.5 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$TDR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$TDR = 0.078 + 0.005 * IR + 0.225 * ROA + 0.662 * ROE - 1.285 * ROIC + 0.281 * ROCE$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 3:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 3 have been excluded and only the significant variables are used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are interest rate from macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability.

Table 5.5.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.502 ^a	.252	.249	.111890
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				

Table 5.5.4 provides R and R² values. The regression analysis, as per the table reveals that the R value is 0.502. This indicates that the effect from macro environment in terms of interest and profitability in terms ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.252 which is 25.2 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.5.1), this new analysis exhibits weaker result where R value is 0.502 instead of 0.506 and R² is 0.252 instead of 0.256. However, both the values of R and R² produce closer values as compared to the previous analysis. The new R² indicates that interest from macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability can affect the dependent variable which is total debts of capital structure by 25.2 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.5.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.280	5	1.056	84.343	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.699	1254	.013		
	Total	20.979	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) as presented in Table 5.5.5 reveals that the significance level of F-Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), which means the regression model is statistically significant. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.5.2), this new model depicts the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis. However, this new analysis is taken as an acceptable model because the insignificant variables have been excluded in this model. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, macro environment and profitability have a statistically significant effect on capital structure.

Table 5.5.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of total debt.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.083	.006		14.769	.000
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.003	.001	.057	2.318	.021
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.225	.104	.352	2.170	.030
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.665	.055	1.246	12.131	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.294	.111	-2.075	-11.683	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.277	.031	.486	9.008	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.5.6, the results of the T-Statistics reveals that interest of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability and total debt of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.021, 0.030, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.021, 0.030, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 < 0.05). This explains that interest, ROA, ROE and ROCE have a statistically and positively significant effect on the total debts. However, ROIC has a statistically and negative and significant effect on total debts. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.5.3), this new analysis shows weaker significant value which are 0.021 instead of 0.009 for interest and slightly stronger significant value in ROA which is 0.030 instead of 0.031. In regard to the other variables like ROE, ROIC and ROCE, the significant level shows same result which is 0.000 significant level.

In Table 5.5.6, beta value of interest, ROA, ROE and ROCE reveals a positive effect, which is 0.003, 0.225, 0.665 and 0.277 respectively. This depicts that increase of interest, ROA, ROE and ROCE triggers the total debt level to increase by 0.3, 22.5, 66.5 and 27.7 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC exhibits negative effect, which is -1.294. This signifies that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in total debts by -129.4 percent. In regard to the interest and ROCE, both the variables exhibit positively weaker effect on total debts which is 0.3 percent instead of 0.5 percent and 27.7 percent instead of 28.1 percent which is from previous analysis (see table 5.5.3). In addition, ROIC shows negatively stronger effect on total debts which is -129.4 percent instead of -128.5 percent which is from

the prior analysis (see table 5.5.3). On the contrary, ROE exhibits positively stronger effect on total debts which is 66.5 percent instead of 66.2 percent and ROA produced the same result of 22.5 percent which is from previous analysis (see table 5.5.3). Comparing this new analysis to previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the analysis produces stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be said that the interest of macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability affect the total debts of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$TDR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$TDR = 0.083 + 0.003*IR + 0.225*ROA + 0.665*ROE - 1.294*ROIC + 0.277*ROCE$$

Hypothesis 4

H4: Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (DER).

Table 5.6.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.534 ^a	.285	.280	.919366
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				
b. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio				

The result of the regression analysis given in Table 5.6.1 reveals that the R value is 0.534. This indicates that the effect from macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation and interest and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis reveals that the R² value is 0.285. This indicates that both the independent variables from macro environment and profitability determine the model significantly because the debt to equity of capital structure can be affected by the macro environment and the profitability by 28.5 percent according to this study.

Table 5.6.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	421.560	8	52.695	62.344	.000 ^b
	Residual	1057.387	1251	.845		
	Total	1478.947	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Financial Crisis, Inflation Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The outcome of analysis of variance (ANOVA) is given in Table 5.6.2, which reveals that the significance level of F-Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This indicates the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is highly significant, it illustrates that the independent variable of the macro environment and profitability has an effect on the debt to equity of capital structure. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of the macro environment and profitability on the debts to equity of capital structure. Therefore, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.6.3 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of financial crisis, GDP, inflation, interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.391	.091		4.288	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	-.035	.090	-.013	-.392	.695
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.030	.025	-.045	-1.221	.222
	Inflation Rate (INF)	-.012	.027	-.012	-.439	.660
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.032	.015	.067	2.101	.036
	Return on Asset (ROA)	-12.654	.855	-2.352	-14.807	.000
	Return on Equity (ROE)	4.048	.451	.904	8.975	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	4.802	.913	.917	5.258	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	3.038	.253	.635	11.996	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio						

As shown in Table 5.6.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that interest rate of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability and debt to equity of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.036, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.036 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$ and $0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, this can be explained that the interest rate, ROE, ROIC and ROCE have a statistically positive and significant effect on the debts to equity. On the other hand, ROA has a statistically negative and significant effect on the debts to equity. Other variables like financial crisis, GDP and inflation of macro environment show significance at the level of 0.695, 0.222 and 0.660 respectively with debts to equity, which is more than 0.05 ($0.695 > 0.05$, $0.222 > 0.05$ and $0.660 > 0.05$). Thus, the researcher concludes that financial crisis, GDP and inflation have an effect on debt to equity of capital structure despite these variables being statistically insignificant.

In Table 5.6.3, beta exhibits a negative effect, which is -0.035, -0.030 and -0.012 for financial crisis, GDP and inflation. This illustrates that when there is financial crisis the debt to equity of financial service companies also decrease by -3.5 percent. In addition, when there is an increase in GDP and inflation, there is a decrease in debt to equity in financial service companies by -3 percent and 1.2 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta value of interest shows positive effect of 0.032. This indicates that when there is an increase in bank interest, there is an increase in the debt to equity by 3.2 percent. In regards to the profitability variables, ROE, ROIC and ROCE show positive effect on debt to equity in which the beta value is recorded as 4.048, 4.802 and 3.038 respectively. These represent that when there is an increase in ROE, ROIC and ROCE, there is an increase in debt to equity of capital structure by 404.8, 480.2 and 303.8 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROA shows negative effect, which is -12.654. This signifies that when there is an increase in ROA, there is a decrease in debt to equity by -1265.4 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$DE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$DE = 0.391 + 0.032 * IR - 12.654 * ROA + 4.048 * ROE + 4.802 * ROIC + 3.038 * ROCE$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 4:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 4 have been excluded and only the significant variables have been used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are interest rate from macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability.

Table 5.6.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.533 ^a	.284	.281	.918902
a. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				

Table 5.6.4 provides R and R² values. As per the table, R value is 0.533. This indicates that the effect of macro environment such as interest and profitability in terms ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure, which is debt to equity is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.284 which is 28.4 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.6.1), this new analysis showed weaker result where R value is 0.533 instead of 0.534 and R² is 0.284 instead of 0.285. However, both the values of R and R² exhibits closer results as compared to the previous analysis. The new R² indicates that the interest from macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability can affect the dependent variable which is debt to equity of capital structure by 28.4 percent.

Table 5.6.5 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	420.094	5	84.019	99.503	.000 ^b
	Residual	1058.853	1254	.844		
	Total	1478.947	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Return on Capital Employed, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is given in Table 5.6.5. As per the table, F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). The result indicates that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.6.2), this new model depicts the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis. However, this new analysis is taken as an acceptable model because the insignificant variables are excluded in this model. Therefore, macro environment and profitability have a statistically significant effect on capital structure.

Table 5.6.6 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of interest rate and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE on capital structure in terms of debt to equity.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
		1	(Constant)	.326		
Bank Interest rate (IR)	.023		.012	.047	1.966	.049
Return on Asset (ROA)	-12.609		.853	-2.344	-14.780	.000
Return on Equity (ROE)	4.079		.450	.911	9.063	.000
Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	4.710		.910	.899	5.176	.000
Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	3.026		.252	.632	11.990	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio						

As shown in Table 5.6.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that interest of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability and debt to equity of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.049, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.049, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 < 0.05). This illustrates that the interest, ROE, ROIC and ROCE have statistically positive and significant effect on debt to equity. However, ROA has a statistically negative and significant effect on debt to equity. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.6.3), this new analysis produces weaker significant value which are 0.049 instead of 0.036 for interest. In regard to other variables such as ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE, the significant level exhibits same result which is at 0.000 significant levels.

In Table 5.6.6, beta value of interest, ROE, ROIC and ROCE showed positive effect, the values being 0.023, 4.079, 4.710 and 3.026 respectively. This shows that increase of interest, ROE, ROIC and ROCE trigger the debt to equity level to increase by 2.3, 407.9, 471 and 302.6 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROA exhibits negative effect, which is -12.609, signifying that when there is an increase in ROA, there is a decrease in debt to equity by -1260.9 percent. In regard to the interest, ROA, ROIC and ROCE, these variables show weaker effect on the debt to equity which is 2.3 percent instead of 3.2 percent, -1260.9 percent instead -1265.4, 471 percent instead 480.2 percent and 302.6 percent instead of 303.8 percent respectively (see table 5.6.3). In addition, ROE exhibits stronger effect on debt to equity which is 407.9 percent instead of 404.8 percent (see table 5.6.3). After comparing this new analysis with previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is acceptable in this study because the analysis presents a stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be written that the interests of macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability affect the debt to equity of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$DE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$DE = 0.326 + 0.023 * IR - 12.609 * ROA + 4.079 * ROE + 4.710 * ROIC + 3.026 * ROCE$$

Model 2: Factors affecting Capital Structure with Control Variables

In this analysis, all variables from control variables, macro environment and profitability have been used as independent variables and all the variables from capital structure have been used as dependent variables. Control variables are total assets, assets growth, firm age, earning per share, liquidity, interest coverage and effective tax. Variables in macro environment are financial crisis, gross domestic product, inflation and interest rate. Variables in profitability are return on assets, return on equity, return on invested capital and return on capital employed. Variables in capital structure are short-term debt (STD), long-term debt (LTD), total debts (TD) and debt to equity (DE).

Hypothesis 5

H5: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (STDR).

Table 5.7.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of STD.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.245 ^a	.060	.049	.062892
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital				
b. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio				

Table 5.7.1 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis shows that the R value is 0.245. This indicates that the effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of STD is low. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.060. This indicates that STD of capital structure can be affected by the macro environment and profitability along with control variables by 6 percent according to this study.

Table 5.7.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of STD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.315	15	.021	5.303	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.921	1244	.004		
	Total	5.235	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital						

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is presented in Table 5.7.2. The result exhibits that significance level of F-Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), signifying that the regression model is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Since this regression model is highly significant, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of the macro environment and profitability along with control variables on the STD of capital structure.

Table 5.7.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of STD.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.145	.028		5.241	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	.002	.006	.012	.327	.744
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.001	.002	-.013	-.299	.765
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.005	.002	.077	2.541	.011
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	-.002	.001	-.054	-1.441	.150
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.081	.059	.252	1.359	.175
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.026	.032	.096	.813	.416
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-.152	.064	-.488	-2.378	.018
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.025	.018	.086	1.336	.182
	Total Assets (TA)	-.012	.003	-.113	-3.889	.000
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.000	.000	.047	1.185	.236
	Firm Age (FA)	-7.408E-005	.000	-.050	-1.769	.077
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	-7.099E-006	.000	-.011	-.321	.748
	Liquidity Ratio (LR)	.000	.000	-.156	-5.630	.000
	Interest Coverage (IC)	-6.832E-007	.000	-.044	-1.583	.114
Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.000	.008	-.002	-.057	.955	

a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.7.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that inflation of macro environment, ROIC of profitability, total assets and liquidity of control variables and STD of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.011, 0.018, 0.000, and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.011 < 0.05$, $0.018 < 0.05$, $0.000 < 0.05$, and $0.000 < 0.05$). This can be understood that inflation has statistically and positively significant effect on STD. On the other hand, ROIC and total asset have statistically and negatively significant effect on STD. In regard to liquidity, it shows statistically significant value but has no effect on STD. Other variables like financial crisis, GDP, interest, ROA, ROE, ROCE, AG, FA, EPS, IC and ET show statistically insignificant values.

In Table 5.7.3, beta represents a negative effect, which is -0.001, and -0.002 for GDP and interest. It is understood that when there is an increase in GDP and interest, there is a decrease in STD in financial service companies by -0.1 percent and -0.2 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta value of FC and INF shows positive effect, which is 0.002 and 0.005 respectively. This illustrates that when there is financial crisis and increase in inflation, the STD of financial service companies also increase by 0.2 percent and 0.5 percent respectively. In regards to the profitability variables, ROA, ROE and ROCE exhibits positive effect on STD in which the beta values are 0.081, 0.026 and 0.025 respectively. These figures represent that when there is an increase in ROA, ROE and ROCE, there is an increase in STD of capital structure by 8.1, 2.6 and 2.5 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC shows negative effect, which is -0.152. The depiction in this case is that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in STD by -15.2 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model. In regard to control variables, only total assets exhibits negative effect on STD in which the beta value is -0.012, depicting that when there is an increase in total assets, there is decrease in STD by -1.2 percent. On the contrary, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET show no or less effect on STD where the beta value of these variables is 0.000 which is 0 percent effects.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$STD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF_1 + \beta_2 ROIC_2 + \beta_3 TA_3 + \beta_4 LR_4 \dots \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$STD = 0.145 + 0.005 * INF - 0.152 * ROIC - 0.012 * TA + 0.000 * LR$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 5:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 5 have been excluded and only the significant variables have been used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are INF from macro environment, ROIC from profitability, TA and LR from control variables.

Table 5.7.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of INF and profitability in terms of ROIC with control variables such as TA and LR on capital structure in terms of STD.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.217 ^a	.047	.044	.063054
a. Predictors: (Constant), Liquidity Ratio, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Return on Invested Capital				

Table 5.7.4 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis shows that R value is 0.217, indicating that effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of STD is low. Further, the analysis shows that R² value is 0.047 which is 4.7 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.7.1), this new analysis shows weaker result where R value is 0.217 instead of 0.245 and R² is 0.047 instead of 0.060. The new R² value indicates that INF from macro environment and ROIC from profitability along with TA and LR from control variables can affect STD of capital structure by 4.7 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.7.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of INF and profitability in terms of ROIC with control variables such as TA and LR on capital structure in terms of STD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.245	4	.061	15.436	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.990	1255	.004		
	Total	5.235	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Liquidity Ratio, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Return on Invested Capital						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is provided in Table 5.7.5. It reveals that F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.7.2), this new model produces the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis.

Table 5.7.6 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of INF and profitability in terms of ROIC with control variables such as TA and LR on capital structure in terms of STD.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.125	.026		4.883	.000
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.006	.002	.100	3.612	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-.017	.009	-.055	-1.999	.046
	Total Assets (TA)	-.011	.003	-.101	-3.655	.000
	Liquidity Ratio (LR)	.000	.000	-.157	-5.694	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Short-term debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.7.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that INF of macro environment, ROIC of profitability and STD of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.046, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.000, 0.046, 0.000 and 0.000 < 0.05). This demonstrates that INF has a statistically positive and significant effect on the STD. ROIC and TA have statistically negative and significant effect on STD. However, LR is showed to be statistically significant yet has no effect on STD. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.7.3), this new analysis exhibits stronger significant value which are 0.000 instead of 0.011 for INF. It also shows weaker significant value for ROIC which is 0.046 instead of 0.018. In regard to the other variables like TA and LR, the significant level shows the same result which is 0.000 significant levels.

In Table 5.7.6, beta value of INF exhibits positive effect, which is 0.006. This shows that increase of INF triggers STD level to increase by 0.6 percent. On the other hand, ROIC and TA exhibits negative effect, which is -0.017 and -0.011 respectively. It can be understood that when there is an increase in ROIC and TA there is a decrease in STD by -1.7 and -1.1 percent respectively. However, LR produces no effect on STD because beta value is 0.000. When compared to previous analysis (see table 5.7.3) INF produces slightly stronger effect on STD which is 0.6 percent instead of 0.5 percent. ROIC and TA shows a weaker effect on STD which is -1.7 percent instead of -15.2 percent and -1.1 percent instead of -1.2 percent respectively. The beta value of LR remains the same in both the analyses, which is 0.000 percent. It can be concluded from the comparison of the new analysis to the previous analysis that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the analysis presents a stronger f-

statistics. Therefore, it can be said that INF of macro environment and ROIC of profitability along with control variable affect the STD of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$STD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF_1 + \beta_2 ROIC_2 + \beta_3 TA_3 + \beta_4 LR_4 \dots \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$STD = 0.125 + 0.006 * INF - 0.017 * ROIC - 0.011 * TA + 0.000 * LR$$

Hypothesis 6

H6: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (LTDR).

Table 5.8.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.579 ^a	.336	.328	.097931
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital				
b. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio				

Table 5.8.1 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis shows that R value is 0.579, indicating that the effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of LTD is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis displays that R² value is 0.336, indicating that LTD of capital structure can be affected by the macro environment and the profitability along with control variables by 33.6 percent according to this study.

Table 5.8.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.025	15	.402	41.881	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.931	1244	.010		
	Total	17.956	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Investment						

The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.8.2. As per the table, F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), denoting that the regression model is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Since this regression model is highly significant, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on the LTD of capital structure.

Table 5.8.3 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.334	.043		-7.785	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	.004	.010	.013	.420	.675
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.004	.003	-.050	-1.397	.163
	Inflation Rate (INF)	-.002	.003	-.018	-.704	.482
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.008	.002	.151	4.772	.000
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.214	.092	.361	2.312	.021
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.587	.049	1.190	11.958	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.117	.100	-1.935	-11.207	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.235	.029	.445	8.187	.000
	Total Assets (TA)	.043	.005	.213	8.676	.000
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.000	.000	.023	.696	.487
	Firm Age (FA)	.000	.000	.113	4.765	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.000	.000	-.100	-3.420	.001
	Liquidity Ratio (LR)	2.820E-005	.000	.006	.241	.810
	Interest Coverage (IC)	-8.005E-007	.000	-.028	-1.191	.234
	Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.047	.013	.086	3.639	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.8.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that IR of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability, TA, FA, EPS and ET of control variables and LTD of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.021, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.001 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.000, 0.021, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.001 and 0.000 < 0.05). The figures explain that IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA, and ET have statistically positive and significant effect on LTD. On the other hand, ROIC has statistically negative and significant effect on LTD. In regard to FA and EPS, these exhibit to have statistically significant value but has no effect on LTD. Other variables like FC, GDP, INF, AG, LR and IC show that these are statistically insignificant.

In Table 5.8.3, beta produces negative effect, which is -0.004, and -0.002 for GDP and INF. This illustrates that when there is an increase in GDP and INF, there is a decrease in LTD in financial service companies by -0.4 percent and -0.2 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta value of FC and IR shows positive effect which is 0.004 and 0.008 respectively. From this, it can be understood that when there is financial crisis and increase in IR, the LTD of financial service companies also increase by 0.4 percent and 0.8 percent respectively. In regards to the profitability variables, ROA, ROE and ROCE exhibit positive effect on LTD in which the beta values are 0.214, 0.587 and 0.235 respectively. These represent that when there is an increase in ROA, ROE and ROCE, there is an increase in LTD of capital structure by 21.4, 58.7 and 23.5 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC produces negative effect, which is -1.117. This denotes that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in LTD by -111.7 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model. In regard to control variables, TA and ET exhibit positive effect on LTD in which the beta value are 0.043 and 0.047 respectively. This depicts that when there is an increase in TA and ET, there is increase in LTD by 4.3 percent and 4.7 percent respectively. On the contrary, AG, FA, EPS, LR and IC produce no or less effect on LTD where the beta value of these variables is 0.000 which is 0 percent effects.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 LTD &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \beta_6 TA_6 + \beta_7 FA_7 + \\
 &\quad \beta_8 EPS_8 + \beta_9 ET_9 + \dots + \beta_n X_n \\
 LTD &= -0.334 + 0.008*IR + 0.214*ROA + 0.587*ROE - 1.117*ROIC + \\
 &\quad 0.235*ROCE + 0.043*TA + 0.00*FA + 0.000*EPS + 0.047*ET.
 \end{aligned}$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 6:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 6 have been excluded and only the significant variables have been used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are IR from macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability, TA, FA, EPS and ET from control variables.

Table 5.8.4 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.576 ^a	.332	.327	.097942
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Firm Age, Total Assets, Earning Per Share, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				

In Table 5.8.4 R and R² values are presented. As per the regression analysis, it shows that the R value is 0.576, indicating that the effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of LTD is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis reveals that R² value is 0.332 which is 33.2 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.8.1), this new analysis shows slightly weaker result where R value is 0.576 instead of 0.579 and R² is 0.332 instead of 0.336. The new R² indicates that IR from macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability along with TA, FA, EPS and ET from control variables can affect LTD of capital structure by 33.2 percent.

Table 5.8.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.965	9	.663	69.091	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.991	1250	.010		
	Total	17.956	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Firm Age, Total Assets, Earning Per Share, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.8.5. The analysis shows F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05), denoting that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.8.2), this new model produces the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis.

Table 5.8.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of LTD.

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.343	.042		-8.153	.000
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.007	.001	.134	5.645	.000
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.207	.092	.349	2.250	.025
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.591	.049	1.198	12.188	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.114	.098	-1.931	-11.384	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.236	.028	.447	8.481	.000
	Total Assets (TA)	.043	.005	.214	8.752	.000
	Firm Age (FA)	.000	.000	.110	4.634	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.000	.000	-.102	-3.530	.000
	Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.046	.013	.084	3.551	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Long-term debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.8.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that IR of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability, TA, FA, EPS and ET of control variables and LTD of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.025, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.000, 0.021, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 < 0.05). The figures explain that IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA and ET have statistically positive and significant effect on LTD. ROIC has statistically negative and significant effect on the LTD. However, FA and EPS are shown to be statistically significant but have no effect on LTD. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.8.3), this new analysis produces slightly stronger significant value which are 0.000 instead of 0.001 for EPS. It also shows weaker significant value for ROA which is 0.025 instead of 0.021. In regard to other variables like IR, ROE, ROIC, ROCE, TA, FA and ET the significant level produced same result which is 0.000 significant levels.

In Table 5.8.6, beta values of IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA, and ET shows positive effect, which is 0.007, 0.207, 0.591, 0.236, 0.043 and 0.046 respectively. The figures illustrate that increase of IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA, and ET triggers the LTD level to increase by 0.7, 20.7, 59.1, 23.6, 4.3 and 4.6 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC exhibits negative

effect, which is -1.114. This leads to the understanding that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in LTD by -111.4 percent. However, FA and EPS produces no effect on LTD because beta value is 0.000. As compared to previous analysis (see table 5.8.3) ROE and ROCE exhibits slightly stronger effect on the LTD which is 59.1 and 23.6 percent instead of 58.7 and 23.5 percent respectively. IR, ROA, ROIC and ET exhibit weaker effect on LTD which is 0.7, 20.7, -111.4 and 4.6 percent instead of 0.8, 21.4, -111.7 and 4.7 percent respectively. The beta values of TA, FA and EPS remain the same in both the analyses, which is 4.3 and 0.000 percent. From the comparison of new analysis to the previous analysis, the researcher finds that the new analysis is acceptable because the analysis produces a stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be said that the IR of macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability along with TA and ET of control variable affect the LTD of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 LTD &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \beta_6 TA_6 + \beta_7 FA_7 + \\
 &\quad \beta_8 EPS_8 + \beta_9 ET_9 + \dots + \beta_n X_n \\
 LTD &= -0.343 + 0.007*IR + 0.207*ROA + 0.591*ROE - 1.114*ROIC + \\
 &\quad 0.236*ROCE + 0.043*TA + 0.00*FA + 0.000*EPS + 0.046*ET.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hypothesis 7

H7: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (TDR).

Table 5.9.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of TD.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.550 ^a	.302	.294	.108487
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital				
b. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio				

Table 5.9.1 provides R and R² values. As per the regression analysis, R value is 0.550. This indicates that the effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of TD is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.302, indicating that TD of capital structure can be affected by the macro environment and the profitability along with control variables by 30.2 percent according to this study.

Table 5.9.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of TD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.338	15	.423	35.900	.000 ^b
	Residual	14.641	1244	.012		
	Total	20.979	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital						

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.9.2. The analysis shows that F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that regression model is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Since this regression model is highly significant, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on the TD of capital structure.

Table 5.9.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of TD.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.188	.048		-3.958	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	.005	.011	.016	.507	.612
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.004	.003	-.055	-1.478	.140
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.003	.003	.022	.834	.405
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.007	.002	.115	3.551	.000
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.291	.102	.454	2.841	.005
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.613	.054	1.148	11.257	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.264	.110	-2.027	-11.455	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.259	.032	.455	8.171	.000
	Total Assets (TA)	.031	.006	.140	5.557	.000
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.000	.000	.045	1.312	.190
	Firm Age (FA)	.000	.000	.079	3.231	.001
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.000	.000	-.099	-3.303	.001
	Liquidity Ratio (LR)	.000	.000	-.072	-3.012	.003
	Interest Coverage (IC)	-1.488E-006	.000	-.048	-1.998	.046
Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.047	.014	.079	3.242	.001	

a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio

As shown in Table 5.9.3, the results of the T-Statistics showed IR of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability, TA, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET of control variables and TD of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.005, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.001, 0.001, 0.003, 0.046 and 0.001 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000, 0.005, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.001, 0.001, 0.003, 0.046$ and $0.001 < 0.05$).

Therefore, this explains that IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA, and ET have statistically positive and significant effect on TD. On the other hand, ROIC has statistically negative and significant effect on TD. FA, EPS, LR and IC are shown to be statistically significant but has no or less effect on TD. Other variables like FC, GDP, INF and AG reveal that these are statistically insignificant.

In Table 5.9.3, beta produces negative effect, which is -0.004 for GDP, which is illustrative of the fact that when there is an increase in GDP, there is a decrease in TD in financial service companies by -0.4 percent. On the other hand, beta values of FC, INF and IR exhibit positive effect which is 0.005, 0.003 and 0.007 respectively. This illustrates that when there is financial crisis and increase in INF and IR, the TD of financial service companies also increases by 0.5, 0.3 and 0.7 percent respectively. In regards to the profitability variables, ROA, ROE and ROCE produces positive effect on TD in which the beta values are shown as 0.291, 0.613 and 0.259 respectively. These represent that when there is an increase in ROA, ROE and ROCE, there is an increase in TD of capital structure by 29.1, 61.3 and 25.9 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC exhibits negative effect, which is -1.264, from which it can be understood that an increase in ROIC produces a decrease in TD by -126.4 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model. In regard to control variables, TA and ET show positive effect on TD in which beta values are 0.031 and 0.047 respectively. These figures depict that when there is an increase in TA and ET, there is increase in TD by 3.1 percent and 4.7 percent respectively. On the contrary, AG, FA, EPS, LR and IC exhibit no or less effect on TD where the beta value of these variables is 0.000 which is 0 percent effects.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 TD &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \beta_6 TA_6 + \beta_7 FA_7 + \\
 &\quad \beta_8 EPS_8 + \beta_9 LR_9 + \beta_{10} IC_{10} + \beta_{11} ET_{11} \dots \dots \dots + \beta_n X_n \\
 TD &= -0.188 + 0.007*IR + 0.291*ROA + 0.613*ROE - 1.264*ROIC + 0.259*ROCE \\
 &\quad + 0.031*TA + 0.00*FA + 0.000*EPS + 0.000*LR + 0.000*IC + 0.047*ET.
 \end{aligned}$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 7:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 7 have been excluded and only the significant variables have been used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are IR from macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability, TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET from control variables. Despite IC being statistically significant, it has been omitted from this new analysis because it is shown to be insignificant in the new analysis.

Table 5.9.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET on capital structure in terms of TD.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.543 ^a	.295	.289	.108810
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Liquidity Ratio, Firm Age, Total Assets, Earning Per Share, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Equity, Return on Asset				

Table 5.9.4 provides R and R² values. The regression analysis shows that the R value is 0.543, indicating that the effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of TD is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.295 which is 29.5 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.9.1), this new analysis shows slightly weaker result where R value is 0.543 instead of 0.550 and R² is 0.295 instead of 0.302. The new R² indicates that IR from macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability along with TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET from control variables can affect TD of capital structure by 29.5 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.9.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET on capital structure in terms of TD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.191	10	.619	52.293	.000 ^b
	Residual	14.788	1249	.012		
	Total	20.979	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Bank Interest rate, Return on Invested Capital, Liquidity Ratio, Firm Age, Total Assets, Earning Per Share, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Equity, Return on Asset						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.9.5. As per the analysis, F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), denoting that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.9.2), this new model depicts the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis.

Table 5.9.6 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR, and ET on capital structure in terms of TD.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.186	.047		-3.975	.000
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.005	.001	.084	3.456	.001
	Return on Asset (ROA)	.272	.102	.425	2.666	.008
	Return on Equity (ROE)	.613	.054	1.149	11.365	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	-1.244	.109	-1.994	-11.435	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.265	.031	.465	8.586	.000
	Total Assets (TA)	.031	.005	.141	5.612	.000
	Firm Age (FA)	.000	.000	.074	3.027	.003
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.000	.000	-.101	-3.403	.001
	Liquidity Ratio (LR)	.000	.000	-.071	-2.971	.003
	Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.046	.014	.078	3.208	.001
a. Dependent Variable: Total debt ratio						

As shown in Table 5.9.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that IR of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability, TA, FA, EPS, LR and ET of control variables and TD of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.001, 0.008, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.003, 0.001, 0.003 and 0.001 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.001, 0.008, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.003, 0.001, 0.003 and 0.001 < 0.05). From these figures, it can be understood that IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA and ET have statistically positive and significant effect on TD. ROIC has statistically negative and significant effect on the TD. However, FA, EPS and LR are shown to be statistically significant yet have no effect on TD. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.9.3), this new analysis shows slightly weaker significant value for IR and ROA which are 0.001 instead of 0.000 and 0.008 instead of 0.005. In regard to the other variables like ROE, ROIC, ROCE and TA, the significant level shows the same result at 0.000 significant levels. Further, FA, EPS, LR and ET produces the same results at 0.003, 0.001, 0.003 and 0.001 significant levels.

In Table 5.9.6, beta values of IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA, and ET exhibit positive effect, which are 0.005, 0.272, 0.613, 0.265, 0.031 and 0.046 respectively. These figures suggest that increase of IR, ROA, ROE, ROCE, TA, and ET triggers the TD level to increase by 0.5, 27.2, 61.3, 26.5, 3.1 and 4.6 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROIC produces negative effect, which is -1.244, suggesting that when there is an increase in ROIC, there is a decrease in TD by -124.4 percent. However, FA, EPS and LR shows no effect on LTD because beta value is 0.000. When compared with previous analysis (see Table 5.9.3), ROCE shows slightly stronger effect on the TD which is 26.5 percent instead of 25.9 percent. IR, ROA, ROIC and ET displays a weaker effect on TD which is 0.5, 27.2, -124.4 and 4.6 percent instead of 0.7, 29.1, -126.4 and 4.7 percent respectively. The beta value of ROE, TA, FA, EPS and LR remained same in both the analyses, which is 61.3 percent for ROE and 3.1 percent for TA and 0.000 percent for FA, EPS and LR. When the new analysis is compared to previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the analysis presented a stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be expressed that IR of macro environment and ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability along with TA and ET of control variable affect the TD of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$TD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \beta_6 TA_6 + \beta_7 FA_7 + \beta_8 EPS_8 + \beta_9 LR_9 + \beta_{10} ET_{10} + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$TD = -0.186 + 0.005*IR + 0.272*ROA + 0.613*ROE - 1.244*ROIC + 0.265*ROCE + 0.031*TA + 0.00*FA + 0.000*EPS + 0.000*LR + 0.046*ET.$$

Hypothesis 8

H8: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies affect the capital structure (DER).

Table 5.10.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of DE.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.588 ^a	.345	.337	.882197
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital				
b. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio				

Table 5.10.1 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis, as shown in the table shows that R value is 0.588. This indicates that the effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of DE is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis reveals that R² value is 0.345, indicating that DE of capital structure can be affected by macro environment and the profitability along with control variables by 34.5 percent according to this study.

Table 5.10.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of DE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	510.777	15	34.052	43.753	.000 ^b
	Residual	968.170	1244	.778		
	Total	1478.947	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Interest Coverage, Bank Interest rate, Liquidity Ratio, Earning Per Share, Firm Age, Financial Crisis, Total Assets, Inflation Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Return on Equity, Gross Domestic Product, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital						

The results from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.10.2. According to the analysis, F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), signifying that the regression model is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Since this regression model is highly significant, it can be concluded that there is statistically significant effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on the DE of capital structure.

Table 5.10.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP, INF and IR and profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET on capital structure in terms of DE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.428	.387		-1.105	.269
	Financial Crisis (FC)	-.013	.086	-.005	-.151	.880
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-.031	.024	-.046	-1.291	.197
	Inflation Rate (INF)	-.024	.026	-.023	-.907	.365
	Bank Interest rate (IR)	.031	.015	.065	2.069	.039
	Return on Asset (ROA)	-12.546	.833	-2.332	-15.058	.000
	Return on Equity (ROE)	3.978	.443	.888	8.988	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	4.833	.898	.923	5.385	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	2.753	.258	.575	10.670	.000
	Total Assets (TA)	.082	.045	.045	1.832	.067
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.007	.001	.173	5.195	.000
	Firm Age (FA)	.003	.001	.120	5.075	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	-.002	.000	-.144	-4.934	.000
	Liquidity Ratio (LR)	.000	.001	-.009	-.396	.692
	Interest Coverage (IC)	4.161E-007	.000	.002	.069	.945
	Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.677	.117	.136	5.774	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio

As shown in Table 5.10.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that IR of macro environment, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability, AG, FA, EPS and ET of control variables and DE of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.039, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.039, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, and 0.000 < 0.05). It can be explained from the figures that IR, ROE, ROIC, ROCE, AG, FA and ET have statistically positive and significant effect on DE. On the other hand, ROA and EPS have statistically negative and significant effect on DE. Other variables like FC, GDP, INF, TA, LR and IC are shown to be statistically insignificant.

In Table 5.10.3, beta is shown to have negative effect on FC, GDP and INF, which is -0.013, -0.031 and -0.024 respectively. This illustrates that when there is FC and an increase in GDP and INF, there is a decrease in DE in financial service companies by -1.3, -3.1 and -2.4 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta value of IR shows positive effect which is 0.031. This illustrates that when there is an increase in IR, DE of financial service companies also increases by 3.1 percent. In regards to the profitability variables, ROE, ROIC and ROCE shows positive effect on DE in which beta values are 3.978, 4.833 and 2.753 respectively. This implies that when there is an increase in ROE, ROIC and ROCE, there is an increase in DE of capital structure by 397.8, 483.3 and 275.3 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROA exhibits negative effect, which is -12.546, signifying that when there is an increase in ROA, there is a decrease in ED by -1254.6 percent, which is also the highest effect amongst all the other variables in this model. In regard to control variables, TA, AG, FA and ET exhibit positive effect on DE in which the beta value is 0.082, 0.007, 0.003 and 0.677 respectively. This depicts that when there is an increase in TA, AG, FA and ET, there is an increase in DE by 8.2, 0.7, 0.3 and 67.7 percent respectively. Beta value of EPS shows negative effect on DE, which is -0.002, depicting that when there is an increase in EPS, there is a decrease in DE by -0.2 percent. On the contrary, EPS and IC exhibit no or less effect on DE where the beta value of these variables is 0.000 which is 0 percent effects.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$DE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_1 + \beta_2 ROA_2 + \beta_3 ROE_3 + \beta_4 ROIC_4 + \beta_5 ROCE_5 + \beta_6 AG_6 + \beta_7 FA_7 + \beta_8 EPS_8 + \beta_9 ET_9 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$DE = -0.428 + 0.031*IR - 12.546*ROA + 3.978*ROE + 4.833*ROIC + 2.753*ROCE + 0.007*AG + 0.003*FA - 0.002*EPS + 0.677*ET.$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 8:

In this analysis, all the insignificant variables in the first analysis of hypothesis 8 have been excluded and only the significant variables have been used in the analysis. The variables taken in this analysis are ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability, AG, FA, EPS and ET from control variables. Despite IR being statistically significant, it has been omitted in this new analysis because it exhibits insignificance in this new analysis.

Table 5.10.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as AG, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of DE.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.583 ^a	.340	.336	.883071
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Firm Age, Earning Per Share, Return on Equity, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital				

Table 5.10.4 provides R and R² values. As per the regression analysis as shown in the table, R value is 0.583, indicating that effect of macro environment and profitability along with control variables on capital structure in terms of DE is medium. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.340 which is 34 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.10.1), this new analysis exhibits slightly weaker result where R value is 0.583 instead of 0.588 and R² is 0.340 instead of 0.345. The new R² indicates that the ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE from profitability along with AG, FA, EPS, and ET from control variables can affect DE of capital structure by 34 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.10.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as AG, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of DE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	503.400	8	62.925	80.692	.000 ^b
	Residual	975.547	1251	.780		
	Total	1478.947	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Effective Tax Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Firm Age, Earning Per Share, Return on Equity, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Asset, Return on Invested Capital						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is presented in Table 5.10.5. The analysis shows that F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05), meaning the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.10.2), this new model depicts the same result which is 0.000 in both the analysis.

Table 5.10.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of profitability in terms of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE with control variables such as AG, FA, EPS and ET on capital structure in terms of DE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.234	.044		5.321	.000
	Return on Asset (ROA)	-12.814	.821	-2.382	-15.615	.000
	Return on Equity (ROE)	4.089	.441	.913	9.281	.000
	Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	4.892	.891	.934	5.492	.000
	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	2.786	.257	.582	10.853	.000
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.007	.001	.177	5.430	.000
	Firm Age (FA)	.003	.001	.119	5.082	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	-.001	.000	-.140	-4.890	.000
	Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.677	.117	.136	5.789	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Debt to Equity ratio

As shown in Table 5.10.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that all the independent variables like ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability, AG, FA, EPS and ET of control variables and DE of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This suggests that ROIC, ROCE, AG, FA and ET have statistically positive and significant effect on DE. ROA and EPS have statistically negative and significant effect on DE. As compared to previous analysis (see table 5.10.3), this new analysis exhibits significance level of all the independent variable at the same level which is 0.000.

In Table 5.10 .6, beta values of ROE, ROIC, ROCE, AG, FA and ET exhibit positive effect, which is 4.089, 4.892, 2.786, 0.007, 0.003 and 0.677 respectively. This is illustrative of the fact that increase in ROE, ROIC, ROCE, AG, FA and ET triggers the DE level to increase by 408.9, 489.2, 278.6, 0.7, 0.3 and 67.7 percent respectively. On the other hand, ROA and EPS exhibit negative effect, which is -12.814 and -0.001. This demonstrates that when there is an increase in ROA, there is a decrease in DE by -1281.4 and -0.1 percent respectively. When compared with previous analysis (see table 5.10.3) ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE produce stronger effect on DE which is -1281.4, 408.9, 489.2, 278.6 percent instead of -1254.6, 397.8, 483.3 and 275.3 percent. EPS exhibits weaker effect on DE which is -0.1 percent instead of -

0.2 percent. The beta value of AG, FA and ET remains the same in both the analyses, which is 0.7, 0.3 and 67.7 percent. It can be concluded that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the analysis produces a stronger f-statistics. Therefore, it can be expressed that the ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE of profitability along with AG, FA, EPS and ET of control variable affect the DE of capital structure in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$DE = \beta_0 + \beta_1ROA_1 + \beta_2ROE_2 + \beta_3ROIC_3 + \beta_4ROCE_4 + \beta_5AG_5 + \beta_6FA_6 + \beta_7EPS_7 + \beta_8ET_8 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$DE = 0.234 - 12.814*ROA + 4.089*ROE + 4.892*ROIC + 2.786*ROCE + 0.007*AG + 0.003*FA - 0.001*EPS + 0.677*ET.$$

Model 3: Capital Structure Affecting Profitability

In this analysis, all the variables from capital structure have been used as independent variables and all the variables from profitability have been used as dependent variables. Variables in capital structure are short-term debt (STD), long-term debt (LTD), total debts (TD) and debt to equity (DE). Variables in profitability are return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), return on invested capital (ROIC) and return on capital employed (ROCE).

Hypothesis 9

H9: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROA).

Table 5.11.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROA.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.088 ^a	.008	.005	.200992
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset				

Table 5.11.1 provides R and R² values. Regression analysis shows that the R value is 0.088. This indicates that the effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROA is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.008. This indicates that ROA of profitability can be affected by capital structure by 0.8 percent, according to this study.

Table 5.11.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROA.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.399	4	.100	2.472	.043 ^b
	Residual	50.699	1255	.040		
	Total	51.099	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio						

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.11.2. As per the analysis, F-Statistics is at 0.043 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.043 < 0.05$), meaning the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is significant, the significant value illustrates that at least one independent variable of the capital structure affects the ROA of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.11.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROA.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.070	.008		8.770	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.554	.845	-.177	-.655	.512
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.457	.843	-.271	-.543	.588
	Total debt ratio (TDR)	.352	.843	.226	.418	.676
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	-.001	.006	-.008	-.259	.796
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset						

As shown in Table 5.11.3, the results of the T-Statistics shows that STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.512, 0.588, 0.676 and 0.796 respectively, which is more than 0.05 (0.512, 0.588, 0.676 and 0.796 > 0.05). Therefore, this explains that STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER have statistically insignificant effect on ROA.

According to Table 5.11.3, beta exhibits negative effect on STDR, LTDR and DER, which is -0.554, -0.457 and -0.001 respectively. This illustrates that when there is an increase in STDR, LTDR and DER, there is a decrease in ROA in financial service companies by -55.4, -45.7 and -0.1 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta value of TDR shows positive effect which is 0.352, illustrating that when there is an increase in TDR, ROA of financial service companies also increases by 35.2 percent. However, the regression equation is not possible to form because the independents variables are insignificant in this analysis.

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 9:

In this analysis, TDR and DER have been excluded because the significance level of this variables are greater than 0.05 (see table 5.11.3). Therefore, the variables taken in this analysis are STD and LTD because the significance levels of these variables are closer to 0.05.

Table 5.11.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROA.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.087 ^a	.008	.006	.200851
a. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Short-term debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset				

Table 5.11.4 provides R and R² values. According to this table, R value is 0.087. This indicates that effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROA is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.008 which is 0.8 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.11.1), this new analysis exhibits slightly weaker result where R value is 0.087 instead of 0.088. The new R² indicates that the STDR and LTDR of capital structure can affect ROA of profitability by 0.8 percent.

Table 5.11.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROA.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.390	2	.195	4.831	.008 ^b
	Residual	50.709	1257	.040		
	Total	51.099	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Short-term debt ratio						

The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.11.5. The table shows that F-Statistics is at 0.008 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.008 < 0.05$), denoting the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.10.2), this new model produces stronger significant value which is 0.008 instead of 0.043. Thus, it can be concluded that this new model is a better predictor and an acceptable model for hypothesis 9.

Table 5.11.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROA.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.070	.008		8.811	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.205	.088	-.066	-2.321	.020
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.110	.048	-.065	-2.316	.021
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset						

As shown in Table 5.11.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that STDR and LTDR of capital structure and ROA of profitability are significant at the level of 0.020 and 0.021 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.020 and $0.021 < 0.05$). This explains that STDR and LTDR have statistically negative and significant effect on the ROA. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.11.3), this new analysis reveals that STDR and LTDR is statistically significant and affect ROA of profitability.

In Table 5.11.6, beta values of STDR and LTDR shows negative effect, which is -0.205 and -0.110 respectively. This demonstrates that an increase in STDR and LTDR triggers the ROA level to decrease by -20.5 and -11 percent respectively. When compared with previous analysis (see table 5.11.3) STDR and LTDR shows weaker effect on the ROA which is -20.5 and -11 percent instead of -55.4 and -45.7 percent. From the comparison of this new analysis with previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is accepted in this study because the f-statistics exhibits stronger and t-statistics produces significance in STDR and LTDR. Therefore, it can be said that the STDR and LTDR of capital structure affect the ROA of profitability in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1STDR_1 + \beta_2LTDR_2 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$ROA = 0.070 - 0.205*STDR - 0.110*LTDR.$$

Hypothesis 10

H10: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROE).

Table 5.12.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.113 ^a	.013	.010	.240786
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity				

Table 5.12.1 provides R and R² values. The result of the regression analysis shows that R value is 0.113, indicating that the effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROE is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.013, indicating that ROE of profitability can be affected by capital structure by 1.3 percent.

Table 5.12.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.949	4	.237	4.093	.003 ^b
	Residual	72.762	1255	.058		
	Total	73.712	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio						

The results from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.12.2. As per the analysis, F-Statistics is at 0.003 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.003 < 0.05$), which is illustrative of the fact that the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is a significant one, the significant value illustrates that at least one independent variable of the capital structure affects the ROE of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.12.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.067	.010		7.051	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.726	1.012	-.193	-.717	.473
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.498	1.010	-.246	-.493	.622
	Total debt ratio (TDR)	.493	1.010	.263	.488	.625
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.022	.007	.098	3.270	.001
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity						

As shown in Table 5.12.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that DER of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.001, which is less than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$). Therefore, this explains that DER has statistically insignificant effect on ROE. On the other hand, STDR, LTDR and TDR shows significance at the level of 0.473, 0.622 and 0.625 which is more than 0.05 ($0.473, 0.622$ and $0.625 > 0.05$). Therefore, STDR, LTDR and TDR are statistically insignificant.

In table 5.12.3, beta exhibits negative effect on STDR and LTDR which are -0.726 and -0.498 respectively, illustrating that when there is an increase in STDR and LTDR, there is a decrease in ROE in financial service companies by -72.6 and -49.8 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta values of TDR and DER show positive effect, which are 0.493 and 0.022. This illustrates that when there is an increase in TDR and DER, ROE of financial service companies also increases by 49.3 and 2.2 percent respectively.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_1 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$ROE = -0.067 + 0.022 * DER.$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 10:

In this analysis, LTDR and TDR have been excluded because the significance level of this variables are greater than 0.05 (see table 5.11.3). Therefore, the variables taken in this analysis are STD and DER because the significance level of STD is closer to 0.05 and DER is shown to be statistically significant.

Table 5.12.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.113 ^a	.013	.011	.240618
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity				

Table 5.12.4 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis shows that the R value is 0.113, indicating that the effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROE is weak. Further, regression analysis displays that R² value is 0.013 which is 1.3 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.1), this new analysis shows the R and R² value are as same as the previous analysis.

Table 5.12.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.935	2	.467	8.073	.000 ^b
	Residual	72.777	1257	.058		
	Total	73.712	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is given in Table 5.12.5. According to the analysis, F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), signifying that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.2), this new model depicts stronger significant value which is 0.000 instead of 0.003. Thus, it can be concluded that this new model is a better predictor and an acceptable model for hypothesis 10.

Table 5.12.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.067	.008		8.106	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.233	.105	-.062	-2.211	.027
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.022	.006	.097	3.471	.001
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity						

Table 5.12.6 shows the result of the T-Statistics. As per the table, STDR and DER of capital structure and ROE of profitability are significant at the level of 0.027 and 0.001 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.027 and $0.001 < 0.05$). This can be understood that STDR has statistically negative and significant effect on ROE. Further, DER has statistically positive and significant effect on ROE. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.3), this new analysis reveals that STDR and DER are statistically significant and affect ROE of profitability.

In Table 5.12.6, beta value of STDR shows negative effect, which is -0.233. This indicates that an increase in STDR has made the ROE level to decrease by -23.3 percent. Beta value of DER exhibits positive effect, which is 0.022. This means when there is an increase in DER, there is an increase in ROE. When compared to previous analysis (see table 5.12.3), STDR shows weaker effect on the ROE which is -23.3 percent instead of -72.6 percent. However, DER exhibits the same result as previous analysis. The comparison of new analysis with previous analysis implies that this new analysis is more acceptable in this study because the f-statistics exhibits stronger and the t-statistics reveals a significant effect in STDR and DER. Therefore, it can be expressed that the STDR and DER of capital structure affect the ROE of profitability in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1STDR_1 + \beta_2DER_2 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$ROA = 0.067 - 0.233*STDR - 0.022*DER.$$

Hypothesis 11

H11: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROIC).

Table 5.13.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROIC.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.120 ^a	.014	.011	.205803
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital				

Table 5.13.1 provides R and R² values. According to the table, R value is 0.120. This is indicative of the weak effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROIC. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.014, indicating that ROIC of profitability can be affected by capital structure by 1.4 percent.

Table 5.13.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROIC.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.777	4	.194	4.585	.001 ^b
	Residual	53.155	1255	.042		
	Total	53.932	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio						

The results from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in the Table 5.13.2. As per the analysis, F-Statistics is at 0.001 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$), meaning the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is significant, the significant value illustrates that at least one independent variable of the capital structure has affected the ROIC of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.13.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROIC.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.056	.008		6.871	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.686	.865	-.214	-.793	.428
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.604	.863	-.348	-.700	.484
	Total debt ratio (TDR)	.423	.863	.264	.490	.624
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.010	.006	.051	1.683	.093
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital						

As shown in Table 5.13.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER of capital structure are significant at the level of 0.428, 0.484, 0.624 and 0.093 respectively, which is more than 0.05 ($0.428, 0.484, 0.624 \text{ and } 0.093 > 0.05$). The figures explain that STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER have statistically insignificant effect on ROIC.

In Table 5.13.3, beta exhibits negative effect on STDR and LTDR, which is -0.686 and -0.604 respectively. This illustrates that when there is an increase in STDR and LTDR, there is a decrease in ROIC in financial service companies by -68.6 and -60.4 percent respectively.

On the other hand, beta values of TDR and DER show positive effect, which are 0.423 and 0.010 respectively. This illustrates that when there is an increase in TDR and DER, ROIC of financial service companies also increase by 42.3 and 1 percent.

However, the regression equation is not possible to form because all the independents variables are insignificant in this analysis.

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 11:

In this analysis, TDR and DER have been excluded because the significance level of TDR is greater than 0.05 (see table 5.11.3) and DER is showed to be insignificant in this new analysis. Therefore the variables taken in this analysis are STDR and LTDR because the significance levels of these variables are closer to 0.05.

Table 5.13.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROIC.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.109 ^a	.012	.010	.205892
a. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Short-term debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital				

Table 5.13.4 provides R and R² values. According to this table, R value is 0.109. This indicates that the effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROIC is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.012 which is 1.2 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.1), this new analysis exhibits slightly weaker result where R and R² values are 0.109 and 0.012 instead of 0.120 and 0.014 respectively. Therefore, it can be understood that STDR and LTDR of capital structure can affect ROIC of profitability by 1.2 percent according to this new analysis.

Table 5.13.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROIC.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.646	2	.323	7.618	.001 ^b
	Residual	53.286	1257	.042		
	Total	53.932	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Short-term debt ratio						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is presented in Table 5.13.5. The analysis shows that F-Statistics is at 0.001 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), which means the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.13.2), this new model produces same significant value which is 0.001. However, it can be concluded that this new model is a better predictor and an acceptable model for hypothesis 11 because the independent variables are statistically significant in this new analysis.

Table 5.13.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR on profitability in terms of ROIC.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.057	.008		6.948	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.249	.091	-.077	-2.744	.006
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.150	.049	-.087	-3.067	.002
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital						

As shown in Table 5.13.6, the result of the T-Statistics shows that STDR and LTDR of capital structure and ROIC of profitability are significant at the level of 0.006 and 0.002 respectively, which is less than 0.05 (0.006 and $0.002 < 0.05$). This explains that STDR and LTDR have statistically negative and significant effect on the ROIC. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.13.3), this new analysis shows that STDR and LTDR are statistically significant and have an effect on ROA of profitability.

In Table 5.13.6, beta values of STDR and LTDR exhibits a negative effect, which is -0.249 and -0.150 respectively. This implies that an increase in STDR and LTDR triggers the ROIC level to decrease by -24.9 and -15 percent respectively. When compared with previous analysis (see table 5.13.3), STDR and LTDR shows weaker effect on the ROIC which is -24.9 and -15 percent instead of -68.6 and -60.4 percent. When this new analysis is compared to the previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis is more acceptable in this study because the f-statistics exhibits stronger and the t-statistics shows significant effect in STDR and LTDR. Therefore, it can be said that the STDR and LTDR of capital structure affect the ROIC of profitability in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1STDR_1 + \beta_2LTDR_2 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$ROA = 0.057 - 0.249*STDR - 0.150*LTDR.$$

Hypothesis 12

H12: Capital structure has an impact on profitability (ROCE).

Table 5.14.1 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.190 ^a	.036	.033	.222763
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed				

Table 5.14.1 provides R and R² values. The regression analysis shows that R value is 0.190, which indicates that the effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROCE is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.036. This is indicative of ROCE of profitability being affected by capital structure by 3.6 percent in this study.

Table 5.14.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.320	4	.580	11.689	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.277	1255	.050		
	Total	64.598	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Long-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is presented in Table 5.14.2 where F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), denoting that the regression model is statistically significant. Since the regression model is significant, it illustrates that at least one independent variable of the capital structure affects ROCE of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.14.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, LTDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.052	.009		5.834	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.545	.937	-.155	-.582	.561
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.294	.934	-.155	-.314	.753
	Total debt ratio (TDR)	.436	.935	.248	.466	.641
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.031	.006	.147	4.941	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed						

Table 5.14.3 shows the results of the T-Statistics. As per the table, DER of capital structure is significant at the level of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that DER has statistically significant effect on ROCE. On the other hand, STDR, LTDR and TDR exhibits statistical significance at the level of 0.561, 0.753 and 0.641 which is more than 0.05 ($0.561, 0.753 \text{ and } 0.641 > 0.05$). Therefore, STDR, LTDR and TDR are statistically insignificant.

In table 5.14.3, beta represents a negative effect on STDR and LTDR, which are -0.545 and -0.294 respectively. This illustrates that when there is an increase in STDR and LTDR, there is a decrease in ROCE in financial service companies by -54.5 and -29.4 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta values of TDR and DER exhibits positive effect, which are 0.436 and 0.031, illustrating that when there is an increase in TDR and DER, ROCE of financial service companies also increase by 43.6 and 3.1 percent respectively.

However, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables only. This is as follows:

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_1 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$ROE = -0.052 + 0.031 * DER.$$

Results after avoiding insignificant variables in hypothesis 12:

In this analysis, LTDR has been excluded because the significance level of this variables is greater than 0.05 (see table 5.11.3). Therefore, the variables taken in this analysis are STD, TDR and DER because the significance level of STD and TDR are closer to 0.05 and DER is shown to be statistically significant.

Table 5.14.4 Model Summary of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.189 ^a	.036	.034	.222683
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed				

Table 5.14.4 provides R and R² values in which the regression analysis shows that R value is 0.189. This indicates that effect of capital structure on profitability in terms of ROCE is weak. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.036 which is 3.6 percent. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.1), this new analysis shows R value to be slightly weaker which is 0.189 instead of 0.190 and R² value is as same as the previous analysis.

Table 5.14.5 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.315	3	.772	15.563	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.282	1256	.050		
	Total	64.598	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Short-term debt ratio, Total debt ratio						

The results from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) as given in Table 5.14.5 reveals that F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.2), this new model depicts the same significant value which is 0.000.

Table 5.14.6 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of capital structure in terms of STDR, TDR and DER on profitability in terms of ROCE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.052	.009		5.847	.000
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.252	.106	-.072	-2.371	.018
	Total debt ratio (TDR)	.142	.057	.081	2.513	.012
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.031	.006	.147	4.940	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed						

As shown in Table 5.14.6, the result of the T-Statistics displays that STDR, TDR and DER of capital structure and ROCE of profitability are significant at the level of 0.018, 0.012 and 0.000 respectively, which is less than 0.05 ($0.018, 0.012$ and $0.000 < 0.05$). This is indicative of STDR to bear statistically negative and significant effect on ROE. Further, TDR and DER have statistically positive and significant effect on ROCE. As compared to the previous analysis (see table 5.12.3), this new analysis reveals that STDR, TDR and DER are statistically significant and have an effect on ROE of profitability.

In Table 5.14.6, beta value of STDR exhibits negative effect, which is -0.252. This depicts that an increase in STDR triggers ROCE level to decrease by -25.2 percent. Beta values of TDR and DER exhibits positive effect, which are 0.142 and 0.031. This means that when there is an increase in TDR and DER, there is an increase in ROCE. When compared with previous analysis (see table 5.14.3) STDR and TDR produce weaker effect on the ROCE which is -25.2 percent instead of -54.5 percent and 14.2 percent instead of 43.6 percent respectively. However, DER shows the same result as the previous analysis. From the comparison of this new analysis with previous analysis, it can be concluded that this new analysis stands as a better model in this study because the f-statistics is stronger and the t-statistics exhibits significant effect in STDR, TDR and DER. Therefore, it can be said that the STDR, TDR and DER of capital structure affect the ROCE of profitability in this study.

Therefore, the accepted regression equation in this study is formed as follows:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1STDR_1 + \beta_2TDR_2 + \beta_3DER_3 \dots \dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$ROA = 0.052 - 0.252*STDR + 0.142*TDR + 0.031*DER.$$

Model 4: Factors that affect Capital Structure also impact the Profitability

In this analysis, the significant variables from macro environment and capital structure along with control variables have been used as independent variables and all the variables from profitability have been used as dependent variables.

Hypothesis 13

H13: Micro and macro environment and capital structure do not have an impact on profitability (ROA).

Table 5.15.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROA.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.729 ^a	.531	.529	.138323
a. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Earning Per Share, Inflation Rate, Short-term debt ratio, Financial Crisis, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset				

Table 5.15.1 provides R and R² values, according to which R value is 0.729. This indicates that effect of macro environment and capital structure along with control variables on profitability in terms of ROA is strong. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that the R² value is 0.531, indicating that ROA of profitability can be affected by macro environment and capital structure with control variables by 53.1 percent.

Table 5.15.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROA.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.125	6	4.521	236.279	.000 ^b
	Residual	23.974	1253	.019		
	Total	51.099	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Earning Per Share, Inflation Rate, Short-term debt ratio, Financial Crisis, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage						

According to the result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) as shown in Table 5.15.2 F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. The statistical significance of the regression model illustrates that at least one independent variable of the macro environment, capital structure and control variables affects the ROA of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.15.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROA.

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.001	.009		-.137	.891
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.004	.000	.519	23.436	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.001	.000	.283	12.782	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	-.044	.010	-.085	-4.160	.000
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.010	.004	.050	2.518	.012
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.125	.061	-.040	-2.051	.040
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.077	.033	-.046	-2.348	.019

a. Dependent Variable: Return on Asset

As shown in Table 5.15.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that AG and EPS of control variables, FC and INF of macro environment and STDR and LTDR of capital structure and ROA of profitability are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.012, 0.040 and 0.019, which is less than 0.05 (0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.012, 0.040 and 0.019 < 0.05). From these figure it can be explained that AG, EPS, FC, INF, STDR and LTDR have statistically significant effect on ROA.

In Table 5.15.3, beta has been depicted to have a negative effect on FC, STDR and LTDR which is -0.044, -0.125 and -0.077 respectively. This illustrates that when there is FC and an increase in STDR and LTDR, there is a decrease in ROA in financial service companies by -4.4, -12.5 and -7.7 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta values of AG, EPS and INF exhibit positive effect which is 0.004, 0.001 and 0.010, illustrating that when there is an increase in AG, EPS and INF, ROA of financial service companies also increases by 0.4, 0.1 and 1 percent respectively.

Thus, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables. This is as follows:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AG_1 + \beta_2 EPS_2 + \beta_3 FC_3 + \beta_4 INF_4 + \beta_5 STDR_5 + \beta_6 LTDR_6 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$ROA = -0.001 + 0.004*AG + 0.001*EPS - 0.044*FC + 0.010*INF - 0.125*STDR - 0.077*LTDR.$$

Hypothesis 14

H14: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROE).

Table 5.16.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROE.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.715 ^a	.511	.508	.169684
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Financial Crisis, Short-term debt ratio, Inflation Rate, Earning Per Share, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity				

Table 5.16.1 provides R and R² values. The result from the regression analysis shows that R value is 0.715, indicating that effect of macro environment and capital structure along with control variables on profitability in terms of ROE is strong. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.511, which is indicative of ROE of profitability being affected by macro environment and capital structure with control variables by 51.1 percent.

Table 5.16.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	37.634	6	6.272	217.848	.000 ^b
	Residual	36.077	1253	.029		
	Total	73.712	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Financial Crisis, Short-term debt ratio, Inflation Rate, Earning Per Share, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage						

Table 5.16.2 shows result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA). As per the table, F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) which means the regression model is statistically significant. The significance of the regression model illustrates that at least one independent variable of the macro environment, capital structure and control variables affects the ROE of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.16.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.008	.011		-.761	.447
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.004	.000	.478	20.939	.000
	Earning Per Share (EPS)	.001	.000	.313	13.829	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	-.049	.013	-.079	-3.804	.000
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.010	.005	.042	2.077	.038
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.130	.075	-.035	-1.739	.082
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.010	.004	.044	2.179	.029
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Equity						

As shown in Table 5.16.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that AG and EPS of control variables, FC and INF of macro environment and DER of capital structure and ROE of profitability are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.038 and 0.029, which is less

than 0.05 (0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.038 and 0.029 < 0.05). Therefore, from these figures it can be explained that AG, EPS, FC, INF and DER have statistically significant effect on ROE. However, STDR and ROE exhibit significance at 0.082, which is greater than 0.05 (0.082 > 0.05). This means the DTDR has statistically insignificant effect on ROE.

In Table 5.16.3, beta represented a negative effect on FC and STDR which is -0.049 and -0.130 respectively which illustrates that when there is FC and an increase in STDR, there is a decrease in ROE in financial service companies by -4.9 and -13 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta value of AG, EPS, INF and DER showed a positive effect which is 0.004, 0.001, 0.010 and 0.010 respectively. This illustrates that when there is an increase in AG, EPS, INF and DER, ROE of financial service companies also increases by 0.4, 0.1, 1 and 1 percent respectively.

Thus, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables. This is as follows:

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AG_1 + \beta_2 EPS_2 + \beta_3 FC_3 + \beta_4 INF_4 + \beta_5 STDR_5 + \beta_6 DER_6 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$ROE = -0.008 + 0.004*AG + 0.001*EPS - 0.049*FC + 0.010*INF - 0.130*STDR + 0.010*DER.$$

Hypothesis 15

H15: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROIC).

Table 5.17.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROIC.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.734 ^a	.539	.536	.140942
a. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Earning Per Share, Inflation Rate, Short-term debt ratio, Financial Crisis, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Gross Domestic Product (Growth Rate)				
b. Dependent Variable: Return on Investment				

Table 5.17.1 provides R and R² values in which the R value is 0.734. This indicates that effect of macro environment and capital structure along with control variables on profitability in terms of ROIC is strong. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.539. This indicates that ROIC of profitability can be affected by macro environment and capital structure with control variables by 53.9 percent.

Table 5.17.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROIC.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	29.061	7	4.152	208.995	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.871	1252	.020		
	Total	53.932	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Investment						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Long-term debt ratio, Earning Per Share, Inflation Rate, Short-term debt ratio, Financial Crisis, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Gross Domestic Product (Growth Rate)						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.17.2 in which F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. Since this regression model is statistically significant, the significant value signifies that at least one independent variable of the macro environment, capital structure and control variables affects the ROIC of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.17.3 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC, GDP and INF, capital structure in terms of STDR and LTDR along with control variables in terms of AG and EPS on profitability in terms of ROIC.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.016	.014		-1.170	.242
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.004	.000	.528	23.975	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.001	.000	.277	12.615	.000
	Financial Crisis (FC)	-.041	.012	-.078	-3.380	.001
	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	.000	.003	.002	.065	.948
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.009	.004	.045	2.191	.029
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.166	.062	-.052	-2.669	.008
	Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	-.116	.034	-.067	-3.466	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Return on Invested Capital

As shown in Table 5.17.3, the result of the T-Statistics shows that AG and EPS of control variables, FC and INF of macro environment and STDR and LTDR of capital structure and ROIC of profitability are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.000, 0.001, 0.029, 0.008 and 0.001, which is less than 0.05 (0.000, 0.000, 0.001, 0.029, 0.008 and 0.001 < 0.05). These figures suggest that AG, EPS, FC, INF, STDR and LTDR have statistically significant effect on ROIC. However, GDP and ROIC exhibit significance at 0.948, which is greater than 0.05 (0.948 > 0.05). This means the GDP has a statistically insignificant effect on ROIC.

In Table 5.17.3, beta exhibits negative effect on FC, STDR and LTDR which is -0.041, -0.166 and -0.116 respectively. This illustrates that when there is FC and an increase in STDR and LTDR, there is a decrease in ROIC in financial service companies by -4.1, -16.6 and -11.6 percent respectively. On the other hand, beta values of AG, EPS and INF exhibit positive effect which is reflected as 0.004, 0.001 and 0.009 respectively, illustrating that when there is an increase in AG, EPS and INF, ROIC of financial service companies also increases by 0.4, 0.1, 1 and 0.9 percent respectively. Since GDP is statistically insignificant, it also shows no effect on ROIC because the beta value is 0.000 which is 0 percent.

Thus, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables.

This is as follows:

$$ROIC = \beta_0 + \beta_1AG_1 + \beta_2EPS_2 + \beta_3FC_3 + \beta_4INF_4 + \beta_5STDR_5 + \beta_6LTDR_6 + \dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$ROIC = -0.016 + 0.004*AG + 0.001*EPS - 0.041*FC + 0.009*INF - 0.166*STDR - 0.116*LTDR.$$

Hypothesis 16

H16: Micro and macro environment and capital structure have an impact on profitability (ROCE).

Table 5.18.1 Model summary of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of LTDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET on profitability in terms of ROCE.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.754 ^a	.569	.566	.149228
a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Financial Crisis, Short-term debt ratio, Inflation Rate, Earning Per Share, Effective Tax Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Total debt ratio				

Table 5.18.1 provides R and R² values, according to which R value is 0.754, indicating that effect of macro environment and capital structure along with control variables on profitability in terms of ROCE is strong. Further, the result of regression analysis shows that R² value is 0.569. This indicates that ROCE of profitability can be affected by macro environment and capital structure with control variables by 56.9 percent.

Table 5.18.2 ANOVA of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of LTDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET on profitability in terms of ROCE.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	36.739	8	4.592	206.222	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.859	1251	.022		
	Total	64.598	1259			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt to Equity ratio, Financial Crisis, Short-term debt ratio, Inflation Rate, Earning Per Share, Effective Tax Rate, Assets Growth Rate in Percentage, Total debt ratio						

The result from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is shown in Table 5.18.2 in which F-Statistics is at 0.000 significance level, which is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This indicates that the regression model is statistically significant. The significant value suggests that at least one independent variable of the macro environment, capital structure and control variables affects the ROCE of profitability. Thus, the null hypothesis of this model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5.18.3 Coefficients of the analysis of the effect of macro environment in terms of FC and INF, capital structure in terms of LTDR and DER along with control variables in terms of AG, EPS and ET on profitability in terms of ROCE.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.030	.010		-2.946	.003
	Assets Growth Rate (AG)	.004	.000	.491	22.797	.000
	Earnings Per Share (EPS)	.001	.000	.327	15.355	.000
	Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.039	.020	.038	1.952	.051
	Financial Crisis (FC)	-.049	.011	-.084	-4.302	.000
	Inflation Rate (INF)	.011	.004	.048	2.558	.011
	Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	-.210	.072	-.060	-2.923	.004
	Total debt ratio (TDR)	.218	.038	.124	5.685	.000
	Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.014	.004	.069	3.377	.001
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Capital Employed						

Table 5.18.3 shows the results of the T-Statistics, according to which AG and EPS of control variables, FC and INF of macro environment and STDR, TDR and DER of capital structure and ROCE of profitability are significant at the level of 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.011, 0.004, 0.000 and 0.001, which is less than 0.05 (0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.011, 0.004, 0.000 and 0.001 < 0.05). These figures suggest that AG, EPS, FC, INF, STDR, TDR and DER have statistically significant effect on ROCE. However, ET and ROCE exhibit significance at 0.051 significance level, which is greater than 0.05 (0.051 > 0.05), indicating that ET has statistically insignificant effect on ROCE.

It is clear from Table 5.18.3 that beta exhibits negative effect on FC and STDR, which is reflected in the values -0.049 and 0.210 respectively. This illustrates that when there is FC and increase in STDR, there is a decrease in ROCE in financial service companies by -4.9 and -21 percent. On the other hand, beta values of AG, EPS, INF, TDR and DER exhibit positive effect which is 0.004, 0.001, 0.011, 0.218 and 0.014 respectively, illustrating that when there is an increase in AG, EPS, INF, TDR and DER, ROCE of financial service companies also increase by 0.4, 0.1, 1.1, 21.8 and 1.4 percent respectively. Beta value of ET is 0.039 but ET is statistically insignificant.

Thus, the regression equation is formed by considering the significant independent variables. This is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ROCE} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AG}_1 + \beta_2 \text{EPS}_2 + \beta_3 \text{FC}_3 + \beta_4 \text{INF}_4 + \beta_5 \text{STDR}_5 + \beta_6 \text{LTDR}_6 \dots\dots\dots + \\
 &\quad \beta_n \text{X}_n \\
 \text{ROCE} &= -0.030 + 0.004 * \text{AG} + 0.001 * \text{EPS} - 0.049 * \text{FC} + 0.011 * \text{INF} - 0.210 * \text{STDR} \\
 &\quad + 0.218 * \text{TDR} + 0.014 * \text{DER}.
 \end{aligned}$$

5.5 Summary of Descriptive Findings

Table 5.19 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean
Total Assets (TA)	8.41145
Assets Growth Rate (AG)	8.21032
Firm Age (FA)	53.26982
Earnings Per Share (EPS)	41.72629
Liquidity Ratio (LR)	6.65896
Interest Coverage (IC)	266.88470
Effective Tax Rate (ET)	.03131
Financial Crisis FC	.19048
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	1.97143
Inflation Rate (INF)	1.99048
Bank Interest rate (IR)	2.67857
Short-term debt ratio (STDR)	.04097
Long-term debt ratio (LTDR)	.08107
Total debt ratio (TDR)	.12232
Debt to Equity ratio (DER)	.36223
Return on Asset (ROA)	.05270
Return on Equity (ROE)	.06550
Return on Invested Capital (ROIC)	.03429
Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	.06981
Valid N (listwise)	

According to the table 5.19, the financial service companies (FSCs) had both the current assets and fixed assets on an average of £257,899,203 (8.41145) per year from 1998 to 2018 and shows an assets growth rate on an average of 8.2 percent per year. In this study, sample companies appear to be mature as the table 5.19 depicts 53 years on an average of the sample companies. The returns from the share of FSCs were profitable as the average EPS of this study is 41.7 per share. FSCs maintained a healthy liquidity ratio and interest coverage ratio because the ratio is greater than 1 (6.7 and 267 > 1) and the average tax for FSCs remained low during the study period which is 3.1 percent. Macro environment such as GDP, INF and interest remained low during the year 1998 to 2018 which is 2, 2 and 2.7 percent respectively. In regard to debts level, FSCs maintained 12.2 percent of total debts level which included 8.1 percent of long-term debts and 4 percent of short-term debts. According to the DER, FSCs depended mainly on equity funds during this study period which is 36.2 percent debts levels. The average value of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE is .05270, .06550, .03429 and .06981.

The figures suggest that the FSCs generated 5.2, 6.5, 3.4 and 6.9 percent of ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE respectively every year on an average from 1998 to 2018.

5.6 Summary of Correlation and Regression Analyses

In this study, analysis is divided into four models and each model consists of four hypotheses. Thus, there are sixteen hypotheses in this study. In regression analysis, all the hypotheses of model 1, model 2 and model 3 have been reanalysed to attain stronger results. In addition, Pearson Correlation has been employed in order to examine the relationship of the variables and regression analysis has been employed to analyse and test the hypotheses of this study. The following are the summary of all the tested results:

Model 1: This model treats capital structure as dependent variable and macro environment and profitability as independent variable. Capital structure in terms of STDR is statistically correlated with GDP, INF, ROA, ROE and ROIC. In the case of LTDR, it is statistically correlated with IR, ROA, ROIC and ROCE. TDR is statistically correlated with FC, ROA, ROIC and ROCE. Similarly, DER is statistically correlated with IR, ROE and ROCE. In regard to the effect on dependent variables, INF and ROIC have significant effect on STDR, while IR, ROE, ROIC and ROCE have significant effect on LTDR. Similarly, IR, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE have significant effect on TDR and DER (see table 5.2 and 5.19).

Model 2: This model 2 is related to model 1, but analysis is carried out with the additional variables, which is a control variable. Capital structure in terms of STDR is statistically correlated with TA, LR, GDP, INF, IR, ROA, ROE and ROIC. The correlation of LTDR includes variables such as TA, FA, ET, IR, ROA, ROIC and ROCE. TDR exhibits greater correlation with control variables as it is shown to be correlated with TA, FA, LR, IC, ET, FC, ROA, ROIC and ROCE. DER is statistically correlated with TA, AG, FA, ET, IR, ROE and ROCE. In regard to the effect on the dependent variables when there is control variables, TA, LR, INF and ROIC have a significant effect on STDR. Further, TA, FA, EPS, ET, IR, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE have a significant effect on LTDR. TDR is significantly affected by variables such as TA, FA, EPS, LR, ET, IR, ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE, while DER is significantly affected by AG, FA, EPS, ET, ROA, ROE, ROIC AND ROCE (see table 5.2 and 5.20).

Model 3: This model treats capital structure as independent variable and profitability as dependent variable. The main variables that are statistically correlated with ROA are STDR, LTDR and TDR. Unlike ROA, ROE is statistically correlated with STDR and DER only. ROIC exhibits similar correlation with ROA in which the statistically correlated variables are STDR, LTDR and TDR. ROCE produces unique correlation as it is statistically correlated with LTDR, TDR and DER. In regard to the effect on dependent variables, STDR and LTDR appear to have a significant effect on ROA and ROIC. On the other hand, STDR and DER exhibit a significant effect on ROE. Similar to ROE, variables such as STDR, TDR and DER reveals that it has a significant effect on ROCE (see table 5.2 and 5.21).

Model 4: This model merges all the variables from control variables, macro environment and capital structure as independent variables and considered profitability as dependent variables. According to Pearson Correlation, variables such as TA, AG, EPS, IC, FC, GDP, STDR, LTDR and TDR are statistically correlated with ROA and ROIC. In the case of ROE, TA, AG, EPS, IC, ET, FC, GDP, STDR and DER exhibit correlation with ROE. ROCE exhibit slightly different correlation as the variables such as TA, AG, EPS, IC, ET, FC, GDP, LTDR, TDR and DER are statistically correlated with ROCE. In regard to the effect on profitability, AG, EPS, FC, INF, STDR and LTDR show significant effect on ROA and ROIC. In the case of ROE, it is significantly affected by the variables such as AG, EPS, FC, INF and DER. Variables such as ROCE, AG, EPS, FC, INF, STDR, TDR and DER exhibit a significant effect on ROCE.

5.7 Summary

This chapter is focussed exclusively on data analyses. The main objective of this chapter which is to present descriptive analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis has been accomplished. In descriptive analysis, the characteristics of the data have been discussed such as minimum and the maximum of the data, the mean value and the standard deviation of the data. In regard to correlation analysis, Pearson correlation has been employed to study the significance of the variables. In addition, this analysis examined the strength of the significance level. To meet the objective of this study, regression analysis has been applied to test the hypotheses. This analysis exhibited both the significance of the variable the beta value of the variables. The summary of regression analysis is shown in Table 5.20, Table 5.21, Table 5.22 and Table 5.23 below.

Table 5.20 Summary of hypotheses results model 1

Hypotheses	Significant Value (alpha)	Beta (β) Value	Result
H1: Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (STDR). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INF • ROIC 	 0.001 0.014	 0.006 -0.022	 Accept H1 Accept H1
H2: Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (LTDR). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IR • ROE • ROIC • ROCE 	 0.001 0.000 0.000 0.000	 0.004 0.649 -1.030 0.267	 Accept H2 Accept H2 Accept H2 Accept H2
H3: Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (TDR). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IR • ROA • ROE • ROIC • ROCE 	 0.021 0.030 0.000 0.000 0.000	 0.003 0.225 0.665 -1.294 0.277	 Accept H3 Accept H3 Accept H3 Accept H3 Accept H3
H4: Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (DER). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IR • ROA • ROE • ROIC • ROCE 	 0.049 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000	 0.023 -12.609 4.079 4.710 3.026	 Accept H4 Accept H4 Accept H4 Accept H4 Accept H4

Table 5.21 Summary of hypotheses results model 2

Hypotheses	Significant Value (alpha)	Beta (β) Value	Result
H5: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (STDR). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INF • ROIC • TA • LR 	<p>0.000</p> <p>0.046</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p>	<p>0.006</p> <p>-0.017</p> <p>-0.011</p> <p>0.000</p>	<p>Accept H5</p> <p>Accept H5</p> <p>Accept H5</p> <p>Accept H5</p>
H6: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (LTDR). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IR • ROA • ROE • ROIC • ROCE • TA • FA • EPS • ET 	<p>0.000</p> <p>0.025</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p>	<p>0.007</p> <p>0.207</p> <p>0.591</p> <p>-1.114</p> <p>0.236</p> <p>0.043</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.046</p>	<p>Accept H6</p>
H7: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (TDR). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IR • ROA • ROE • ROIC • ROCE • TA • FA • EPS • LR • ET 	<p>0.001</p> <p>0.008</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.003</p> <p>0.001</p> <p>0.003</p> <p>0.001</p>	<p>0.005</p> <p>0.272</p> <p>0.613</p> <p>-1.244</p> <p>0.265</p> <p>0.031</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.000</p> <p>0.046</p>	<p>Accept H7</p>
H8: Micro and Macro environment and profitability of the companies do not affect the capital structure (DER). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROA 	<p>0.000</p>	<p>-12.814</p>	<p>Accept H8</p> <p>Accept H8</p>

• ROE	0.000	4.089	Accept H8
• ROIC	0.000	4.892	Accept H8
• ROCE	0.000	2.786	Accept H8
• AG	0.000	0.007	Accept H8
• FA	0.000	0.003	Accept H8
• EPS	0.000	-0.001	Accept H8
• ET	0.000	0.677	

Table 5.22 Summary of hypotheses results model 3

Hypotheses	Significant Value (alpha)	Beta (β) Value	Result
H9: Capital structure does not have an impact on profitability (ROA).			
• STDR	0.020	-0.205	Accept H9
• LTDR	0.021	-0.110	Accept H9
H10: Capital structure does not have an impact on profitability (ROE).			
• STDR	0.027	-0.233	Accept H10
• DER	0.001	0.022	Accept H10
H11: Capital structure does not have an impact on profitability (ROIC).			
• STDR	0.006	-0.249	Accept H11
• LTDR	0.002	-0.150	Accept H11
H12: Capital structure does not have an impact on profitability (ROCE).			
• STDR	0.018	-0.252	Accept H12
• TDR	0.012	0.142	Accept H12
• DER	0.000	0.031	Accept H12

Table 5.23 Summary of hypotheses results model 4

Hypotheses	Significant Value (alpha)	Beta (β) Value	Result
H13: Micro and macro environment and capital structure do not have an impact on profitability (ROA).			
• AG	0.000	0.004	Accept H13
• EPS	0.000	0.001	Accept H13
• FC	0.000	-0.044	Accept H13

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INF • STDR • LTDR 	0.012	0.010	Accept H13
	0.040	-0.125	Accept H13
	0.019	-0.077	
H14: Micro and macro environment and capital structure do not have an impact on profitability (ROE).			Accept H14
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AG • EPS • FC • INF • STDR • DER 	0.000	0.004	Accept H14
	0.000	0.001	Accept H14
	0.000	-0.049	Accept H14
	0.038	0.010	Reject H14
	0.082	-0.130	Accept H14
	0.029	0.010	
H15: Micro and macro environment and capital structure do not have an impact on profitability (ROIC).			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AG • EPS • FC • GDP • INF • STDR • LTDR 	0.000	0.004	Accept H15
	0.000	0.001	Accept H15
	0.001	-0.041	Accept H15
	0.948	0.000	Reject H15
	0.029	0.009	Accept H15
	0.008	-0.166	Accept H15
	0.001	-0.116	Accept H15
H16: Micro and macro environment and capital structure do not have an impact on profitability (ROCE).			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AG • EPS • ET • FC • INF • STDR • TDR • DER 	0.000	0.004	Accept H16
	0.000	0.001	Accept H16
	0.051	0.039	Reject H16
	0.000	-0.049	Accept H16
	0.011	0.011	Accept H16
	0.004	-0.210	Accept H16
	0.000	0.218	Accept H16
	0.001	0.014	Accept H16

The result from Table 6.1 shows that capital structure of the financial service companies in the UK are significantly influenced by the profitability of the companies. As per the table, all the debts level are statistically affected by profitability ratios. In addition, interest rate of the bank also plays an important role in the capital structure because it shows a significant effect on long-term debts, total debts and debt to equity ratios. Inflation also plays an important role in terms of determining the short-term debts as it produces statistically significant results. Table 6.2 provides the different types of control variables while analysing the impact of macro environment on the capital structure decision of financial service companies.

Table 6.3 explains the impact of capital structure on profitability of the financial service companies. The above mentioned table stated that return on assets and return on invested capital is influenced by the level of short-term and long-term debts. On the other hand, return on equity and return on capital employed is influenced by short-term debts and debt to equity ratio. Total debts of the financial service companies depict the influence only in return on capital employed. Table 6.4 illustrates that the factors that influenced capital structure decision also influence the profitability of the firm.

CHAPTER SIX

Discussions

6.1 Introduction

As stated in the research objectives and statement of the problems, this study emphasises on the determinants of the capital structure and the significant relationship between capital structure and profitability of the firms. In addition, this study finds that there is an impact of micro and macro environment and capital structure on profitability. The discussions are presented below.

6.2 Macro environments with control variables and capital structure

The purpose of regression model 1 and model 2 is to study the main determinants of capital structure. In this section, all the main and significant determinants have been discussed and it is found that most of the determinants appeared from micro and macro environment of the firms. The findings of this study reveal that the determinants of capital structure have been affected differently by the control variables.

6.2.1 Macro environments

a) Inflation: Based on the results, the average inflation rate for the UK is 2 percent approximately. INF has a positive and statistically significant relation with STDR. It also has a positive and statistically significant effect on STDR. This suggests that during the period of higher inflation rate, the financial service companies of the UK appeared to utilise more short-term debts. In other words, when inflation rate increased, the level of short-term debts also increased. The results of this study show that inflation can affect short-term debt by 0.6 percent which is reflected in model 1 and model 2 both (see table 5.20 and 5.21). This result is graphically answered in figure 6.1 where inflation rate appears higher during 2008-09 financial crisis and the level of short-term debts in the financial service companies in the UK escalates simultaneously.

The results of this study on the influence of inflation on short-term debts have contradicted the results of studies which find negative impact on short-term debts. Thus, the positive impact of inflation on short-term debts is an opposite outcome to the findings in the previous work of Gajurel (2006) and Ganiyu (2015), who find negative impact and relation of inflation on short-term debts. However, it is important to acknowledge that these studies have been conducted in dissimilar environment. For instance, both the studies have been conducted in developing countries namely, Nepal and Nigeria. Besides, Ganiyu's study has excluded financial companies despite the period of the study (1998-2012) included the 2008-09 financial crisis. On the other hand, Gajurel's study stretches over the period of 1995 to 2004 and does not cover 2008-09 financial crisis. Hence, it is understood that these studies have been conducted in different industry sector where the sample of both the studies is based on firms listed in stock exchange of Nepal and Nigeria.

Interestingly, Mokhova and Zinecker (2014) finds a mix result when they studied non-financial manufactured companies from seven European countries for the period of 2006 to 2010. They study finds a strong negative significant relationship between inflation rate and total debt ratio and short-term debt ratio in Czech Republic and France. In addition, inflation shows a negative relation in other countries such as Slovakia, Hungary, Greece and Poland but the results are insignificant. On the contrary, Mokhova and Zinecker (2014) finds a positive influence in Germany and this study has been supported by the work of Memon *et al.* (2015) who finds that inflation has positive and significant effect on the debt ratios of the firms. The finding of Memon *et al.* (2015) is similar to the findings of Frank and Goyal (2009). Similar to the studies of Gajurel (2006), Ganiyu (2015) and Mokhova and Zinecker (2014), Memon *et al.* (2015) and Frank and Goyal (2009) also studied the non-financial companies from Pakistan and USA for the period from 2001-2012 and 1950-2003 respectively. The study study of Memon *et al.* (2015) and Frank and Goyal (2009) testify that influence of inflation on debts is positive for both the developed and developing countries. Therefore, the influence of inflation on corporate debt structure varies across countries and depends on the firms' capital structure. However, inflation plays a major role in financial decision making process.

b) Interest Rate: In the case of interest rate (IR), the average IR is 2.7 percent approximately during 1998 to 2018. According to the Table 5.2, IR shows negative and statistically significant relation with short-term debts (STD) but it is observed to have a positive relation with long-term debts (LTD). A negative relationship with STD is consistent with the study of Ganiyu (2015) where the study finds a negative relation between IR and STD. IR shows different results when compared to model 1 and model 2. As per the Table 5.20 and 5.21, the IR beta value of model 2 shows an increase when the variable is observed with control variables and it can affect only long-term debt and total debt (TD). Despite the significant relationship in correlation, regression analysis does not show any significant effects by short-term debt. Thus, the result indicates that IR can positively affect LTD by 0.4 percent and TD by 0.3 percent respectively. Having employed control variables, IR rises from 0.4 percent to 0.7 percent for LTD and it rises from 0.3 percent to 0.5 percent for TD. On the contrary, IR exhibits positive and statistically significant with debt to equity (DE) in model 1 and it does not show statistical significance when the control variables are used. Since this study is with control variables, the result of IR and DE are consistent with the study of Bjorkholm and Johansson (2015) where it is found to bear no statistical significance between IR and DE.

According to the figure 6.1, IR has a downward sloping trend and both the LTD and TD follow similar trend with IR. This indicates that IR has a positive relation with LTD and TD except for STD where the trend slightly shows in the opposite direction, denoting a negative relation between IR and STD. The positive effect and relation between IR and debt (leverage) support the previous studies of Deesomsak (2004), Mokhova and Zinecker (2014), Zein and Angstrom (2016) and Vintila *et al.* (2019) which reveal positive relationship between IR and leverage. Deesomsak (2004) studies non-financial firms in the Asia Pacific region, namely Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore and Australia for the period of 1993 to 2001. Deesomak observes an important finding that the interest rate has an insignificant relationship with debt before the 1997 financial crisis, whereas, interest rate becomes positively significant after the financial crisis. Mokhova and Zinecker (2014) is focussed on non-financial manufactured companies from seven European countries for the period 2006 to 2010. Despite the different result from other countries, they find positive and significant influence of interest rate on debt in Germany and France. Similarly, Zein and Angstrom (2016) examines the non-financial companies from Sweden and Vintila *et al.* (2019) studies the technology companies listed on the New York Stock Exchange.

On the contrary, this study adds to the argument of Antoniou *et al.* (2008), Ganiyu (2015) and Memon *et al.* (2015). Antoniou *et al.* (2008) explores the advanced economies of the world, namely France, Germany, Japan, the UK and the USA from 1987 to 2000 and finds a negative effect between interest rate and debts. Ganiyu (2015) investigates the Nigerian market and put up an argument that interest rate and debts are negatively related and affected because debts are not attractive to the firms due to high cost of borrowing. In addition, Memon *et al.* (2015) proves that interest rate is negative and significant in Pakistani markets. The author also claims that Pakistani firms avoid use of debt when interest rate is high in the market.

In case of this study, the results of the UK market are consistent with the study of Deesomsak (2004) where interest rate is positively significant after the 1997 financial crisis in spite of the negative effect of interest rate on debt in the UK. Hence, this proves that the effect of interest rate can vary over time. Debt financing is seen to be popular in developed economies because of abundance of financial markets and low cost of borrowings (Ganiyu 2015). This low cost of debts is seen in figure 6.1 where the interest rates are extremely low after the 2008-09 financial crisis. Thus, interest rate has a positive impact on the capital structure.

6.2.2 Control variables

a) Total Assets: In case of total assets (TA), the average asset of FSCs depicts £257,899,203 (8.41145) per year from 1998 to 2018. Table 5.2 proves that TA is statistically related to capital structure but it is significant in a different way. It exhibits a positive relation with LTD, TD and DE but displays a negative relation with STD. In regression analysis, TA exhibits an effect on STD, LTD and TD but does not show an effect on DE. LTD and TD are positively affected by TA, whereas, STD is negatively affected. Table 5.20 reveals that TA of FSCs affects its STD by -1.1 percent, LTD by 4.3 percent and TD by 3.1 percent. This indicates that FSCs maintained LTD rather than STD for operation. This is displayed in figure 6.1 where the LTD level is higher than STD. The negative impact of TA on capital structure is shown to bear consistency with the study of Schulz (2017), which finds a negative relation between TA and STD in Dutch small and medium firms. On the other hand, positive impact of TA on capital structure in terms of LTD and TD is consistent with the studies of Javed *et al.*, (2014) and Dawar (2014), which depict a positive relation between TA, STD and

LTD in non-financial companies from Pakistan and India respectively. Hence, it can be said that the influence of TA on debts remain consistent in different industry sector and markets.

b) Liquidity: The ability to repay a loan is important when debts are involved. Average liquidity ratio (LR) of FSCs is 6.7 percent, which is highly liquid and indicates that FSCs have no problem in repaying the loan. According to the Table 5.2, LR has statistically negative and significant relationship with STD and TD. On the other hand, it is insignificant with LTD and DE. Likewise, it also exhibits the same result in regression analysis, where LR produces statistically significant value in STD and TD. However, LR does not show any effect on STD and TD because beta value is zero (0). The negative relation between LR and STD is consistent with the findings of Hassan *et al.*, (2015), in which negative relation is found in three different industries such as consumer service, industrials and technology from the USA. Other negative relation between LR and TD is consistent with the findings of Schulz (2017) and Dawar (2014), where negative relationship has been detected in small and medium Dutch firms and non-financial Indian companies respectively. Having found the evidence from both the developed and developing economies, this study provides evidence that the liquidity has a negative relation to debts.

c) Firm Age: According to Table 5.1, average firm age (FA) of the FSCs in this study is 53 years, which indicates that the companies are no longer young. Table 5.2 reveals that FA has statistically positive and significant relationship with LTD, TD and DE and exhibits an insignificant negative relation with STD. This is because older firms normally have more debt ratio than the younger firms (Petersen and Rajan, 1994) and younger firms usually have less ability to access external financing (Anuar and Chin, 2016). Regression analysis predicts that FA does not have an effect on LTD and TD in spite of statistically significant variable. However, it shows positive effect of 0.3 percent on DE. The positive influence of FA on LTD and negative influence of FA on STD is supported by the finding of Hall *et al.* (2004). Hall *et al.* (2004) examines the incorporated SMEs from eight European countries, namely Belgium, Germany, Spain, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal and the UK where the results indicate that FSCs have the access to external financing which is debt financing. Therefore, FSCs use more of long-term financing rather than short-term financing. This result is reflected in figure 6.1, where the debt to equity ratio decreases as the firm grows older because over time, firms increase the internal equity ratio and decrease the level of debts sources (Hamilton and Fox, 1998 and Coad *et al.*, 2010). This also indicates that when FSCs

are highly dependent on debt financing when the firms were younger, it is extremely unfavourable for the profitability of FSCs. Positive significant relationship between FA and LTD, TD and DE contradicts with the findings of Ganiyu (2015) and Dawar (2014) which exhibit statistically negative relationship but both the studies are based on developing economies, namely Nigeria and India respectively. Thus, the influence of firm age on capital structure shows a dependency on regional economies like developed and developing economies.

d) Earnings Per Share: As far as the results of this study is concerned, the FSCs in the UK earn £41.7 per each share. However, earning per share (EPS) exhibits statistically no significant correlation with the capital structure. Similarly, regression analysis depicts that EPS is statistically significant but it does not affect the debts especially LTD and the TD. In the case of DER, EPS shows a negative and significant effect which is -0.1 percent. The result indicates that when investors earn more profit from the share, the debt level of FSCs decreases slowly. In figure 6.1, DE ratio continuously plunges from above 60 percent to below 30 percent. This negative relationship stands in contradiction with the findings of Salim and Yadav (2012), where debt and EPS has a positive relationship in Malaysian listed companies. On the other hand, this study is consistent with the study of Javed *et al.* (2014) where the study detects a negative relationship with debts in Pakistani listed companies. Thus, the result illustrates that earning per share can influence the capital structure of the firm in spite of the dissimilarity of the market.

e) Asset Growth: Assets growth rate (AG) of FSCs had a positive growth on an average of 8.2 percent during the two decades from 1998 to 2018. Both the correlation and regression analysis exhibit a positive and significant relationship only on DE. It indicates that when the AG of the FSCs decreases, DE also decreases by 0.7 percent. Figure 6.1 gives a hint that the AG of FSCs were increasing on an average yet in a declining stage, which also means that the assets of the FSCs reduced over time according to this study. Unfortunately, support for the positive relation between AG and DE fails to detect from another empirical studies.

f) Effective Tax: Table 5.1 reveals that the sample FSC firms paid 0.03 percent tax on an average during the period of 1998 to 2018. Both the results from correlation and regression show the same results as effective tax rate (ET) has a positive and statistically significant relationship with and has an effect on LTD, TD and DE. The results indicate that FSCs

received tax benefits from the government or they had tax advantages when FSCs borrowed a long-term loan, which shows an effect of 4.6 percent. DE or proportion between debts and equity, is greatly affected by ET which is 67.7 percent. However, the finding fails to support the study of Nenu *et al.* (2018) where the authors do not find a relationship between ET and debt in Romanian listed companies. Nevertheless, this study is consistent with the findings of Devereux *et al.* (2018) and Oino and Ukaegbu (2015), according to which there is an effect on and relationship of tax on debts in the UK companies and Nigerian non-financial companies respectively. Therefore, the result explains that influence of tax on debt does not rely on whether the country is developed or not. For instance, both the developing economies are contradicted to each other

6.2.3 Macro environment, capital structure with control variables and profitability

a) Return on Assets (ROA): As far as the management of the asset is concerned, FSCs in the UK made a profit of 5.27 percent on an average during the period of 1998 to 2018. This indicates that FSCs made 527 pence on an average in profit for every pound the companies had invested in assets. In model 1 and model 2, ROA predicts the capital structure of the FSCs. As far as the results of the model 1 and model 2 are concerned, ROA shows positive impact on LTD and negative impact on DE in model 1. Similarly, it exhibits positive impact on LTD and TD and negative impact on DE. Table 5.20 and Table 5.21 show the impact of ROA on capital structure. The strength of beta value increases with addition of control variables in the analysis. ROA exhibits effect on LTD by 20.7 percent in model 2 where it fails to meet the significance level in model 1. Likewise, it shows an increase in TD from 22.5 percent to 27.2 percent and in DE from -1260.9 percent to -1281.4 percent. These results indicate that when the return from the investment in assets increases, FSCs acquire more debts. On the other hand, proportion between debts and equity tends to fall as the ROA increases in the FSCs. Figure 6.1 also depicts clear picture of the impact of ROA on debts. Thus, the positive impact of ROA on LTD and TD supports the positive findings of previous studies by Salawu and Agboola (2008), Chandrasekharan (2012) and Barine (2012) in Nigerian perspective for the period of 1990-2004, 2007-2011 and 2008-2010 respectively. In addition, there are many previous studies that contradict with the positive findings. Some examples are studies conducted by Al-Sakran (2001), Chen (2004), Deesomsak *et al.* (2004), Chakraborty (2010) and Sheikh and Wang (2011) in Saudi Arabia, China, Asia Pacific, India and Pakistan.

Despite the similarity in the economy, the influence of ROA on capital structure is different. In addition, this study fails to detect support for the negative impact of ROA on DE.

Table 5.22 and Table 5.23 represent model 3 and model 4 where the impact of capital structure and macro environment with control variables, on profitability is studied. The control variables, AG and EPS have a positive impact on ROA, which is supported by Shahar and Shahar (2015) and Javed *et al.* (2014), whose studies trace a positive relationship and impact on ROA in Malaysian and Pakistani companies. Further, macro environment, FC has a negative impact on ROA which is related to the study of Hassan *et al.* (2015) which finds an impact of FC on STD and then on ROA in listed US firms. However, this contradicts with the study of Schulz (2017), which finds a positive relation between FC and ROA on Dutch unlisted SMEs. Despite the similar economy, the impact of FC varies according to the nature of the companies where FC negatively affects large companies and positively influences the small companies. Inflation shows a positive impact on ROA which is consistent with the study of Zulfiqar and Din (2015) which traces a positive effect on INF on ROA in Pakistani textile industry. Model 3, which shows the impact capital structure on profitability, illustrates that STD and LTD have a negative and statistically significant effect on ROA. This indicates that when STD grows in FSCs it can affect ROA by -20.5 percent and -11 percent by LTD. Further, model 4 demonstrates a negative effect on STD and LTD on ROA but the beta values of STD and LTD reduce its strength to -12.5 percent and -7.7 percent respectively. This negative effect of STD and LTD on ROA shows consistency with the results of previous research of Miller and Noulas (1997); Athanasoglou *et al.* (2005); Dawar (2014) and Kanwal *et al.* (2017) which find that debt has a negative and significant impact on profitability in the US and Greek banking industry, listed Indian companies and non-financial Pakistani companies respectively. However, this finding contradicts with the study of Abor (2005); Kyereboah-Coleman (2007) and Javed *et al.* (2014) which trace a positive impact of capital structure on firm's performances in listed firms of Ghana, micro-finance firms of Ghana and Pakistani non-financial companies respectively. Thus, the result notifies that debt has negative effect on the financial companies. In addition, Dawar (2014) and Kanwal *et al.* (2017) whose study period cut cross the 2008-2009 financial crisis shows a negative effect of debt on profitability. However, Abor (2005); Kyereboah-Coleman (2007) and Javed *et al.* (2014) which studies are conducted before the 2008-2009 financial crisis, shows a positive effect of debt on firm's profitability despite the economy of the study areas are similar.

Furthermore, it clearly shows that when control variable exists, the impact of debts on ROA also changes, indicating that more debt FSCs have, ROA declines significantly. Therefore, it is important for FSCs in the UK to maintain an optimum capital structure. Thus, the manager or executives of FSCs have to opt for the most profitable option of acquiring the debt. In this regard, LTD exhibits more favourable debt option than STD for FSCs to leverage its resources. This is because LTD is less impactful than STD on ROA (see Table 5.22 and Table 5.23). This observation is supported by figure 6.1 where FSCs acquired more LTD than STD during the period of 1998 to 2018.

b) Return on Equity (ROE): As far as the shareholders' money is concerned, FSCs in the UK made a profit 6.55 percent on an average during the period of 1998 to 2018. This indicates that shareholders of FSCs get a return on an average of 655 pence in profit for every pound the investor had invested in FSCs. In model 1, ROE predicts capital structure without control variables and found that it has a positive and statistically significant effect on LTD, TD and DE. Thus, ROE affects capital structure of LTD by 64.9 percent, TD by 66.5 and DE by 407.9 percent, indicating that debts of FSCs grow as the equity profit increases. This positive effect of profitability on capital structure extends its support to the previous study of Berger and Di Patti (2006) on commercial banks in the United States and Margaritis and Psillaki (2010) for French manufacturing firms as the authors find a positive relation between the firms' performances and capital structure. Furthermore, in model 2, when control variables are utilised in the analyses, the impact value of ROE on LTD and TD decreases by 59.7 percent and 61.3 percent respectively and De increases by 408.9 percent. Hence, it shows that control variables play a role in balancing the impact of ROE on the capital structure. Having reviewed both the model 1 and model 2, it is found that positive impact of ROE on the capital structure still remains similar in both the models in spite of the slight change produced by the control variables. However, this study contradicts with the previous study conducted by Margaritis and Psillaki (2007) for SMEs in New Zealand and Ganiyu (2015) for Nigerian firms as the authors trace a negative relationship between the firm performance and capital structure. Therefore, the results reveal that larger companies are positively affected by ROE and smaller companies and Nigerian companies are negatively affected by ROE.

On the contrary, model 3 and model 4 predict the impact of capital structure and macro environment, with control variables, on profitability. In similar with ROA, the variables such as AG and EPS from control variable and FC and INF from macro environment have an impact on ROE. AG and EPS have a positive impact on ROE and this is consistent with the study of Javed *et al.* (2014) and Shahar and Shahar (2015), which find a positive relationship and impact on ROE in Pakistani and Malaysian non-financial companies. Further, macro environment such as FC has a negative impact on ROE and this result is similar with the findings of Saddique *et al.* (2016) and Madaleno and Barbuta-Misu (2019) where the authors trace negative relationship between FC and ROE and negative influence of FC on ROE in Pakistani banks and non-financial European companies. Inflation exhibits positive impact on ROE which is supported by the study of Zulfiqar and Din (2015), which finds a positive effect on INF on ROE in textile industry of Pakistan, but this contradicts with the findings of Ayadi and Boujelbene (2012), which traces a negative impact of INF on profitability in SMEs of the UK. Zulfiqar and Din (2015) stretches over the period of 2006 to 2011 whereas Ayadi and Boujelbene (2012) extends over a period of 1998 to 2008. Therefore, the influence of 2008-2009 financial crisis plays a major role in Pakistani textile industry and in this study. For instance, when economy is down, government drops the interest rate to boost up the economy. Hence, inflation rises as the supply of money increases in the market which prompts the investment in the market and the profitability of the firms. However, when inflation is high, it is hard to cope for smaller companies like SMEs.

According to model 3 (Table 5.22), STD exhibits negative impact on ROE but in model 4, where the control variables and macro environments are included, STD is shown to be insignificant despite the negative impact on ROE. This negative effect of STD on ROE is supported by the study of Dawar (2014) in Indian perspective but this evidence contradicts with the majority of the studies conducted by Roden and Lewellen (1995); Ghosh *et al.* (2000); Hadlock and James (2002); Abor 2005; Margaritis and Psillaki (2007:2010); Kyereboah-Coleman (2007) and Gill *et al.* (2011) whose findings exhibit positive impact of capital structure on the firms' performance in the USA, Ghana, New Zealand and France. However, studies that show positive effect of STD on ROE do not cover the period of 2008-2009 financial crisis with the exception of Dawar (2014). Therefore, this study has shown that FC played a major role between STD and ROE.

Nevertheless, these contradictory findings by various researchers against the negative impact support the result of DE and ROE, where DE shows positive impact on ROE. Thus, the results indicate that shareholders have to be more concerned about the proportion between debt and equity where it is seen to be significantly affected on ROE in both model 3 and model 4. On the other hand, STD fails to validate its significance when the internal and external factors are considered in the study. Therefore, decision making in terms making the most profitable capital structure is important for FSCs because when DE increases, the profit of the shareholders also improves in spite of STD's negative effect on ROE. The impact of DER is shown as 2.2 percent in model 3 and decreases to 1 percent in model 4. Thus, it reveals that control variables and macro environment play a major role in capital structure decision to enhance the profitability of the firms.

c) Return on Invested Capital (ROIC): FSCs in the UK generated on an average, a profit of 3.43 percent during the period of 1998 to 2018 when it comes to the investment of shareholders' money. The average of ROIC is shown to be the lowest amongst the profitability ratios in this study. This indicates that FSCs get the return on an average of 343 pence in profit for every pound the companies invested in business from the investors' money. In model 1 and model 2, ROIC predicts the capital structure with macro environment and control variables and it is found that ROIC has a negative impact on STD, LTD and TD. On the other hand, it exhibits positive impact on DE, illustrating that when return of FSCs decreases, debt level increases in the capital structure. This is also reflected in figure 6.1 as the ROIC has a positive impact on DE and shows the decline of DER. In regard to the impact of ROIC on capital structure, this study fails to detect the support for the negative impact of ROIC on STD, LTD and TD.

Furthermore, model 3 and model 4 predict the impact of capital structure and macro environment, with control variables, on ROIC. Similar to ROA and ROE, ROIC also presents similar variables, such as AG, EPS from control variables and INF from macro environment, that have a positive impact on ROIC. In addition, FC shows negative impact on ROIC which is also consistent with the results of ROA and ROE, indicating that the return of FSC is affected when FC occurs. According to Achilleas *et al.* (2017) during the economic crisis, the profitability of the firm was affected adversely. Further, the positive effect of 0.4 percent in AG shows that the FSCs efficiently managed their invested capital, which shows EPS as having 0.1 percent positive return on their investors. These results support the positive

relationship between AG, EPS and firm performance in the study of Shahar and Shahar (2015) and Javed *et al.* (2014) on Malaysian construction companies and Pakistani non-financial companies respectively. The impact of INF on ROIC signifies that FSCs generate more profit from its investment when the inflation rate is higher. This contradicts the findings with the negative effect of Benabou (1992b) in the US retail sector and Kaskarelis (1993) in the UK manufacturing industry. However, this is supported by Ali and Ibrahim (2018) where the authors trace a positive relationship between INF and firms' profitability in manufacturing companies in Malaysia. The study of Benabou and Kaskarelis conducted before the 2008-2009 financial crisis stretches over the period of 1948-1985 and 1956-1991 respectively whereas the study of Ali and Ibrahim has been conducted for the period of 2011-2015. Therefore, the evidence proves that the firm's profitability is dependent on FC.

In regard to debt, STD and LTD exhibit negative impact on ROIC on both model 3 and model 4, which are similar with ROA, indicating that the return on FSCs' investment decreases when the debt level goes up. However, FSCs do not maintain heavy debts, which are reflected on figure 6.1 as the DER continuously fall over time. This negative impact related with the findings of Dawar (2014) and Kanwal *et al.* (2017) which finds that debt has negative and significant impact on profitability in India and Pakistan.

d) Return on Capital Employed (ROCE): In regard to the efficiency of FSCs with which its capital is employed, the average return the companies had during the period of 1998 to 2018 is 6.98 percent. This indicates that FSCs get the return on an average of 698 pence in profit for every pound the companies invested in business from its total capital. In model 1 and model 2, ROCE predict the capital structure with macro environment and control variables and it is found that ROCE has a positive impact on LTD, TD and DE. This shows that when return from the total capital employed in the business increases, the debt level increases in the capital structure. In regard to the impact of ROCE on capital structure, this study fails to detect support for the positive impact of ROCE on LTD, TD and DE.

Furthermore, model 3 and model 4 show consistent results with ROA, ROE and ROIC in terms of macro environment and control variables. This means AG, EPS and INF have a positive impact on ROCE, indicating when AG, EPS and INF rise, there is a higher ROCE in FSCs. This positive impact of macro environment and control variables on ROCE is related to the findings of Shahar and Shahar (2015) and Javed *et al.* (2014) and Ali and Ibrahim

(2018) where the researchers find a positive relationship and impact on firms' performances in Malaysian construction companies, Pakistani non-financial companies and Malaysian manufacturing companies. On the other hand, FC has a negative impact on ROCE but this study fails to detect the support from the previous study.

In regard to debts, STD exhibits negative impact, whereas TD and DE show positive impact on ROCE. Therefore, STD affects ROCE by -21 percent. TD and DE positively affect ROCE by 21.8 percent and 1.4 percent respectively. Negative impact of STD on ROCE is related to the findings of Dawar (2014) and Kanwal *et al.* (2017) which find that debt has negative and significant impact on profitability in Indian and Pakistani markets. On the other hand, Abor (2005); Kyereboah-Coleman (2007) and Javed *et al.* (2014) which trace a positive impact of capital structure on firm's performances in listed companies and microfinance companies of Ghana and non-financial Pakistani companies support the findings of the positive impact of TD and DE on ROCE. Thus, the results indicate that FSCs' capital structure is not optimum if the STD increases in the debt level. Instead, FSCs are profitable when they reduce STD and focus on other sources of fund.

6.3 Summary

The chapter is aimed at discussing the outcomes of quantitative aspects of the study. To achieve its objectives, results have been examined and the main findings of the current study have been highlighted, and more importantly, the role of external and internal factors in the financial service companies have been demonstrated by looking at the impact of capital structure and its determinants to the profitability of financial service sector in the UK.

This chapter explains external factors such as inflation and interest rate having an impact on capital structure of FSCs in the UK. In regard to the internal factors, total assets, liquidity, firm age, earning per share, assets growth rate, effective tax and profitability are shown to have an influence in the decision of capital structure of the FSCs in the UK. In addition, the explanation regarding the impact of capital structure and its determinants on profitability has been covered in this chapter where the results exhibit to have a significant impact on profitability of FSCs in the UK.

Figure 6.1 Average values of macro environment, capital structure and profitability

Source: Created by the author.

CHAPTER SEVEN

Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

This chapter aimed at deriving conclusions and suggesting recommendations based on the major findings and implications of this study. Summary of the research has also been discussed. Through careful investigation, this study contributes to various empirical studies. In addition, this study contributes to practical application of FSCs in the UK. Contribution of the study is followed by recommendations in which it provides several practical recommendations to FSCs in the UK and to the lenders in the UK in general. It is also important to acknowledge the limitations in the research. Therefore, limitations in terms of methodology and other difficulties faced in this research have been discussed. In addition, this study also provides new suggestions for future research in the area of capital structure and profitability analysis.

7.2 Overview of the Study

The main aim of this study is to determine the effects of capital structure on profitability or firms' performance of FSCs in the UK. The need to have an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon and to have an adequate reflection, this study has established three major questions for this study: *What are the main determinants of capital structure? Is there a significant relationship between capital structure and firm performance? Does capital structure affect the profitability of FSCs in UK?* To answer the research questions thoroughly, this study extensively conducts related theoretical and empirical literature review so as to find research gap in literature so that it can be fulfilled the gap in the literature.

To fulfil the research questions and research gap, this study builds research objectives: *To identify the determinants of capital structure. To analyse the relationship between capital structure and firm performance. To determine the impact of capital structure of FSCs' profit in the UK.* To build the foundation for the research objectives, this study closely explores related literature and built theoretical framework to develop the foundation for new conceptual framework. Based on the theoretical framework, the new conceptual framework

has been developed to display the path and idea of this research. Hence, this conceptual framework helps to establish dependent and independent variables for this research. Therefore, based on dependent and independent variables, the research hypotheses have been developed in this research to show the testable variables and predict the effect of capital structure on the firm's profitability.

Further, to achieve the aim and objectives and to empirically prove the new constructed model, this study explores the sixty (60) financial service companies (FSCs) from 1998 to 2018 which are listed in London Stock Exchange (LSE), United Kingdom. In addition, this study develops four models including four variables on capital structure, four variables on macro environment, seven control variables and four variables on profitability. The data of this study have been analysed by using Pearson correlation and regression analysis.

Based on the correlation analysis of this study, majority of the control variables (TA, AG, FA, LR, IC and ET) are correlated with capital structure. However, EPS fails to show correlation with any of the variables of capital structure. In case of profitability analysis, FA and LR fail to show correlation with any of the variables from the profitability and other variables like TA, AG, EPS, IC and ET exhibit correlation with profitability. The macro environment (FC, GDP, INF and IR) are correlated with capital structure. In the case of profitability, only FC and GDP exhibit correction where as INF and IR have failed to determine the correlation with any of the variables of profitability. As far as relationship between capital structure and profitability of the firm is concerned, all the variables of capital structure prove that there is a correlation between capital structure and the profitability of the firm.

Besides, the regression results of model 1 and model 2 confirm that profitability (ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE) of the FSCs affects capital structure of FSCs that include variables like INF and IR from macro environment but FC and GDP have no impact on capital structure. Internal factors (control variables) also play a significant role in the capital structure decision where majority of the variables (TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR and ET) of control variables have an impact on capital structure of FSCs. However, IC has no impact on any of the variables of capital structure.

Furthermore, the regression results of model 3 and model 4 prove that capital structure (STD, LTD, TD and DE) has an impact on the profitability of FSCs. In regard to macro environment, FC and INF shows an effect on profitability. On the other hand, GDP and IR exhibit no impact on profitability of the firm. In the case of control variables, only AG and EPS have an effect on profitability and other variables like TA, FA, LR, IC and ET has no impact on the profitability of the firm. In the case of GDP and IC, these two variables exhibit no effect in both capital structure and profitability of FSCs. Thus, despite many variables failing to affect profitability, it can be concluded that the factors (macro environment and control variables) that affect the capital structure of FSCs also impact the profitability of FSCs as a whole.

7.3 Contribution of the Research

7.3.1 Theoretical and empirical Contributions

The results of this study provides a negative impact of debt on profitability which means higher the debt, lower the profitability of the firms. According to these results, there are two capital structure theories consistent with the results; namely, pecking order theory and agency cost theory. Firstly, the negative effect of debts on profitability is consistent with the pecking order theory (Muscettola and Naccarato, 2016). As far as this theory is concerned, internal financing is more preferred than any external financing (Myers, 1984) because debts are appeared to be costly for FSCs in the UK. Secondly, Fama and French (1998) state that negative effect of debts on profitability may cause agency issues between shareholders and managers or creditors. Kebewar (2012) supports the claim of Fama and French (1998) and clarifies that there is positive effect of debt on profitability when there is agency issue between shareholders and managers. In contrast, there is negative effect of debt on profitability when there is agency issue between shareholders and lenders. Therefore, this study supports the assumptions of pecking order theory and agency cost theory of capital structure by demonstrating negative effect of STD and LTD on ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE in the case of FSCs in the UK.

This study extends the previous study of Abor (2005) by focusing on time frame, which is from 1998 to 2018, instead of five years. In addition, this study focuses more in terms of selecting the study area by concentrating only on one industry, which is FSCs in the UK instead of studying different industries together. Therefore, this study contributes new evidence by revealing that debt has a negative impact on ROA and ROIC. However, debt has a mix effect on ROE and ROCE, where STD has a negative effect and TD and DE has a positive effect, which is related to Abor's previous findings.

Similar to Abor (2005), this study further expands the study of Gill *et al.* (2011) who, in turn extends the study of Abor by narrowing down the industry by focusing only on two industries, which are American service firms and manufacturing firms listed on New York Stock Exchange. They examine the study only for the period of three years and trace a positive relationship. However, this study provides a new argument that debts negatively affect profitability of the firm, in which this study finds that all the debts negatively affect ROA and ROIC and STD negatively affect ROE and ROCE.

Abeywardhana (2016) examines the impact of capital structure on firm performance of manufacturing sector SMEs in the UK. The findings of this study conclude that SMEs in the UK which perform well do not rely on debt capital. On the contrary, they finance their firms from retained earnings. This is due to fact that SMEs have less access to external finance and face difficulties in borrowing funds. Although this study focuses on the financial service firms, this study experiences similar situation where smaller FSCs maintain less or zero level of debts in their capital structure. On the other hand, giant FSCs experience high debt level in their capital structure including the crisis period. This study provides new input to the evidence of the study of Abeywardhana.

Nasimi (2016) explored the relationship between capital structure and profitability by examining thirty firms from FTSE-100 index of the London Stock Exchange for the period of 2005-14. However, Nasimi used only two independent variables which are interest coverage and debt to equity. Therefore, this study extended this study by including more independent variables and found that debts, assets growth, earnings per share, financial crisis and inflation affect the profitability of the firm.

The study by Vuong *et al.* (2017) concentrates on 739 UK's large companies listed in London Stock Exchange (LSE). One of the findings of their study show that the global financial crisis does not affect on the relationship between leverage and profitability indicators. However, this study re-examines the impact of financial crisis on firm's profitability and the finding of this study contradicts with their study. This study finds that financial crisis negatively affect ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE and hence proves that financial crisis impact the profitability of the firm. Thus, this study provides a new understanding to the financial crisis by extending the study of Vuong *et al.* (2017).

The study of Bui (2017) finds that there is insignificant effect of STD on ROA and ROE of British Gas and Oil companies. Bui finds this result by examining 99 financial statements of 18 British Gas and Oil companies from 2009 to 2014. This shows that the result of Bui's study contradicts with the result of Abeywardhana (2016). The reason for this could be due to the nature of the business as British Gas and Oil companies and SMEs are two different industries. Despite the size of the companies, this study finds that STD has a significant and negative effect on ROA and ROE. Therefore, this study clarifies the confusion between these two studies by supporting Abeywardhana's findings.

7.3.2 Contributions for Financial Service Companies

There are many studies which explore the impact of capital structure on profitability in the case of the UK such as Bui (2017); Vuong *et al.* (2017); Nasimi (2016) and Abeywardhana (2016). However, all the related studies examine different industries in the UK and the financial service industry in the UK remains unexplored. Therefore, this study contributes to FSCs to understand the impact of internal and external factors on capital structure of FSCs and its profitability.

Further, the concept of newly developed framework in this study is based on previously proven work. Thus, it gives a robust concept regarding the investigation of cause and effect of internal and external factors on capital structure and the profitability of FSCs. In addition, this study is believed to be one of the earliest studies that focuses in the area of financial service in the UK. Therefore, this study contributes a new concept to the FSCs so that FSCs could extend this concept to develop a superior concept to investigate their operations.

The variables of this study are based on many related studies. Majority of the variables have an impact on capital structure and profitability but interest coverage and GDP fails to show any significant impact on capital structure and profitability. Therefore, this study reveals insignificant variables and contributes to the FSCs that interest coverage and GDP are insignificant to predict the impact of capital structure on profitability in financial service field in the UK. On the other hand, this study reveals important macro environment variables that have a significant effect on the profitability of the financial service companies in the UK. These variables are interest rate and inflation. Therefore, this study adds to the importance of interest rate and inflation rate because borrowing money is highly dependent on the interest rate of the banks and the inflation of the country. This new knowledge regarding the significant and insignificant factors would help the managers of FSCs in their financing decisions.

This study exhibits that short-term debts are more expensive to acquire than long-term debts in the UK as the impact of short-term debt is negatively greater than long-term debt. The findings of this study also reveal that financial service companies preferred long-term debts to short-term debts. Thus, this study introduces new insights regarding the cost of debt financing so that the managers of FSCs would be able to pre-decide the cost of debt in their proficient planning because cost of debts are already noticed by the firms (Mandelker and Rhee, 1984).

In addition, this study reveals that the FSCs in the UK are mainly dependent on equity funds or other resources despite extremely low interest rate in the UK. This finding indicates that low interest rate in the UK fails to attract the FSCs in the UK which mean debt financing is less popular than the equity financing in the financial service area. According to the pecking order theory, firms prefer internal sources to debt funds and equity funds, indicating negative effect of debt on profitability. However, FSCs prefer more expensive funding (equity funds) to debt funding. On the other hand, agency cost theory suggests that negative effect of debt on profitability is also experienced when there is conflict between the shareholders and lenders (Kebewar, 2012). Since FSCs prefer equity funds to debt funds inspite of the interest rate is low, the reason for negative effect of debts on profitability of FSCs in the UK could be agency cost of debt between the shareholders and debt holders. This is because the debt holders impose a restriction on the use of the funds. Therefore, this study contributes a new knowledge for the FSCs and signals their managers to inspect their management issues.

7.4 Recommendations

This study finds that macro environment has an impact on capital structure. Variables like inflation and interest rate exhibit a significant impact on capital structure of FSCs in the UK. In regard to the inflation, it shows positive impact on STD. Therefore, when FSCs decide to fund their operation through STD, it is advisable to consider the rate of inflation in the market and to choose the right timing to exercise the contract. The advisable timing to exercise the STD contract is when the inflation rate is higher than the normal rate in the UK market because the flow of fund is higher when the inflation is high. In addition, internal factors such as TA and LR show significant influence on capital structure especially on STD. However, LR does not show any impact on STD. Thus, only TA has an impact from internal environment. Based on the result, bigger the size of the FSCs, there is a lower preference for STD because TA shows negative impact on STD. Therefore, this research recommends FSCs to follow the trend of inflation regardless of their sizes because STD is highly expensive than the LTD to acquire.

In regard to interest rate, it is shown to have a positive impact on LTD. Similar to STD, when FSCs decide to obtain LTD for its business operation, this study recommends FSCs to follow the trend of interest rate as it has a positive impact on companies' capital structure. The advisable trend is when the interest rate is high, FSCs should opt for LTD and they should avoid when the rate is lower than the normal rate. According to Antoniou *et al.* (2008) and Memon *et al.* (2015) when the tax rate is higher, there are more benefits of using the debts because high interest expense brings more tax shield to the companies' profitability. However, figure 6.1 indicates that FSCs in the UK obtain more LTD when interest rate in low because when LTD debts are cheaper, the interest in the bank is lower. By doing this, FSCs miss the opportunities of higher tax shield. Thus, borrowing LTD while the interest is higher is more advisable as per this study. In addition, internal factors like TA, FA, EPS and ET exhibit significant influence. However, only TA and ET are shown to have positive impact on capital structure. These indicate that bigger the size, bigger the LTD. However, FSCs should consider the interest rate regardless of their size to increase the profitability through tax shield. In regard to the ET, if FSCs can borrow LTD when interest rate in higher, they can bring more tax shield as per the result of this study that shows higher payment of tax leads to higher LTD.

Based on the results, debt has a significant negative impact on profitability in terms of ROA and ROIC. In general, this means when FSCs in the UK acquire more debts in their capital structure to operate the business, the return in ROA and ROIC tends to decrease. In addition, FC has a negative effect on ROA and ROIC which could further hamper the business if the FSCs borrow funds during FC. Therefore, in order to improve ROA and ROIC, the study recommends that the FSCs should improve the strategy to acquire the debt funds. Since inflation has positive impact on ROA and ROIC, FSCs should not increase the borrowings during the inflation rate is low or at the average. Figure 6.1 justifies that during 2000 to 2003 inflation rate is at the lowest, however, FSCs increase its borrowings in this period, which affects the profitability of FSCs in the UK. Thus, FSCs should avoid raising debt financing when the rate is low and wait for the inflation rate to go up.

The findings of this study show that DE has a positive effect on ROE and ROCE. This indicates that when DE ratio is high, the profitability of FSCs also grows and when it is low, the profitability also low. According to the figure 6.1, DE ratio of FSCs from 1998 to 2018 reveals a continuously decreasing trend. This signifies that FSCs rely more on equity funds since 2001. On the other hand, Bank of England has cut the interest rate in order to maximise the inflow of the fund to the businesses in the UK. Thus, it can be understood that FSCs have been relying on the expensive source of funding for its businesses. Therefore, to reduce the expenses FSCs could borrow more debts to reduce the agency-based costs and increase the tax shield. Gallo (2015) clearly explains that DE ratio tends to be below 2 for technology-based businesses and between 2 to 5 for large manufacturing and publicly traded companies. However, for banking and financial based companies, it is not uncommon to have a ratio of 10 to 20, which is 100 to 200 percent. Thus, FSCs being financial based companies, they could rely more on debt financing instead of equity financing.

The finding of this study shows that interest rate in the UK has been extremely low since 2008. However, DE ratio reveals that the rate of borrowing has been declining continuously in the UK. Therefore, to encourage the borrowings in the market, lenders could come up with more attractive incentives. For instance, in the UK the interest rate of STD which needs to be repaid within one year is approximately 5 percent or more. However, in the case of LTD, the interest is approximately 1 percent. Thus, lenders could reduce the interest rate of STD (Business Comparison, Online).

7.5 Limitations of the Study

This study provides a detailed view of the effect of capital structure on the profitability of FSCs in the UK. However, there are few limitations of the study relating to target population, choice of independent variables and time period. Therefore, the researcher assumes that limitations of the study might influence the final outcome.

In the financial service sector, there are 549 companies all together. However, the researcher could not consider all the 549 companies to analyse this study. The unavailability of data from all the companies led the researcher to choose the companies whose data are readily available and accessible to the researcher. Therefore, the researcher takes into account all the 549 companies but analysed only 60 companies whose data are available to the researcher.

In the present study, researcher selects only secondary data in order to analyse the profitability of the companies that are totally dependent on sources like annual reports of the companies. In this study, the researcher does not consider other factors which could be done by primary sources such as goodwill, brand loyalty and so on and so forth, which also helps companies to attain profitability. However, these types of variables are qualitative in nature. Further, this research misses out on many important inputs such as the opinion from the finance manager from the respective companies. Although the primary data could give further insight into the study, it was beyond the scope of this study. Therefore, in this study the researcher could not study all the variables that might possibly have an impact on profitability. Thus, the researcher has selected the variables only on the basis of availability of sources like financial data of the companies.

In addition, the financial reports of FSCs change the accounting format in certain years. The researcher finds that all the companies do not follow the similar formula while presenting the accounting report. This type of complexity restrains the data to be calculated more accurately.

This study examines the financial service companies in the UK. However, the sizes of the companies are not similar in this study. For example; some companies are big and already existed in the market for a long period of time. However, some companies are smaller in size and relatively newer in the market. Therefore, studying different size of the companies may

affect the outcome of the analysis and the outcome may not be applicable for all the sample companies.

7.6 Future Research

This study focuses on testing the impact of the macro environment (FC, GDP, INF and IR) with control variables (TA, AG, FA, EPS, LR, IC and ET) on capital structure (STD, LTD, TD and DE) and its impact on profitability (ROA, ROE, ROIC and ROCE). These variables prove that this study mostly includes financial ratios and numerical variables. However, there are numerous other factors that influence the profitability of the firm. Therefore, future studies should look from different perspective such as marketing and human resource perspective. In addition, this study is done based on quantitative data whereas, the results of qualitative data may differ from this study. Therefore, future research should include both quantitative and qualitative data.

The samples of this study are listed companies on the London Stock Exchange. This could pose as one of the limitations as the outcome of this study fails to represent the entire financial service sector and the whole industry in the UK. As this study takes into account the data of companies in the UK only, the results cannot be generalised and applied in other countries or region. This calls for the future studies for expansion of the scope of study to stretch across different sectors and countries.

This research gathered the data for the period of 21 years which is from 1998 to 2018. Within this study period and outside the study period there are countless difficulties for FSCs both domestically and internationally. Some of the noteworthy issues are BREXIT and the Covid-19 Pandemic, which this study could not cover. However, it is remarkably important to notice that during Covid-19 Pandemic the Government of the UK slashes the interest rate from 0.75 percent to 0.25 percent on 11 March, 2020 and then cut it again to 0.1 percent on 19 March, 2020 to boost the economy of the country. Therefore, it would be an interesting study if the future research investigates the profitability of FSCs by including BREXIT, Post-BREXIT and the Covid-19 Pandemic period, which will be from 2016 to beyond 2020.

In the study of Ganiyu (2015) in Nigeria, the author mentions that long-term debt has been largely financed in the developed economies whereas short-term debt is favourable in the

developing economies. In addition, this study also finds that long-term debt is less expensive to acquire than the short-term debt. Therefore, future research on comparative studies of FSCs or two similar industries of two different economies (developed and developing) is likely to produce fascinating results.

The finding of this study is consistent with two theories of capital structure which is the pecking order theory and agency cost theory. Thus, this study suggests the comparative study of these two theories of capital structure in the future research to examine which theory provide the precise understanding on the negative effect of debts on profitability of firms.

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APPENDIX

Financial Service Companies Selected for the Study

No.	Financial Service Companies
1	3I Group
2	ABERDEEN NEW THAI INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
3	ABERFORTH SMALLER COMPANIES TRUST PLC
4	ALLIANCE TRUST PLC
5	BAILLIE GIFFORD JAPAN TRUST PLC
6	BAILLIE GIFFORD SHIN NIPPON PLC
7	BAILLIE GIFFORD UK GROWTH FUND PLC
8	BANKERS INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
9	BRITISH AND AMERICAN INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
10	BRUNNER INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
11	CHARLES STANLEY GROUP PLC
12	CITY OF LONDON INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
13	DUNEDIN ENTERPRISE INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
14	DUNEDIN INCOME GROWTH INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
15	EDINBURGH DRAGON TRUST PLC
16	EDINBURGH INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
17	FIDELITY ASIAN VALUES PLC
18	FIDELITY EUROPEAN VALUES PLC
19	FIDELITY JAPAN TRUST PLC
20	FIDELITY SPECIAL VALUES PLC
21	FOREIGN AND COLONIAL INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
22	GRESHAM HOUSE PLC
23	HENDERSON HIGH INCOME TRUST PLC
24	HENDERSON SMALLER COMPANIES INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
25	HERALD INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
26	INTERMEDIATE CAPITAL GROUP PLC
27	INTERNATIONAL BIOTECHNOLOGY TRUST PLC
28	INVESCO ASIA TRUST PLC
29	INVESTMENT COMPANY PLC
30	LAW DEBENTURE CORPORATION PLC
31	LONDON FINANCE AND INVESTMENT GROUP PLC
32	LOWLAND INVESTMENT COMPANY PLC
33	MAJEDIE INVESTMENTS PLC
34	MANCHESTER AND LONDON INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
35	MID-WYND INTERNATIONAL INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
36	MONKS INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
37	MONTANARO UK SMALLER COMPANIES INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
38	MURRAY INCOME TRUST PLC

39	MURRAY INTERNATIONAL TRUST PLC
40	NORTH ATLANTIC SMALLER COMPANIES INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
41	NORTHERN INVESTORS COMPANY PLC
42	PACIFIC ASSETS TRUST PLC
43	PACIFIC HORIZON INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
44	PERPETUAL INCOME AND GROWTH INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
45	PERSONAL ASSETS TRUST PLC
46	PROVIDENT FINANCIAL PLC
47	RIGHTS AND ISSUES INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
48	RIT CAPITAL PARTNERS PLC
49	S AND U PLC
50	SCHRODER INCOME GROWTH FUND PLC
51	SCHRODER JAPAN GROWTH FUND PLC
52	SCOTTISH AMERICAN INVESTMENT CO. PLC
53	SCOTTISH INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
54	SCOTTISH ORIENTAL SMALLER COMPANIES TRUST PLC
55	SHIRES INCOME PLC
56	TEMPLE BAR INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
57	TEMPLETON EMERGING MARKETS INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
58	TR EUROPEAN GROWTH TRUST PLC
59	TR PROPERTY INVESTMENT TRUST PLC
60	VALUE AND INCOME TRUST PLC